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**ANNOTATION AND ANALYSIS OF
LEXICAL CATEGORIES IN L2 ITALIAN**

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To my family and friends

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Glossary

1	First Person
2	Second Person
3	Third Person
ADJ	Adjective
ADV	Adverb
CALL	Computer Assisted Language Learning
F	Feminine
FLA	First Language Acquisition
GER	Germal
GERUN	Gerund
IL	Interlanguage
IMPS	Impersonal
IND	Indicative
INF	Infinitive
ITA	Italian
L1	First Language
L2	Second Language

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M	Masculine
MDS	Multidimensional Scaling
NL	Native Language
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NOUN	Noun
NP	Noun Phrase
NS	Native Speaker
PL	Plural
PoS	Part of Speech
PRS	Present
PST	Past
PTCP	participle
REFL	Reflexive
SG	Singular
SLA	Second Language Acquisition
SPA	Spanish
TL	Target Language
VER	Verb
VP	Verb Phrase

1

Introduction

1.1 Goal

The goal of this thesis is to investigate whether certain morpho-syntactic peculiarities of Italian interlanguage can be recognized and studied by analyzing the characteristics and the distribution of lexical categories.

This work will deal in the first place with the theoretical issues involved in defining what is meant by lexical categories in general. We will evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of a formal vs a functional definition with particular regard to the problems of interlanguage (Chapter 2).

Secondly some problems concerning the theory and methodology of SLA research will be outlined (Chapter 3): the present work will evaluate corpus data using quantitative methods developed in computational linguistics, corpus stylistics, corpus analysis in general.

The bulk of the analysis will be divided into three chapters, dealing with the investigation of inherent categories in interlanguage by means of clustering techniques (Chapter 4), the problem of annotation of target categories in interlanguage (Chapter 5) and the analysis of differences in the distribution of target categories (Chapter 6).

Our aim is to show that:

1. quantitative corpus analysis is applicable with non trivial results to interlanguage texts, despite the fact that the data is less homogeneous and generally more problematic;

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2. when dealing with interlanguage data it is necessary to distinguish between target-categories, which are the categories of the target language, and interlanguage inherent categories (categories recognizable in the language sample that is analyzed);
3. source categories can vary from sample to sample, and form different sets with different degrees of homogeneity, while target categories do not vary since they refer to a very specific linguistic system and they form the only possible tagset for an annotation that can be used for comparative analysis of different data samples.

1.2 Key Acquisitional Concepts

This thesis deals with the analysis of texts produced by non native speakers of Italian, that is to say adults acquiring Italian as their second language in a spontaneous or semi-spontaneous way via contact with an Italian linguistic environment.

It is therefore necessary to introduce a general acquisitional framework and to briefly discuss some key acquisitional concepts, before proceeding with our more specific topics.

When a person learns a language during early infancy usually by transmission from his or her caretakers, this person becomes a native speaker (NS) of this language which will be his or her first or native language (L1). The process of spontaneously acquiring an L1 is called first language acquisition (FLA). Of course a person may acquire more than one L1 and become an NS of more than one language. When a person learns a language after puberty, by being exposed to a linguistic environment different from his or her L1, this person is said to be acquiring a second language (L2) and the process is called second language acquisition (SLA). “L1” and “L2” are relational terms: one person’s L1 may another person’s L2. In the field of acquisition, more specifically, reference is often made to two different L1s: the L1 of the learner, and the L1 of the linguistic environment in which the learner is immersed. To avoid ambiguity this term shall be used in this work to refer exclusively to the linguistic inventory of a specific person or group of people. In terms of the process of acquisition, we shall speak of native language (NL) to refer to the learner’s L1 and of target language (TL) to refer to the learner’s L2 as it is spoken and used by its native speakers.

The terms NL and TL imply that the learner is moving from one linguistic system to another viewed as a target which may or may not be attained. The linguistic systems

that the learner goes through in the process of acquisition are called interlanguages (ILs). More specifically, according to Tarone (1994):

The term interlanguage (IL) was introduced by the American linguist Larry Selinker to refer to the linguistic system evidenced when an adult second language learner attempts to express meanings in the language being learned. The interlanguage is viewed as a separate linguistic system, clearly different from both the learner's 'native language' (NL) and the 'target language' (TL) being learned, but linked to both NL and TL by interlingual identifications in the perception of the learner.

Interlanguage is therefore an abstract term, denoting a class of linguistic systems. The plurality of interlanguages is due to 3 different reasons:

- the number of potential target languages, coinciding with the number of existing languages (there are interlanguages of Italian, of English, of Chinese, of Norwegian, etc).
- the number of different individuals acquiring an L2: the differences in each individual (motivation, background, L1, ...) result in differences in their individual interlanguages.
- the different stages that each individual goes through in the process of acquisition.

Ideally, the description of an interlanguage would imply describing a single system S1, used by learner X at time T1. From the practical point of view, though, it is unthinkable to collect enough information about S1 before X moves to S2; in fact X's massive exposure to - and practice of - the target language caused by elicitation might even accelerate his or her evolution from S1 to S2.

As a result, any analysis of IL can only be the analysis of a subset of the class of possible interlanguages. If it contains only samples of ILs of Italian, one might analyze the characteristics that are common to ILs of Italian. If it selects ILs by the gender of the learner, it might allow us to study the difference between male and female interlinguistic systems. If it's a random sample, it might allow us to generalize over the features common to all ILs.

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Subsets of ILs are usually selected by the learner's L1 or by stage of acquisition. The idea behind this choice is that most of the similarities that can be found between different ILs are due either to the effect of the learner's L1 or to the level of acquisition. The similarities are due in the first case to the transfer of characteristics from the L1 to the IL, and in the second case to a set of cognitive, linguistic and functional constraints that predetermine specific paths of acquisition.

It is often the case that researchers who are convinced of the importance of the level factor tend to disregard the effect of transfer and vice versa. We do not presume to offer a solution to this problem. What we hope to do is to be able to offer a possible method of investigation. In chapter 6 we will illustrate a possible way of measuring syntactic distance between IL samples together with a set of statistical tools that enable us to evaluate whether the measured distance is significantly higher with respect to the distance between random sets.

2

Theoretical Background

2.1 What we mean by the term *lexical category*

In linguistics the term *category* is often used to refer to different concepts. It can be applied both to concepts such as gender or number, as well as to noun or verb. In the current work the term *lexical category* will be used to refer to items belonging to the class of nouns, verbs, etc. These shall be the object of our investigation.

It is intuitively easy to grasp why gender, number, and case are grammatical objects that cannot be grouped together with nouns, adjectives and adverbs.

Let us try to give a more explicit definition of the differences between these two sets by considering the scheme 2.1 in Ramat (1999), derived from Pullum (1996)

As we can see the term *category* is used for the items in the first column of this schema.

In Ramat (1999) this terminological distinction is justified by the asymmetry between columns 1-2 and 2-3 respectively. While an *indicative* is a *mood*, and *feminine* is a *gender*, it cannot be said that a *gender* is a *noun*. A noun can *have* a gender, but so can an adjective, and in some languages so can a verb.

While the definition of a *feature* consists in listing all of its possible values, the definition of a *category* is much more complicated. Two categories can have identical features in a language but be nonetheless distinct in other respects. For instance adjectives and nouns in Italian share the features of ‘gender’ and ‘number’, but they differ for the features of ‘definiteness’ and ‘degree’.

In the present work we shall follow this denomination and use the term *lexical category* uniquely for elements from the first column in the scheme, and the term

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CATEGORY	features	values
VERB	tense	present
		imperfect
		...
	mood	indic.
		subj.
		opt.
		...
	aspect	...
	number	...

NOUN	gender	...

DET.	number	...

...

Table 2.1: Categories vs features

feature for whatever is used to define a category; later in this chapter we shall see that morphological features such as gender and case are not the only kinds of features (others being position and root).

Syntactic categories, *word classes* and *parts of speech* are terms often used as synonyms for *lexical categories*. In this work only the term *lexical category* shall be used to refer to the aforementioned concept. On a closer analysis, only the term *word class* can be considered as a pure synonym, while the term *syntactic category* should be correctly used as a hypernym, to refer to both the non terminal (phrasal: NP, VP, ...) and the terminal (lexical: noun, verb, ...) terms of a syntactic tree. Finally, we reserve *Part of Speech (PoS)* to refer to the specific label that is applied to words in a text that is annotated at a syntactic level. The use of a different term is justified by the fact that differences between a set of lexical categories and their PoS label counterpart are possible due to practical reasons ¹.

2.2 The definition of lexical category

1. how many lexical categories are there? what are they?
2. at what level of analysis does the classification apply? Are categories properties of the syntagms, of roots, or of instantiated words?
3. do open classes like nouns and adjectives have the same status as closed classes (like prepositions and conjunctions)?
4. which features assign words in a text to a given category? how do we recognize a noun from a verb? an adjective from an adverb?
5. are these criteria formal or functional (semantic/pragmatically related)?
6. is there a universal set of categories, or does each language have a specific set of categories which is then *language specific*?

¹PoS tagsets examples can be seen in E. By way of anticipation we can say that PoS tagsets are often very ample, and articulated in subcategories that consist in category plus a specific feature: for instance the PoS tag VER:fin:pres indicates an element belonging to category ‘verb’ and having the feature ‘tense’ equal to ‘present’

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These questions have a long tradition and have been amply investigated throughout the history of linguistics. Here we shall discuss some of the answers from an acquisitional perspective. A very neutral starting point can be a general encyclopedic definition such as Anward (2006) (see also Haspelmath 2001):

The word-class system of a language is a classification of the individual elements that make it up, viz., words, in terms of properties that determine their use in syntax and their contribution to meaning.

In fact the idea of grouping words into classes is not new. Ancient Greek grammarians were the first to develop the idea of 8 Parts of Speech: Of these categories four are open sets (noun, verb, participle, and adverb), and four are closed sets (article, preposition, pronoun and conjunction).² This classification was held to be universal but, significantly enough, when Roman scholars tried to apply it to Latin, they had to first face a problem of interoperability due to the fact that Latin was lacking the category of articles, which was substituted by interjection, to preserve the traditional number of eight categories (Priscian, *Institutiones grammaticae*, 6th century AD). Finally, in modern times, the participle was substituted by the adjective as an intermediate class between verb and noun; thus the canonical set (noun, verb, adjective, adverb, article, preposition, pronoun, conjunction) was established such as we can still find in dictionaries and traditional grammars.

Modern research in linguistic typology has shown that a much broader variety exists in the sets of lexical categories amongst the world's languages. Articles for instance are not very common in non European languages: in Dryer (1989, 85) articles are present in only one third of the languages in the sample; at the same time new classes, such as classifiers or converbs, have been identified and are found in a significant number of languages.

What does it mean though to say of two languages that they both have articles, or that both lack converbs? In order to be able to claim that both English and German have articles we need to have a definition of article that is valid in both languages.

²Although the distinction of words into categories had been known since the classical era, the Greek system of eight categories was finally fixed only in the *Tékhnē grammatiké*, a treatise of uncertain attribution, written in the 2nd century BC.

The class of articles is a closed set. This means that a simple way of defining articles is by enumerating them. This however is unhelpful in determining what English and German articles have in common that would justify calling them by the same name.

As a matter of fact, in current linguistic theory there is no generally agreed-upon classification scheme that can apply to all languages, and many linguists argue that the formal distinctions between parts of speech must be made within the framework of a specific language or language family, and should not be carried over to other languages or language families.

In the next few paragraphs we shall see some possible solutions to the problem, and we will argue that the choice of a specific definition for lexical categories can only be motivated by the kind of analysis and research to which it is then applied.

2.2.1 Formal language specific definition

When investigating the nature of lexical categories, the first question to answer is at which level do lexical categories apply? When talking about word classes, the complex problem of the definition of word is called upon. The first question to answer here is: which words? Are we talking about entries in a dictionary? Of words in isolation?

In fact lexical categories can relate to different levels of analysis (Lyons 1977, Ježek 2005):

- lexical categories can be properties of **roots** (when we talk about nominal vs verbal roots),
- lexical categories can be properties of **lemmas** (when root is affected by transcategorisation, for instance by derivational morphology, lemmas with the same root can be assigned to different categories),
- lexical categories can be properties of **types** (when we say that a certain inflected form is identifiable as, say, a verb due to its inflectional morphology),
- lexical categories can be properties of **token** (when we say that some types can occur as adjectives or as nouns depending on the context).

It is clear that the levels interact in cascade, in that each level inherits the categorization from the upper level, but has some (limited) capacity for changing it. A root can have a prototypical category, by effect of its semantics, but transcategorization can

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take place at the level of the lemma (by using derivational morphology lemmas with the same root can be assigned to different categories); lemmas in their turn can be subject to conversion and change their category at the type or form level; types finally can still occur as instances of two different categories depending on the occurrence (token level). Let's observe the following examples:

(2.1) I saw a man with a **green** scarf

(2.2) **Green** was another difficult color to obtain

(2.3) 50 ways to **green** your business!

In these examples according to the dictionary, the same word, “green”, instantiates 3 different lexical categories: adjective, noun, verb. The morphological phenomenon of conversion, which is so common in the English language, makes it possible to move a lexical root from one class to another without any addition of explicit linguistic material. In this case the only feature that allows us to recognize the lexical category is the position in which the word occurs.

Not all words are necessarily ambiguous at the token level, still the fact that some words are ambiguous leads us to the conclusion that lexical categories should be considered as properties of tokens: words used together with other words to form meaningful sentences.

Given this assumption, the distributional method, which can be considered a syntactic application of Harris's distributional structure (Harris 1954), is probably the most simple way of finding groups of words given a huge corpus, or given data from a native speaker capable of producing grammaticality judgements (we are not problematizing the difference between corpus evidence and introspective evidence here).

A distributional analysis may start with a simple sentence:

(2.4) *The boy kicks the ball.*
1 2 3 4 5.

and turn this sentence into a pattern:

(2.5) *The boy kicks the x.*
1 2 3 4 5.

2.2 The definition of lexical category

All words that are found to occur in position 5 can be considered to belong to the same class as *ball*. Further investigation will show that this class of words (let's call it A) also occurs uniformly in other contexts, such as:

(2.6) *The boy takes the A.*
1 2 3 4 5

and this can lead us to discover another pattern, with position 3 as x:

(2.7) *The boy x the A.*
1 2 3 4 5

and so on.

Although this process can only be described as a theoretical abstraction, it is true that positional tests are often used to determine the degree of nominality, adjectivity or verbality of certain words (word types) in relation to the contexts in which they can grammatically occur (see for example of the discussion of English “-ing” forms in Aarts 2007).

Position is very important, but other formal criteria can be found to distinguish words:

(2.8) When fall frost approaches, home gardeners can pick unripe **green** peppers and **green** tomatoes to ripen indoors

(2.9) It was printed in seven different passes: two different oranges, two different **greens**, two blacks and one gray

(2.10) If the northern forests are **greening**, they may already be absorbing carbon

(2.11) Consciously, under my attention, she **reddened**

Adjectives in English do not inflect. Thus the presence of an “s” suffixed to the lexical root “green” rules out the possibility that the word is an adjective even if it still does not allow us to choose between a verb (3rd person singular) or a noun (plural). Other morphological material, such as the “-ing” suffix, can be evidence (though not

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conclusive) of verbality. Finally derivational affixes like “-en” added to an adjectival root, output verbs by definition.

From the formal point of view it is therefore possible to assign the words of a text to different parts of speech by combining information about their root, their distribution and their morphological behavior.³

Root, morphology and distribution are therefore the features (as in the schema 2.1) which define the set of lexical categories for a given language. The value and the weight of the features may be, as often happens, a matter of debate, but this framework is commonly accepted at an intralinguistic level.

Problems arise on an interlinguistic level however, when languages are compared. The features defining a category can be very different from language to language. Adjectives, e.g., can have a different distributional behaviour even in two cognate languages like French and Italian. German adjectives inflect by number, gender and case, whereas English adjectives don’t inflect at all. How can we then presume to refer to the same objects when talking about adjectives in languages X and Y?

2.2.2 Universal definitions

Traditionally (Lyons 1977, 441) lexical categories have been given not only a formal definition, but also a semantic one: nouns denote objects, verbs denote actions, adjectives denote properties. This simple definition can be easily falsified by the existence of nouns denoting actions (*explosions*), verbs denoting properties (*redden*). Other more sophisticated solutions to the problem have also been tried.

In Langacker (1987) categories instantiate a **schema** and have a **prototype**⁴:

³As a matter of fact, recent empirical studies (Farmer, Christiansen & Monaghan 2006) seem to indicate that, at least for English, the main categories of nouns and verbs are distinguished also by a series of phonological typicalities; in other words “phonological properties of words cluster together coherently within lexical categories”; the same is probably true for prosodic features. This means that children may be driven to distinguish lexical categories of words even before they are aware of their meaning.

⁴Following Taylor (2006) the definition of prototype that is used in linguistics goes back to the studies of the psychologist Eleanor Rosch (Rosch 1978) who “presented experimental results that demonstrated that the categories designated by words such as ‘fruit’ may indeed be understood in terms of ‘good examples,’ or ‘prototypes,’ whereby entities are assimilated to the category on the basis of their similarity to the prototype, rather than through their sharing in a set of common, defining features.” Rosch’s definition of prototype has been popularized among linguists by the works of Lakoff and Taylor among others, but it was not completely new to linguistics, since Ross (1973) had already argued that “some

2.2 The definition of lexical category

- Nouns designate regions and have concrete objects as prototypes
- Verbs profile processes and have actions as prototypes

Verbs like *to explore* designate a process. Nouns like *explosion*, though not referring to a concrete object, instantiate a nominal schema by referring to the whole sequence of the action as if it were an object.

The idea of using prototypes to reach a universal definition of lexical categories has been further developed in Croft (1991).

Croft identifies universal prototypes for noun (reference to an object), verb (predication of an action), and adjective (modification by a property). Language-specific categories are derived from the universal prototypes by using the formal criterion of **markedness**.

According to the following schema (Croft 1991, 53):

	Reference	Modification	Predication
Objects	unmarked	marked	marked
Properties	marked	unmarked	marked
Actions	marked	marked	unmarked

a certain class of words in a specific language instantiates the universal category X if its members occur in a less marked form when expressing the prototypical semantic/functional relation for X. Therefore nouns in English will present less marked features when expressing reference to objects (e.g. “house”) rather than to actions (e.g. “explosion”, here the markedness is expressed by the presence of the derivational suffix).

The universality of the definition is given by the fact that the prototypical pairing between reference and objects, modification and properties, predication and actions remains the same and allows us to identify at least the 3 major classes of nouns, adjectives and verbs in every language by checking the markedness criterion⁵.

nouns were ‘nounier’ than others, in that some exhibited the full range of noun-like properties and others exhibited fewer noun-like properties”.

⁵In a subsequent work, Croft (2001) opts for a radical constructionist theory of grammar; categories are not the primary unit of grammar, but are derived from constructions, that is from syntactic templates that are paired with conventionalized semantic and pragmatic content. This does not change the prototype-based definition for nouns, verbs and adjectives, which can be easily seen as constructions, namely as the prototypical constructions denoting the propositional acts of reference to an object, predication of an action and modification by a property (see, chapter 3 pp. 63-108). Thus in the Radical Constructions approach as well as in previous works, the universal definition of lexical categories re-

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Note that Croft's solution should not necessarily be seen as an alternative to a formal (language specific) definition of lexical categories. When studying a new language, the researcher might first produce a language specific classification of words, and then use the prototype/markedness criterion to apply a universal label to each class, thus making a comparison with other languages possible.

A language-specific formal definition seems to be therefore sufficient when addressing questions concerning the behavior of a specific language, (e.g., when analyzing the distribution of word classes by tagging Parts of Speech in texts), but a functional or semantic definition of categories is necessary when comparing different languages (Haspelmath 2007).

A similar approach can be found in Hengeveld (1992). Here the definition of lexical categories is based on the syntactic roles that words belonging to each category can fill without further morphologic or syntactic measures being taken. More specifically (p. 58):

- Verbs have a predicative use *only*, without further measures being taken
- Nouns can be used as the head of a term, without further measures being taken
- Adjectives can be used as the modifier of a nominal head, without further measures being taken
- Adverbs can be used as the modifier of a non nominal head, without further measures being taken

This definition parallels the Croftian one in that the “*without further measures being taken*” is not too distant from *unmarkedness*, whereas the distinguishing functions are not dissimilar to the prototypical functions⁶.

mains based on the concept of semantic-functional prototypes, and its identification in language specific constructs still relies on the concept of markedness.

⁶Hengeveld is very clear in stressing that the notion of distinguishing function is quite different from the notion of prototype. In my opinion though the notion of prototype that is implied in Hengeveld (1992, 59) is quite limited, being uniquely connected with frequency: “the predicative use of adjectives, which would generally be considered non-prototypical, is far more frequent than their attributive use [...] . Even if the attributive use of adjectives is not their prototypical use, it still is the use that distinguishes them from predicates of other classes”.

An important point in Hengeveld's definition is the idea that languages do not necessarily have a distinct category for each function. Languages that display a full set of 4 main categories are called specialized languages. As for the non specialized languages, they can be divided into those in which a single part of speech may be used in different functions, and those in which for certain functions a part of speech is lacking; languages of the first kind are called flexible (like Quechua, in which there is a single class that cover the functions of nouns and adjectives) while languages of the second kind are called rigid (like Mandarin Chinese, which lacks the class of adjectives, and uses verbs as modifiers).

Another crucial point that distinguishes Hengeveld's definition is the idea that - unlike in Croft - the lexical categories are not all at the same level: verbs occupy a higher position among the other classes, in that they require obligatory marking for any non-predicative use.

In the following chapter we are going to see how this idea can be used (Bernini 2008*b*) to model the acquisition of categories in L2.

2.2.3 Categorical grammar vs. deep structure grammar

In the last paragraph we have discussed some definitions of lexical categories. But another more radical question must be addressed: why are lexical categories so important?

A possible answer to this question is that they are necessary to the description of the grammar of a language, because they allow us to express the fact that only certain categories can occupy certain places in the sentence and have a certain syntactic function. We can call this bottom up perspective categorical grammar: the recognition of lexical categories is somehow a presupposition of the recognition of higher level structures (just as, in a more practical NLP approach, PoS tagging is a prerequisite for parsing).

This perspective can be turned upside down (deep structure grammar): it's the deep phrasal structure of the sentence that determines which distributional and morphological features the single lexical items can take. This kind of approach requires very strong *a priori* assumptions about the inherent structure of human language, such as those offered by Chomskian generative grammar.

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Still until Baker (2003) most of what the Principle and Parameters (P and P) tradition of Generative Syntax had to say about lexical categories was that they were distinguished by having different values for the two binary distinctive features +/- N and +/- V in the following way (Chomsky 1970):

- (2.12) **a** +N - V = noun
b -N + V = verb
c +N +V = adjective
d -N -V adposition (preposition and postposition)

This definition is quite circular (what are the features N and V, if not something like “nominality” and “verbality”) and does not refer to the syntactic functions that lexical categories implement. As lamented by Baker (2003, 1-2) “this theory is widely recognized to have almost no content in practice. The feature system is not well integrated into the framework as a whole, in that there are few or no principles that refer to these features or their values”. According to Mark Baker:

A serious consequence of the underdevelopment of this aspect of syntactic theory is that it leaves us ill equipped to do typology. The literature contains many claims that one language has a different stock of lexical categories from another. In many cases, these claims have caused controversy within the descriptive traditions of the language families in question. Since there is no substantive generative theory of lexical categories, we have no way to assess these claims or resolve these controversies. (p. 3)

Baker’s own insightful work is motivated by the idea of finding a universal definition for lexical categories that relies on the principles of UG. In Baker’s proposal, only 3 main categories are considered to be universal ⁷:

- verbs as licensers of subjects
- nouns as bearers of a referential index
- adjectives as neither nouns nor verbs

⁷Adpositions, which were present in the early Chomskian framework, are downgraded to functional categories.

This three-way distinction among lexical categories is claimed to be universal among all natural languages and a very in depth analysis is given on how to recognize the three categories in different word languages. What is more interesting for us here is the solution that Baker gives to the question of the level at which lexical categories should be recognized. The question is explicitly raised in the concluding part of the book:

What exactly bears a category? Is it fundamentally roots that are categorized as nouns, verbs and adjectives, or is it stems, or inflected words, or the minimal leaves of a syntactic tree, or the maximal X° s, or even larger phrases? For which of these linguistic units is category inherent, and for which is it derivative or even undefined? A logically similar and partially related set of questions concerns whether the category distinctions are fundamentally syntactic, semantic or morphological in nature. One intriguing (and maddening) aspect of this topic is that whether something is a noun, verb, or adjective seems to have relevance in all three of these domains. Yet presumably the category distinctions inhere fundamentally in one domain and then project into the others; otherwise it would be a kind of coincidence that parallel categorial distinctions exist in each domain. Which domain, then, is the most fundamental one in this respect? (Baker 2003, 264)

Baker denies that category distinctions can be morphologically or lexically based, and claims that the correct approach is a syntax-oriented one: “it is syntactic phrases as a whole that bear the category. Phrase structure also determines how complex words are created and inflected by way of processing like incorporating and morphological merger. Roots are inserted into functional contexts wherever they make sense, and our judgement about the categories of roots are derived from that” (Baker 2003, 265–266).

Though being a strictly formal proposal, what this framework has in common with functional-typological frameworks is the necessity of distinguishing a subgroup of lexical categories, usually coinciding with the open classes that must necessarily be provided with an Interlinguistic definition thus allowing for typological comparisons.

In some broad sense, as the author himself recognizes, this approach, too, is a functional one, even if the functions here are syntactic ones, rather than pragmatic ones. It is important to underline the difference between this kind of approach and a plainly positional one: it is one thing to talk about the position that a lexical root

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can occupy in a syntactic environment, and a very different one to simply categorize a word “by the company it keeps” (Firth 1957). In the first case a knowledge of the deep structure of the language is implied, while in the second case only the surface structure is taken into account.

The main problem with this proposal is the impossibility of applying it outside the framework of universal grammar. Even assuming that all languages share the same syntactic functions, it seems quite problematic to apply this kind of definition to the study of interlanguage, since it is certainly not trivial to determine *a priori* the level of access to syntax that adult learners have (in the next chapter something more will be said about the generative position on SLA). This definition only captures the syntactic side of lexical categories, while lexical categories are at the interface of syntax and lexicon (in fact they can be seen as the part of lexicon that is accessible to syntax) and is ill suited when the distribution of lexical categories is meant to be used as a device to formulate hypothesis on the nature of syntax.

2.2.4 Fuzziness

Fuzziness is another theoretical problem that needs to be dealt with in the definition of lexical categories. In the generative tradition categories are defined by binary oppositions, which produce sharp boundaries. The cognitive-functional framework instead defines categories by prototypes, and generally accepts the idea that categories may fade one into another. Still prototype-based definitions do not necessarily imply fuzziness. Aarts (2007) very acutely distinguishes between intracategorical and intercategorical gradients.

This distinction corresponds to two different theoretical positions with respect to categories: the first position assumes only that each category has a prototype, and therefore has members that are more prototypical than others (in other words it has a center and a periphery), for instance gerund or infinite forms with respect to the category of verbs. The second - stronger - position claims that categories may fade one into another, in such a way that peripheral members can be said to belong partly to one category and partly to another: terms denoting colors or numerals in many languages could be seen as belonging both to the category of nouns and the category of adjective.

In Aarts' view only the first position is acceptable, but if we assume the view that lexical categories are properties of tokens, and not of types, there is nothing problematic

in the idea that the same form can sometimes be used as an adjective and sometimes as a noun. In fact, if we follow a plain formal definition, the problem of deciding which lexical category a token belongs to can be reduced to the problem of which lexical category the token behaves like. The formal traits of a token are not hints that enable us to discover the hidden lexical category, they are the features that define the category.

2.3 Lexical categories in IL: problems

Let's now consider the problems outlined in the last paragraph from the point of view of study of interlanguage.

- which definition of lexical category is more adequate to the analysis of interlanguage?
- when studying the lexical categories in interlanguages of Italian, should one rely on a universal, functional definition or on a parochial formal one, derived from the word classes of the target language?
- which formal or functional features are relevant in assigning categories to the words of an IL text, if any category can be recognized at all?
- which features prevail upon the others in case of ambiguity?

Here the question of ambiguity is a crucial one in that it implies two levels of ambiguity. On the one hand we have the ambiguity arising from the conflict between different clues for attributing an item to one category or another; and on the other the ambiguity derived from the inherent ambiguity of the features themselves. In the first case the ambiguity is considered from the external point of view of the observer who is trying to find the best method to discriminate between two existing categories. In the second case the ambiguity is considered from the internal point of view, as intrinsic to the phenomenon, since it can be the case that no identifiable categories exist in IL or that they significantly differ from the ones of TL. Let us analyze some examples of noun-verb ambiguity:

The following example is taken from interview 02 to informant MK (Corpus Pavia⁸); Mk is talking about the members of his family:

⁸The Pavia Corpus is published in Andorno (2001) and described in Andorno & Bernini (2003)

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(2.13) \Mk\ eh ++ mh - la madre ++ del figli=
\It\ =mh mh
\Mk\ non hai lavora= non hai lavora

In 2.13 the main ambiguity occurs between the form and function of the token word *lavora* which has the function of a referent but the morphological form of a 3rd person singular verb. Further ambiguity is to be found between the formal traits, since the lexical root is both nominal and verbal, but the context in the TL allows either a noun or a past participle. The same problem can be observed in the next example (from MK 05), where the informant is describing the process required to obtain the status of political refugee in Italy

(2.14) \Mk\ mh lui tielefo:no (telefono) con - noi=

In 2.14, *telefono* has probably a predicative function, the context is verbal (following a pronoun), but the morphology is nominal (due to the lack of agreement with the preceding pronoun).

In the next example (from MK 05) a trip to Florence is described; from the context it is clear that the cost of the train ticket is discussed:

(2.15) \Mk\ tutta la programma - noi non -
solo -
noi - noi paghiamo solo da: eh pas/pas /pasagio
\It\ ah
ho capito
\Mk\ vado e ritorno

In 2.15 the category of *vado* and *ritorno* cannot be assigned without problems, because of a conflict between different features; the presence of conjunction *e* requires that both of the coordinated elements have the same category; *vado* shows a purely verbal root and morphology, whereas *ritorno* can be a noun or a verb, dependent on context. This ‘conflictual’ instance of token *vado* can be compared with the one in 2.16 (MK 05). Here *vado* seems to behave like a verb, even though its occurrence (finite verb following a modal verb) is *non target like*.

(2.16) \Mk\ eh - io non voglio vado a titti/e a: agli altri^: ci:

2.3 Lexical categories in IL: problems

These examples show how ambiguous the attribution of categories in IL can be, no matter which criteria are selected. Logically, one can imagine two possible reasons for this phenomenon. In the first place the informant can rely on a different syntactic system to produce his utterance; a system that has its own set of categories, with different morphological, distributional and lexical features, and that does not coincide with the system of the TL. Another, more fundamental reason is that learners at early stages of acquisition do not yet have any syntactic system whatsoever in place.

Givón (1985) claims in his work that linguistic utterances can follow two different modes.

Pragmatic mode, characterized by:

- a** topic, comment structure
- b** loose coordination
- c** slow rate of delivery
- d** small chunks under one intonation contour
- e** lower noun/verb ratio in discourse with more simple verbs
- f** no use of grammatical morphology

Syntactic mode, characterized by:

- a** subject, predicate structure
- b** tight subordination
- c** fast rate of delivery
- d** large chunks under one intonation contour
- e** higher noun/verb ratio in discourse, with more complex verbs
- f** extensive use of grammatical morphology

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This distinction between pragmatic and syntactic modes seems to fit quite well into the evolution of IL varieties, more specifically to pre-basic and basic varieties (Giacalone Ramat 1993, Klein & Perdue 1997). This means that, at least in the early stages of IL evolution, morphological distinctions are not yet in place and the use and distribution of lexical material is almost exclusively determined by semantic and pragmatic constraints. No inherent set of categories can be recognized.

2.4 Categories in interlanguage: form to function approach

In the last paragraph the reasons for the non convergence of form and function in IL categories (a convergence that is expected when compared to the TL categories) has been discussed. It is time here to draw some consequences from the methodological point of view. If form and function are two separate and possibly contrasting levels, the researcher can choose between two possible modes of analysis:

- group words presenting similar formal traits and check whether they also present similar functions
- group words by similar functions and see whether they also present similar formal traits

In this work we choose a form-to-function approach, for two reasons:

- from the practical point of view, as we shall see in the next chapters, it is easier to implement an algorithm that groups the words according to some set of formal traits
- from the theoretical point of view, annotating the function creates a higher risk of misinterpretation, whereas a formal analysis seems to be less biased by specific theoretical presuppositions

This research will therefore opt for a formal definition of lexical category. Categories shall be therefore assigned using the following criteria:

Lexical root Lexical roots can restrict the possible options for assignment of a single word or even determine the category of a word without any need of other hints (*bell-*, in Italian is an adjectival root).

2.4 Categories in interlanguage: form to function approach

Derivational morphology Derivational affixes are explicit signs of recategorization of a word.

Inflection Inflectional affixes are the expression of features like number, gender, tense, which only apply to certain categories and not to others (*-avano*, in Italian is an exclusively verbal suffix)

Position The context in which a word occurs is often the final clue to disambiguating the category of some words (in the Italian phrase *il + lavoro*, only the position can rule out a possible assignment to the category verb of the lexically and morphologically ambiguous token *lavoro*).

As for the object of classification, it seems obvious that the annotation pertains to instantiated tokens in context. Any *a priori* assignment of categories to roots or uninstantiated types would be a source of possible ambiguity, and at the same time extending the domain of POS-tagging to the more complex clausal level seems to imply too much about what we know of the learner's syntactic competence. Flat relations of proximity seem to be more useful clues for providing information concerning the categories in IL.

As for the distinction between open and closed classes, for the moment we do not intend to treat them differently. It should be emphasised however that closed classes make up the majority of instances in a corpus, and can be therefore seen as the context in which the classification of open classes may take shape.

Finally, the question as to whether categories can or cannot be fuzzy must also be analyzed from the point of view of IL studies. It may be possible that target categories possess sharp and clear boundaries. Nonetheless, when comparing the IL system of categories, which is just approaching the TL system, we may find it useful to speak of levels of confidence that this IL token is a noun in the TL sense, without in this way making any claim as to the real substance of the inherent categories of both TL and of the level of interlanguage in object, when considered per se.

The last thing that remains to be discussed is the choice of the specific set of features that we shall follow for our categorization. We have argued that interlanguage is not one system, but a potentially infinite set of systems, which may or may not have some similarities with each other. It is therefore impossible to define a formal set of features that can apply to all interlanguages.

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When the research aims at analysing a sample of interlanguages with the same TL, two possible solutions can be envisaged:

- choosing a target oriented approach and tagging each word in IL according to its nearest TL category
- choosing a source oriented approach and grouping words by their inherent formal similarities

The first type of approach is at risk of committing the comparative fallacy (Bley-Vroman 1983) by applying a set of categories which may not be optimal, but it has the advantage of keeping the comparative fallacy under control by explicitly declaring it, and is the only method that will allow some sort of interoperability when comparing heterogeneous varieties of IL with each other and with the target language. The set of native Italian lexical categories may not be the best set to represent a specific IL, but it is the set at which each IL of Italian “aims” at and is therefore the best possible solution when many different varieties have to be annotated with the same PoS set.

The second type of approach allows for an independent, non target-biased description of IL, but can only be applied to a relatively homogeneous sample of IL varieties.

In this work both approaches shall be attempted. In chapter 4 a method for category detection will be used to detect inherent word classes in a corpus. In chapter 5 a possible solution to the automatic annotation of target Parts of Speech will be introduced and used to conduct qualitative and quantitative (chapter 6) analyses of IL corpora. The theoretical presuppositions that have been discussed in the present chapter have methodologically operative consequences concerning corpus tagging, selection of language specific PoS tagsets, tagging methods and algorithms for corpus analysis. These shall be discussed in the next chapters.

3

Second Language Acquisition Research

In the last chapter some theoretical background to the problem of lexical categories has been given, and we argued in favor of a formal definition of lexical categories and for the advantages of keeping formal and functional levels separated in the analysis of interlanguage. In this chapter some general issues shall be discussed concerning the theoretical premises and the methodology of Second Language Acquisition Research.

First of all some key issues concerning Second Language Acquisition will be discussed. Then a brief introduction to the subject of corpora and corpus analysis will be given, with specific attention paid to small SLA corpora.

3.1 Theories of language acquisition

Just as with theories of First Language Acquisition, any theory of Second Language Acquisition faces the choice between the generative paradigm, which posits the existence of an independent and innate language acquisition device, and other positions that try to explain the emergence of linguistic competence on the basis of other general cognitive faculties.

While the generative framework is a more homogeneous paradigm, the opposing theories show a broader variety of positions. What they have in common is the idea that the specific properties of language, and of syntax in particular, can be explained with reference to external, more general principles, such as the general cognitive abilities of the human brain, the specific constraints due to processing limitations and the functional principles of successful communication.

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In order to describe where the two approaches differ let's see how they model the acquisition of lexical categories by children. It is known that from an early age children seem to be very sensitive to the lexical categories of the words they use. Experiments show that children are able to assign lexical categories to made-up words, inferring them from their formal features (Farmer et al. 2006). How is this possible?

The generative explanation is that the main categories are universal and the language acquisition device is thus programmed to categorize certain words in a certain way. The fact that the lexical categories seem to correspond to a certain semantic paradigm (actions for verbs, objects for nouns, etc.) does not enter into the explanation. It may be possible that specific semantic or functional constraints have shaped the evolution of this specific feature in the human linguistic capacity. But no matter what forces have made the Universal Grammar what it is today, and no matter whether those forces are still active now or not, it's the Universal Grammar that makes the language what it is; and every feature of human language can be explained with sole reference to the UG, and without any reference to other external principles (Newmeyer 2005, see in particular pp. 167-172).

The main objection to this explanation is based upon the claim that it is unnecessary to posit the existence of a specific device for language in the brain when more general principles are sufficient to explain the regularities found among the world's languages. With reference to lexical categories, the fact that lexical items are assigned to different categories by young children with a lexicon of no more than 100 words can be seen as a result of how neural networks store information in the brain. Specifically, our brains have a tendency to produce generalizations over data, and elements possessing certain features tend to induce a specific attraction towards other similar elements. When children are exposed to words they register their phonological patterns first, and learn to divide them into clusters accordingly. Subsequently, they become aware of positional information, as well as of meaning, and these features seem to reinforce the existing clusters: words with a certain phonological pattern tend to occur frequently in certain contexts and also tend to be associated with a specific meaning or function. In this way the classificational framework becomes more and more stable and exceptions can be taken into account by the further discovery, by the child, of morphological features. And it's not only inflectional morphology which provides further clues for assigning words to specific configurations, but also derivational morphology, by providing the

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means to re-categorize a word, thus offering a way to readjust the system according to syntactic and semantic pressures.

At the end of the process of acquisition, the child will be able to recognize that a certain syntactic structure requires a specific lexical category with a certain meaning and will be able to provide the right combination. It is of course natural that a better, improved, knowledge of the categories of the native language is the basis for acquiring knowledge concerning more complex syntactic structures (Tomasello 2000).

Among those who hold to this anti-innatist paradigm some divergences arise as to the nature of grammar: for most functionalists and cognitivists, grammar is something that spontaneously arises from the combined pressure of external stimuli and of internal cognitive and functional pressures. In the most extreme position, emergentism, grammar is considered to be an emergent phenomenon, due to the online interaction of cognitive and processing limitations with the functional principle of efficient communication (MacWhinney 1999).

Theories of SLA face the same problems that animate the FLA debate, such as we have tried to illustrate. But they add to these difficulties with difficulties introduced into the framework by the fact that the learner is already in possession of a well established linguistic system.¹

For what concerns the main theories of SLA here again we shall distinguish between generative theories and cognitive functional theories.

¹When dealing with SLA here we are going to leave out some problems like childhood bilingualism, and the parallel acquisition of two or more systems of language before the critical period. The problem of identifying the end of the critical period itself will not be our goal, since we will not work with children or adolescent learners. Similarly the distinction between spontaneous language acquisition in a situation of linguistic immersion and guided language learning in a non TL speaking environment will be left aside. This is because the majority of the informants of the corpora that shall be used are students residing in Italy for a short period (1-2 years) with some or no experience of learning Italian at home, and who during their stay in Italy benefitted both from linguistic immersion in the Italian speaking community, and also from direct learning through attendance at language courses organized by the University.

Finally, the problem of ultimate attainment is also left out of the discussion (Sorace 2003): not only is our corpus lacking data from longterm resident informants, who may have attained some end state in their process of acquisition, but this kind of data is obviously less interesting from the point of view of lexical categories and their acquisition and use. We will see from the data how much it takes before the categories of IL tend to align to those of TL, the problem being that not all features seem to be as strongly decisive as others.

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The main theories in the generativist framework differ on two points: the accessibility of UG by adult learners and the transferability of parameter-settings from the first language into the second language. One position which has gained more and more influence among generative SLA researchers is the Full Access/Full Transfer Hypothesis (FA/FT) (White 1996); this theory has the advantage of simplicity, since it does not need to imply any sort of “expiry date” for the Language Acquisition Device (which should be otherwise proved) and can try to explain L2 acquisition as the combined effect of Universal Grammar and L1 effects. In fact FT/FA hypothesizes that the initial state of L2 acquisition is the final state of L1 acquisition (Full Transfer) and that failure to assign a representation to input data will force subsequent restructurings, drawing from the options of UG (Full Access) (Schwartz & Sprouse 1996). In other words, the learner of a second language copies his fully fledged and fully parametrized version of the UG, and at first attempts to fill the lexical and functional categories required by the old system with the new material from the TL input.

According to White (2003, 1, 15):

[..] it will be presupposed that the linguistic competence of native speakers of a language can be accounted for in terms of an abstract and unconscious linguistic system, in other words, a grammar, which underlies use of language, including comprehension and production. [...] L2 learners face a task parallel to that of L1 acquirers, namely the need to arrive at a linguistic system which accounts for the L2 input, allowing the learner to understand and speak the second language.

The more input the learner receives, the more he/she will receive evidence of the discrepancies between his/her native system and the target system. More and more parameters will be reset to the new ones, until, ideally, the competence of the L2 speaker may become almost equal to that of an L1 speaker of the target language. This does not mean though, that the performance of the two can be equally native like. Only those aspects that are governed by syntax can be acquired completely. Pragmatic and semantic governed phenomena may require a deeper knowledge of the linguistic environment, and may create more problems for acquisition. All recent waves of research on the phenomena of the syntax/pragmatics interface, such as anaphora

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resolution in subordinate constructions (Sorace & Filiaci 2006), aim at proving that syntax governed regularities are easier to acquire than similar pragmatic rules.

From the point of view of SLA, the position of those who reject any access to UG after the critical period can be assimilated to that of the cognitivists and functionalists, since they too claim that the adult learner has to rely on general cognitive capacities and functional principles to be able to reconstruct and reproduce the TL linguistic system. The learner learns in the first place a series of lexical items with a certain meaning assigned to them. These can be words, or even formulaic expressions, stored as one item. When the learner tries to arrange words in his/her output, not only will the influence of the first language act, but the functional problem of conveying understandable meaning will also have an effect. Hence the necessity of giving the utterance an order that is not yet governed by syntax but by pragmatics. No matter whether the learner has a notion of subject, and no matter whether both NL and TL show, say, an SV order, the problem of not knowing how to mark the subject in the TL may cause the learner to arrange his/her utterance by a completely different, pragmatic principle (like theme first, predicate, reme last). In a fully fledged language, the same pragmatic principles act, but only within the limits of syntax. Here, they are free because the learner is at a pre-syntactic level of language production.

If the FA/FT hypothesis is correct, one must be able to verify several things: in the first place, that all those non parametric features of UG that are common to all human languages can be possessed without need of positive or negative evidence; in the second place, that the language specific features of NL should always be transferred to the TL, until evidence proves them incorrect. This theory's strength and its weakness both lie in its potential falsifiability: whenever a feature is present both in NL and TL, but is not present in IL, this constitutes heavy counter-proof against the FA/FT hypothesis. From the point of view of lexical categories this framework has little to offer: the main division in lexical categories (N, V, A) is considered universal, and therefore not problematic for the learner. The other categories are considered as functional categories, and their acquisition is bound to the acquisition of the corresponding functional projection. Therefore, for instance, it's not important if a language possesses articles: the main problem is whether it possesses the functional projection of definiteness, which can remain unexpressed, but visible from other syntactic clues (for instance, Persian has no articles, but has a functional projection for definiteness, which becomes visible

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when the accusative marking is applied to definite referents only). This framework has produced a series of experimental studies which aim at investigating the differences in competence of a TL between learners whose NL differs in one or more parameters (Robertson 2000, Trenkic 2007, for some examples on the acquisition of articles).

One theory that in our opinion offers a convincing alternative to FA/FT in its attempt to explain the phenomena of second language acquisition is the Learner Variety framework. The hypothesis of learner varieties has been developed as the result of a large, crosslinguistic, longitudinal project on adult SLA (for more information on the project see Klein & Perdue (1992)²). The researchers noted that after some time, all learners investigated developed a relatively stable system to express themselves which (Klein & Perdue 1997, 303):

- seemed to be determined by the interaction of a small number of organizational principles,
- was largely (though not totally) independent of the specific details of source and target language organization,
- was very simple, versatile and highly efficient for most communicative purposes.

According to the authors, the reason for these phenomena can be traced back to four key assumptions (Klein & Perdue 1997, 307-308):

- 1 “During the acquisitional process, the learner passes through a series of learner varieties. Both the internal organization of each variety at a given time as well as the transition from one variety to the next are essentially systematic in nature”.
- 2 “There is a limited set of organizational principles of different kinds which are present in all learner varieties. The actual structure of an utterance on a learner variety is determined by a particular interaction of these principles. The kind of interaction may vary, depending on various factors, such as the learner’s source language. With successive input analysis the interaction changes over time. For example, picking up some components of noun morphology from the input may cause the learner to modify the weight of the other factors in marking argument status.

²This project continues the Lernervarietäten approach of Klein & Dittmar (1979), which was in turn a development of the concept of interlanguage as defined by Selinker (1972)

From this perspective, learning a new feature is not adding a new piece to a puzzle which the learner has to put together. Rather, it entails a sometimes minimal reorganization of the whole variety, where the balance of the various factors successively approaches the balance characteristic of the target language”.

- 3 “Under this perspective, learner varieties are not imperfect imitations of a ‘real language’ - the target language - but systems in their own right, error-free by definition, and characterized by a particular lexical repertoire and by a particular interaction of organizational principles. Fully developed languages, such as English, German, French, are simply borderline cases of learner varieties. They represent a relatively stable state of language acquisition - that state where learners stop learning because there is no difference between their variety and the input - the variety of their social environment”.
- 4 “If all learner varieties, including the final one, are manifestations of the human language capacity, then the study of this capacity should not start with the most complex of these manifestation and go from there to the simpler ones. Rather, it is advisable first to study the various organizational principles of human language and their interplay in relatively simple cases, those where the various form-function relations are more elementary, and more transparent (if seen in their own right, and not as an imperfect imitation of the target)”.

Point (3) is particularly important, in that it shows how IL can be studied using the same tools that are applied to fully developed languages. The analysis carried out by Klein and Perdue concentrates especially on what they call the Basic Variety, which is characterized by lack of inflectional marking and the limited size of the TL lexicon. Given the lack of morphological devices, the main focus of research in the study of the Basic Variety is the utterance organization. How are words combined together, and according to which principles?

From the analysis it emerges that (Klein & Perdue 1997, 313):

1. There are absolute constraints on the form and relative order of constituents:
phrasal constraints.
2. There are constraints which have to do with the case role properties of arguments:
semantic constraints.

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3. There are, finally, constraints which have to do with the organization of information in connected text (introduction and maintenance of reference, topic-focus-structure): *pragmatic constraints*

From the point of view of lexical categories, since we have decided to follow a form-to-function definition, the only possible way of classifying the word in a Basic Variety is the distributional clue (we shall work on the implications of this idea in the next chapter, when trying to cluster together the words in an IL corpus, relying on positional features).

Here we want to draw the attention to the fact that the Learner Variety (LV) approach:

- leads to different conclusions from FA/FT, in that the latter assumes that two early interlanguages should be as different from each other as the respective NL of the learners are from each other and that they should become more and more similar the more they progress towards the TL, whereas LV implies that the Basic Variety, being shaped by the same communicative principles, present a greater number of similarities.
- is not necessarily in contrast to the Generative Framework in a broader sense, in that the Basic Variety can be considered as a case of I-language in the sense of Chomsky (1993) (Klein & Perdue 1997, 337)

3.2 Research Perspectives over the Learner Varieties

As we have seen in the last paragraph, the Learner Varieties hypothesis assumes that, during the course of the acquisition of a second language in everyday communication the learner goes through a series of more or less elaborate repertoires of linguistic devices that allow him or her to express him or herself and to understand others with varying degrees of success when he/she tries to communicate with his/her social environment. It is further assumed that both the internal organization of a learner variety and the transition from one variety to the next are systematic in nature.

In this framework two possible research questions arise: what is “the internal organization of the learner varieties” and what is the “logic of development” from one variety to another.

3.2 Research Perspectives over the Learner Varieties

In Klein & Perdue (1989), the authors try to answer to the question concerning the internal organization of learner varieties, and more particularly the question of how learners arrange words in their utterances. If a learner's repertoire is still very limited and most of the normal syntactic devices of the target language are not yet available to him or herself, what other organizational principles can he or she call on to make themselves understood? (p.292)

In particular the authors' claim that the lack of other syntactic or morphological devices makes the importance of non-syntactic organizational principles such as "information distribution" or "theme-rheme structure" particularly strong in learner varieties.

As a competent communicator, the adult learner will use the limited possibilities he has to maximal effect, and the principles underlying this use will emerge more clearly precisely because the linguistic means they apply to are limited. This, a careful analysis of learner varieties and an exemplification of the general principles that obtain in the organization of adult native language. (Klein & Perdue 1989, p. 296-297)

More specifically Klein & Perdue (1989) analyze the distribution of words in IL by concentrating on three types of constraints:

- Phrasal constraints, which posit the necessity for certain parts of speech to take a specific place in the utterance; of course, lexical categories being the goal of our analysis, the PoS will be tagged according to the external intuition of the researcher, which may be proved to have nothing to do with the real clusters of tokens extracted via positional analysis
- Semantic constraints, such as those which may require a certain position in the utterance of say, human animate NPs; in this case, the device of using a specialized corpus, which allows us to verify the extralinguistic referents of the informants' utterances, is of a very practical utility;
- Pragmatic constraints, concerning in particular the nature of the referent, and the presence of a focus and a topic which can usually heavily influence the order of the utterance even in fully fledged language varieties.

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In the following chapter (4) we shall follow this intuition and investigate the kind of constraint that most influences the distribution of words in an IL sample.

3.3 SLA Corpus analysis

Before proceeding to the investigation of second language acquisition of lexical categories, some methodological premises are necessary. Our intention is to use SLA corpora for the quantitative analysis of our topic and therefore the learner corpora and the methodology of their investigation must be presented.

Linguistic corpora are collections of linguistic data, either of written text or transcriptions of recorded speech, which are designed to be a balanced collection of data that accurately represents some aspect of a language. These collections of data are useful not only to linguists, who use them to formally test hypotheses they may have about a given language, but also for language modelling.

Corpora are one of the instruments used in SLA research, together with data derived from experimental evidence (White 2003, for some experimental studies in the generativist framework) and even reliability judgements (Sorace 1996, Mandell 1999, for an introduction on the subject).

More specifically “a learner corpus is a computerized textual database of the language produced by foreign language learners [...] The main purpose in compiling a learner corpus is to gather objective data that can aid in describing learner language” (Pravec 2002).

The problems and advantages arising from the use of corpora in general apply, as is obvious, to learner corpora as well:

- from the functional and cognitive point of view, they offer a powerful tool to investigate language competence as well, since “there is a widespread recognition that absolute frequencies (i.e. percentages), conditional probabilities, relative frequencies etc. are represented in the linguistic systems of the speakers and, thus, play a primary role on all levels of linguistic analysis” (Gries 2008).
- from the generative point of view they are instead a good way to investigate performance, but not language competence; the variability represented in large corpora does not imply a probabilistic nature to grammar, but rather the presence

of different grammars among the informants. Given the categorial nature of the principles of grammar, and their universal foundation, it seems more reasonable to investigate the competence of a few speakers via experiments or grammaticality judgements, rather than to search for universals in a large collection of data. Still, even in the generative framework, corpus analysis may be seen as a preliminary investigation that may help to formulate hypotheses that can be subsequently tested in a more controlled setting. In this sense, corpus analysis may be compared to the “observation” that leads to hypothesis and experiment in the scientific method.

What makes learner corpora so important?

In Myles (2005), an introduction to learner corpora,³ we read:

SLA research crucially depends on good datasets to work from. Researchers aim to build models of the underlying mental representations and developmental processes which shape and constrain second language (L2) productions. The language produced by learners, whether spontaneously or through various elicitation procedures, remains a central source of evidence for these mental processes, and the success of SLA research therefore relies on having access to good quality data. If we are to make generalizations about learner development, we need to be able to capture the various stages that learners go through. For this we either need longitudinal data of a number of learners over a lengthy period of time (as the acquisition of a L2 requires a considerable amount of time), or we need very large cross-sectional datasets, so that the number of learners in each well-defined stage is big enough for us to be confident that the results of the analysis are generalizable (or to capture what is variable in language development across learners for that matter). (pp. 374-375)

More specifically, corpora can be useful in various ways. Granger, Kraif, Ponton, Antoniadis & Zampa (2007, p. 255-256) distinguish between two different methods in corpus studies:

³for a survey of the principal learner corpora see Pravec (2002)

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- a *corpus-based method*, involving looking for words, phrases or structures that the researcher knows or suspects to be interesting. In this case, the corpus is used to verify intuitions and to acquire a more accurate understanding of the IL specific structures using concordancing techniques which highlight the specific patterns of misuse.
- a *corpus-driven method*, which consists in carrying out automatic comparisons of learner and native corpora to identify learner-specific features. In this case, the researcher has no *a priori* idea of which IL-specific structures can be found; corpus comparison is used as a heuristic to uncover them. Granger and Rayson's (1998) automatic profiling of learner texts uncovers many instances of significant over- or underuse, many of which turn out to be due to erroneous or stylistically inappropriate use.

While keeping in mind that both methods are useful but have severe limitations - the first because intuition only gives access to the errors that are most salient in teachers' minds and the second because misuse does not always result in over- or underuse (Granger et al. 2007, p. 252) - in this work we are going to carry out mostly corpus-driven analyses with a particular reference to those analyses that can be carried on using quantitative algorithms that can be implemented in a computer program.

It is well known that a good corpus must be ample enough and as well balanced as possible. Most NL corpora nowadays are as big as 100 million words, and are constructed so as to represent the diastatic, diamesic and diatopic variety of the language in question (they contain spoken as well as written language, languages for specific purposes, and languages of the media, and gather data from different regional varieties).

Although it is mainly true that "more data is better data", it is not too unfrequent that some investigations are conducted on smaller corpora. This is particularly true for learner corpora since the variation in interlanguage spans over many more dimensions (TL, NL, level of proficiency, individual variables such as age, level of instruction, context of acquisition, motivation, etc.): hence the necessity of limiting the variables by creating specialized small learner corpora of around 50,000 words in size (De Beaugrande 2001).

Usually, as stated by Tono (2003), the criteria for selecting a specialized learner corpus (of English, in this case) can be divided into “three major categories: (a) language-related criteria (e.g. mode, medium, genre, topic), (b) task-related criteria (e.g. longitudinal vs. cross-sectional; spontaneous vs. prepared), and (c) learner-related criteria (e.g. ESL or EFL⁴, age, sex, mother tongue, overseas experience)”. In our case, the specialization of the corpora will be based on the selection of informants of specific L1s, who learn Italian both in classroom and from contact with native speakers (as is mostly true for exchange students) and is limited to a collection of spoken data derived from the elicitation of semi-guided tasks.

Corpora are usually characterized by being provided with different levels of annotation (Tono 2003):

Table 3.1: Levels of annotation in SLA corpora

Extra-textual information	Header information (learner/ language/ task variables)
Level of transcription	Orthographic (+ phonemic/ phonetic for spoken corpora)
Level of annotation	Sentence-boundary disambiguation
	Tokenisation
	PoS tagging
	Lemmatisation
	Parsing (Treebanking)
	Semantic tagging (word senses/ semantic relationships and categories)
	Discourse tagging (apologies/greetings/politeness/moves/acts/etc.)
	Error tagging
	Prosody annotation
	Anaphoric annotation

As for the level of PoS annotation and lemmatization, we shall deal with the issues

⁴ESL stands for English as a second language, i.e. spontaneously learned in an English-speaking context, as opposed to EFL, English as a foreign language, learned in classroom in a guided context

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connected to SLA PoS tagging in chapter 5 of this work. Parsing and discourse tagging shall not be the object of our research, nor will prosody or anaphora annotation. As for the orthographic level of annotation, the corpora we have adopted, which shall be described in more detail when the corresponding experiments are introduced, have all been annotated using some version of the CHAT standard, created for the CHILDES corpus (MacWhinney 2000).

Considering that the subject of study does not require a strong annotation at the phonological level, some normalization has been necessary, to get rid of the chat annotation, including repetitions and some level of ambiguity in the spoken corpora under examination. This has certainly caused a non trivial amount of information loss, but has been rewarded by the higher level of automatization and operability of the data so obtained. For a more detailed description of the preliminary corpus cleaning operation we refer to Appendix A of this work.

As for error tagging, it has been widely practiced in learner corpora, but is also subject to many criticisms (Tono 2003):

It is of course useful to adopt generic annotation schemes such as above for learner data in general, but there is one area in which learner corpus researchers have yet to agree on a general scheme: “error annotation”. As shown in the history of error analysis, categorizing learner errors is a laborious and oftentimes fruitless job, for there are various ways of classifying errors, depending on research interest and theories involved and it is often the case that the classification is only as valid as the theory it is based on.

For a more radical critique of error tagging we refer to Rastelli (2007). It will be sufficient to say here that error tagging does not seem to be very useful to the study of problems of categorization since these problems, as we have seen, may be identified at many different levels (positional, lexical, morphological, semantic, pragmatic). In Chapter 5 of this work a proposal shall be presented that seeks to avoid the necessity of error tagging by using the concept of confidence of categorization.

The selection of the annotation and retrieval devices is very important. In our case, where PoS and lemma annotation is added, the XML standard of tagging is chosen, and information will be retrieved by using XQUERY directly or via the Xaira

tool (Burnard 2004), a freely available general purpose XML search engine, which can operate on any corpus of well-formed XML documents.

3.4 Quadripartite schema of analysis

The purpose of this research is both theoretical and methodological. From the theoretical point of view we seek to investigate the nature of category acquisition and use by L2 adult learners, and to analyze the results with reference to the more general findings of the commonly accepted theories of acquisition.

From the methodological point of view, our purpose is to show how it is possible to quickly preprocess, tag, analyze and query a collection of IL texts, without any need for a great investment of time and resources, while at the same time being able to draw some nontrivial results.

More specifically, the possible methodologies in the analysis of corpora can be classified by using two sets of oppositions:

- qualitative vs quantitative, according to whether we want extract specific patterns from the corpus, or we want an algorithm to show us which regularities are extractable from the corpus
- target vs source, according to whether we want to concentrate on how much learners' words align with the categories of the target language, or we want to analyze inherent categories (if they exist) of a specific Learner Variety.

By combining these two oppositions a quadripartite schema (See Table 3.1) is derivable:

In the following chapters we shall proceed to a corpus driven analysis of the source categories, so defined because they don't bear any reference to those of the target language, via an algorithm of category induction. Subsequently a method for target category tagging will be described and applied, and finally target categories distribution will be analyzed in IL and NL texts.

Figure 3.1: Quadripartite Schema of the work - This figure illustrates the possible types of analysis that can be used to investigate lexical categories in IL.

4

Quantitative analysis - Source categories

4.1 Outline

In Chapter 2 and 3 we argued that distributional information is one of the most significant features in a formal definition of lexical categories. So far, the problem has been dealt with from the point of view of language theory. What about language use?

Even though the typological universality of the noun/verb distinction is still argued upon, several experiments in the last few years seem to point at a clear distinction between the lexical organization of the two main classes in the brain (Caramazza & Hillis 1991, Koenig & Lehmann 1996, Tranel, Martin, Damasio, Grabowski & Hichwa 2005, Shapiro, Moo & Caramazza 2006, among others). This distinction arises very early in language development. As a matter of fact, children at the age of 4, 5 seem to be sensitive to categorial distinctions and capable of assigning categories to pseudo words ¹.

This led researchers to investigate the possible ways in which this ability of categorial distinction may be developed by children.

Parallel work in computational linguistics on unsupervised part of speech tagging has provided a powerful tool for simulating category acquisition. The seminal work of Finch & Chater (1991) and Schütze (1995) has proved that, given a large amount of

¹Cassidy & Kelly (1991) found that English verbs contain fewer syllables than English nouns, a difference that appears strongly in both adult-adult language and parental speech to children. Adults and children appear to be sensitive to this difference. Adults use pseudo-words more often in sentences as verbs if their syllable number is small, whereas they use pseudo-words as nouns more often if their syllable number is large. Four-year-old children associate pseudo-words with actions (the prototypical verb meaning) more often than objects (the prototypical noun meaning) if the pseudo-words contain 1 rather than 3 syllables.

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data in a given language, a context similarity algorithm can be created that is capable of inducing a set of categories that are not too dissimilar from the ones traditionally accepted for the language.

The implications of these results for First Language Acquisition were soon investigated (Redington, Chater & Finch 1993, Redington & Chater 1997). Category induction on child directed speech corpora supports the hypothesis that the distinction between the main lexical categories can be induced by the child on the basis of mere positional clues, **without** assuming any innate set of categories².

What about Second Language Acquisition? Adult learners are obviously in a different position in respect to children. They are speakers of a fully fledged language who have to acquire a different system. In the worst case, the new system has a different set of categories; but even in the case of a similar set the learner has to acquire the distinctive features for each category in the new language. In other words, the learner may well have an idea that nouns and adjectives are distinct classes in Italian, but until it appears in his or her language production this is not enough for us to say that he or she has acquired this distinction.

The idea is to use a category induction algorithm to check the behavior of word tokens in an IL Italian corpus. By grouping together words with similar distributions in the corpus, the level of specialization of each word can be tested and compared to that of the TL.

In this chapter, after an introduction to the theoretical framework of category acquisition that we intend to verify, two algorithms for category induction shall be presented and applied to a small corpus of L1 Chinese learners of Italian, and to a comparable control corpus of native Italian speakers. The resulting clusters of words shall be compared and analyzed against the theoretical hypothesis of category acquisition.

4.2 Acquisition of categories in L2 Italian

Before going into the analysis of the experimental setting, we shall outline a brief review of the existing literature on the subject of acquisition of lexical categories in L2 Italian. Some qualitative studies shall be presented which introduce the problem of Basic Variety and category acquisition in Italian from a more theoretical and general

²Note that in real life children can combine positional with phonological and prosodic information.

point of view, which a quantitative analysis, such as ours may run the risk of missing out.³

In the first place, the work of Bernini shall be introduced. Bernini has dedicated several works to the category acquisition, using and applying the generalizations proposed by Klein and Perdue to the acquisition of Italian as a L2. In particular, the attention has been focused on the emergence of the category of verbs, which is considered to be the first one to appear. This idea parallels Hengeveld hierarchy of lexical categories (chapter 2) and is consistent with a functional-typological approach to language acquisition (Giacalone Ramat 2003*a*), where typological hierarchies are considered to have both a synchronic and a diachronic validity, and are expected to be confirmed in Learner Varieties.

According to Bernini (1995) the characteristics of the Basic Variety can be recognized in the absence of morphology and of consistent marking of finiteness; verbs usually display just one invariant form, and the difference between past and present tense is only derivable from the context.

This idea is developed in Bernini (2003*a*) where a complete acquisitional sequence is proposed; in the pre-basic level words can be categorized according to their semantic and phonetic features alone; in the basic level some homogeneous distributional features emerge, and it is only in the post basic level that the morphology becomes distinctive, with a consistent use of the finite morphemes to mark verbal predication.

1. **pre-basic level:** semantics + phonetics;
2. **basic level:** semantics + phonetics + distributional;
3. **post-basic level:** semantics + phonetics + distributional + morphology;

From Bernini (2003*a*) it is clear that the acquisition of the TL lexicon does not end with the acquisition of the phonological form and the meaning, but is a long process, that terminates only when the morphological and the syntactic possibilities of the same word are acquired and mastered. We can infer from this that the acquisition of a word does not imply the acquisition of the lexical category to which it belongs. Rather

³All the works that are here presented are based on the analysis of some excerpts of the Pavia Corpus, a longitudinal corpus, gathered in the framework of the Pavia Project, coordinated by Prof. Anna Giacalone Ramat starting from 1986.

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the reverse: the acquisition (mastery) of the TL lexical category is the end of a long process, that passes through the acquisition of all the morpho-syntactic features whose use defines the category of a word.

According to this path, the acquisition of a full distinction between noun and verb is fully operative only at the Post-Basic level, whereas the distinction between verbs and nouns at the basic level is still rather of a syntactic/semantic kind (predicates vs arguments) (Bernini 2005, p. 125).

At the same time, if it's true that only in Post-Basic Varieties do all the formal traits converge with each other and with the functional-semantic ones, this result is not achieved at once, and the decision of where to put a boundary for the beginning of word categorization is highly influenced by the definition of lexical category that is adopted. As hypothesized in Chapter 2, distributional clues seems to have a sort of primacy among other formal clues, and may therefore align sooner with the specific functions of TL categories. This may work as a reinforcement for the acquisition of other features, like inflectional morphology, that are attracted in the same direction.

This kind of analysis is applied in the work of Valentini (2008), who also starts from a definition of lexical categories as a bundle of functional and structural categories; deriving from this that the acquisition of lexical categories must comprise different levels of analysis. The starting point of the work is the transition from Pre-Basic to Basic Variety. The Pre-Basic Variety is characterized by the absence of any categorial distinction, which appears to be stabilized only in the Post-Basic Variety.

What happens in the transition phase of the Basic Variety? How do lexical categories emerge, and which are the features that are most distinguishing in this phase? Valentini seems to acknowledge that giving the morphological features a too heavy weight can lead one to miss the beginning phases of the categorization of words in the Basic Variety. Valentini's analysis focuses on the categorization of verbs: the presence of a predicate is one of the distinguishing traits that mark the evolution to the Basic Variety. But what makes a predicate a verb? The key point of her argument is that the presence of the copula is a mark of formal "verbality", in the sense that a formally verbal element must be present when the lexical predicate cannot bear the form of a grammatical verb. In this sense, Valentini's argument is a distributional one, in the sense that there is a position proper to the grammatical verb that can be taken either

by the lexical verb or by the copula, but not by the non verbal predicates, as is usual in the Pre-Basic Variety.

A similar argument can be used to claim a precocious categorization of the noun category. The distributional mark of nominality is given, according to Valentini, by the regular marking of the left border of a SN by a series of determiners of various kinds, mostly (indefinite) articles, possessives, or numerals.

Following Valentini, our claim is that if we consider the distributional features alone of tokens in IL utterances, it is possible to see the beginning of clustering of categories in the IL that is partly still due to pragmatic, “pre-basic” motivations, but starts also to take the configuration of TL categories.

The idea behind the following experiments is to try and formalize the hypothesis by giving an operational definition of distribution and context, and by using algorithms that can group words by similarity of distribution. Due to the limited size of the corpus, the categories obtained will not be compared to the TL categories directly, but to the categories extracted with the same procedure from a comparable native corpus.

In the following paragraphs the corpus, the algorithms and the results will be analyzed in the light of our hypothesis.

4.3 The corpus

For the experiment the transcription of the new Marco Polo spoken corpus has been used. The informants are native speakers of Mandarin Chinese (but a control corpus with Italian native speakers is also included), who had resided in Pavia for 6 months in order to participate in an intensive Italian language course. In the sample the informants are first presented with a video - “Finite Story” for both groups (Dimroth 2006)) - which they are then asked to retell to the interviewer (see table C.1).

Being a spoken corpus the recorded interviews have been transcribed using an adaptation of the CHAT standard, created for the CHILDES corpus (MacWhinney 2000)⁴. The annotation of the corpus includes special marking for repetitions, false starts, self repairs and other types of speech disfluencies. This kind of annotation is very useful, since speech disfluencies, in particular one token repetitions (like the repetition of the

⁴The specifications for the corpus have not been published, and the use of the corpus itself was made possible by kind permission of Prof. Cecilia Andorno, University of Pavia. For an introduction to the annotation system we can refer to the Pavia Corpus, see Andorno & Bernini (2003).

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articles) can create large problems to any automatic system of natural language processing and have to be stripped away, together with the other CHAT symbols. The details of the algorithm that has been used to clean the corpus texts can be found in Appendix A ⁵.

Table 4.1: default

Name	Marco Polo
Informants	28 Chinese exchange students
Control groups	19 Italian Native speakers
Elicitation	Retelling of “Finite Story”
Supervision	Cecilia Andorno, University of Pavia
Period	2007-2008
Size of IL group	9014 tokens after cleaning
Size of NL group	9903 tokens after cleaning

Some preliminary considerations regarding the two samples are necessary. Although the dimensions are comparable, the Native group contains less speakers, meaning that overall they produce longer texts. The main reason is that they speak in a more fluent way, requiring less intervention by the interviewer, and therefore less preliminary cleaning, since the interviewer’s lines are expunged.

This said, if we consider the two Zipf’s curves (see plots 4.1 4.2 here and data in Appendix B.1), we can see that the vocabulary of the 2 samples is fairly comparable, with some more richness from the part of the Native sample, but with a similar (0.1) type/token ratio.

The idea is not to compare the two samples, which are obviously very different, for what concerns fluency, grammaticality and informativeness of the content, but to use the Native sample as a reference point in order to know how much clustering we may expect, due to the sparseness of the samples. We know in fact that with a big enough sample (millions of words) it is possible to reconstruct the categories of a language with a striking precision. But we shall see that even with a sample as small as less

⁵It is very important to underline that the annotation of the corpus is very consistent this allows a completely automatic cleaning of the corpus, and no direct intervention on the external annotator’s work.

than 10,000 words, the Italian text shows encouraging results that may help guide us to judge the clusters that emerge in the other group.

Interlanguage Data

Figure 4.1: Zipf's curve for the interlanguage sample - Words in the text are ordered from the most frequent to the least frequent (i.e. by descending rank), and plotted against their frequency. As predicted by Zipf's law the distribution is logarithmic, with a small number of very frequent tokens and a long tail of infrequent ones.

Native Speakers

Figure 4.2: Zipf's curve for the Native sample - Words in the text are ordered from the most frequent to the least frequent (i.e. by descending rank), and plotted against their frequency. As predicted by Zipf's law the distribution is logarithmic, with a small number of very frequent tokens and a long tail of infrequent ones.

4.4 Lexical categories in Chinese

Before we start to illustrate the experiments in detail, it is appropriate to say something about lexical categories in the informant's native language since this is a crucial point in the discussion. It is indeed a very different matter to ask ourselves the question whether Chinese learners approach the acquisition of Italian with very a different system of categories, or with no system of categories at all. If the second is true this may have a very strong impact on our conclusions. We shall follow the argument of Packard (2000) that such a strong claim cannot be held.

The concept of lexical categories has syntactic, semantic as well as morphological aspects Ježek (2005). As we have seen, the lexical category is a property of the word token, since the context is the final clue toward deciding whether a token belongs to a certain class. Still, in languages like Italian, with a very strong morphology, the range of possible choices is predetermined by the morphemes that are attached to the stem, and whose functional meaning prevents the use of some forms in some contexts. Most of the practical applications that deal with PoS tagging are built using this intuition: for each token, a morphological analyzer reduces the range of possible classes to which it may belong, and subsequently a statistical algorithm assigns the token to the most probable class given the context. The reverse is also true: if the morphological form determines the context in which a word can occur, then also the context determines the morphological form of a word.

What happens in languages with a poor morphology, like Mandarin Chinese? Could it be that, if a language has no morphology it also has no lexical categories? Lexical categories are considered a property of words, and indeed Chinese could be seen as a language lacking words and only based on lexical morphemes.

Packard (2000, p.11-12) objects to this by distinguishing between the morphological word as the proper output of word-formation rules in the language and the syntactic word as an independent occupant of a syntactic form class slot. This distinction parallels the one between types and tokens, and is derived from the fact that the formal features defining categories are of a morphological⁶ and a syntactic nature. Morpho-

⁶Among the morphological features the distinction between lexical morphemes, derivational morphemes and inflectional morphemes mirrors the distinction between roots, lemmas and word types strictu sensu

logical words, or types, have one or more potential lexical categories; but only syntactic words, or tokens, really instantiate just one category.

(Packard 2000, p.11-12)

Defining a syntactic word presumes that we can identify basic form class categories, and then use native speaker judgements to determine what entities are able to minimally occupy the category slots within utterances. This notion of syntactic word, as we shall see, will be one we crucially rely on in our description of Chinese words.

In the sense that some entities cannot occur in certain position, we can say that Chinese does have a system of lexical categories. More specifically, in Hengeveld's (Hengeveld 1992, 70-71) definition, it is considered to be a rigid language, with two clear open classes: nouns and verbs, a small closed class of adjectives and no adverbs.

4.5 The first experiment

4.5.1 Biemann's algorithm

There are a number of approaches to derive lexical categories (Finch & Chater 1991, Schütze 1995, Biemann 2006, among others). They rely on the distributional hypothesis: words of similar parts of speech tend to occur in the same syntactic contexts. Operationally the context is usually a list of the most frequent words. The words used to describe syntactic contexts will be called 'feature words' in the remainder. 'Target words', as opposed to this, are the words that are to be grouped into syntactic clusters.

Following Biemann (2006), the general methodology for inducing word class information can be outlined as follows:

1. Collect global context vectors for target words by counting how often feature words appear in neighbouring positions.
2. Apply a clustering algorithm based on the similarity of these vectors to each other to obtain word classes.

Throughout, feature words are the 150-250 words with the highest frequency. Contexts are the feature words appearing in the immediate neighbourhood of a word. The word's global context is the sum of all its contexts. For clustering, a similarity measure

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has to be defined and a clustering algorithm has to be chosen. Finch & Chater (1991) use the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient and a hierarchical clustering, Schütze (1995) uses the cosine between vector angles and Buckshot clustering.

The main difference is in the measurement of the distances between the vector representations using a graph based representation, and a graph-clustering algorithm called Chinese Whispers. For a complete description of the algorithm we refer to Biemann (2006): for our purposes it will suffice to say that the algorithm is capable, given a large enough untagged corpus, to reconstruct a fairly reliable tagset for any given language. Being an unparametrised method, the number of end categories is not defined by the user, but by the program itself.

In practice, Biemann's solution is a complex algorithm in two parts, of which, due to the smallness of our corpus, only the first is useful to us, the partitioning one, used to cluster high and medium frequency words. Part one:

1. Determine 200 feature and 10,000 target words from frequency counts.
2. Construct graph from context statistics
3. Apply Chinese Whispers on graph.
4. Add the feature words not present in the partitioning as one-member clusters.

In a big corpus the algorithm proceeds with the second part, using the clusters obtained in partitioning 1 to cluster lower frequency words. But both our corpora are of a size slightly less than 10,000 words. ⁷

4.5.2 Results and analysis

We have given both the clean Native corpus and the IL corpus as single files (thus merging together the single informants).

⁷As to the number of feature words, the use of a reduced set, in proportion to the much smaller corpus has proved to be ineffective, outputting much less homogeneous categories for both samples. The same happened when the number of feature words was extended to cover the entire vocabulary; in this case too much contextual information probably introduces too much noise, thus reducing the weight of the more typical contexts. This can probably be explained as a zipfian effect: the most frequent 200 words of any corpus are probably a quite homogeneous set - together constituting the ideal context for clustering - no matter what the dimension of the corpus is.

The full results obtained can be seen in Appendix B.2. Note that the small size of the corpora prevents the algorithm from merging many small categories into bigger ones. This is not a problem, since the goal of our analysis is to see what kind of principles emerge from the clustering output. Also, not all words can be clustered together; 408 items over a vocabulary of 982 types for the NL group and 387 items over a vocabulary of 909 types for the IL group.

Considering that the algorithm clusters words that occupy the same position in the sentence, what we want to look at is whether the clusters reflect more grammatical or pragmatic, functional principles. In this case we shall concentrate on two points: the distinction between nouns and verbs, and the distinction between finite and non finite verbs.

It is here taken for granted that, since lexical category is a property of a token (a word used in a specific context), and not of a type, the clustered words will be checked against their context of use when disambiguation is needed. When two possible interpretations are present, both are taken into account.

There is a comparable number of classes in both samples (92 vs 101). On the whole the classes of the Native sample seem to be more homogeneous when the formal, target-like criteria are considered (morphology and root especially): 69 classes over 101 are homogeneous (i.e., contain over 75% elements that belong to the same target category), while only 49 over 92 are homogeneous in the interlanguage sample. (The difference between the two groups is significant; the two-tailed P value equals 0.0387)

Since it is expected that problems in the acquisition of morphology may cause infinitive, past participial and gerunds to function as main verbs in IL, merging the two verb classes (finite and non finite verbs) may be advisable; still some difference remains: 62/92 for the IL group, and 76/101 but it's not statistically significant.

This suggests that the classes of the IL sample seem less homogeneous when the formal criterion is adopted. But when the function is taken into account, the apparent inhomogeneities tend to find an explanation. This becomes more clear when some heterogeneous categories are closely analyzed and the reason for some odd clusterings is reconstructed.

4.5.2.1 Category 2

Category 2 contains mainly nouns, with 3 exceptions: *telefonale*, *plendele*, *qua*.

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- (4.1) *quando il vigile è uscita il bagno il telefonale*
when the policeman is gone:SG-F the toilet the telephone:Verb-Inf
è finito
is finished
'when the policeman exited the bathroom the telephone call was finished'

As we can see from this example the apparently heterogeneous element, the infinite verb, occupies a post-determiner position (or at least it follows a token that, in the TL, has the function of determiner). From the functional point of view this word can be considered to have a referential use in the context.

- (4.2) *poi il vigile del fuoco il prendele l acqua sul fuoco*
then the officier of the fire the take:INF the water on the fire
'then the firefighter throws water on the fire'

In this case the verb occupies the post determiner position. Although it clearly has a predicative function, it is formally constructed as if it was used referentially.

- (4.3) *qua non c'è qualcuno*
here not there is anyone
'here there isn't anyone'

The sentence initial and preverbal position of the item *qua* has the function of *setting* in a presentative sentence; this use is compatible with the TL, but in this case the algorithm has not enough data to cluster these adverbs separately from nouns which frequently occupy this slot.

Just as the apparently heterogeneous elements can be explained by closer analysis, so can the apparently homogeneous element of the category bring up some surprises. Just as *telefonale* has a referential value in some of its instances, *telefono* can have a predicative one.

While the majority of instances behave referentially as in:

- (4.4) *lui prende il telefono e comincia a chiamale*
he takes the telephone and starts to call
'he takes the telephone and starts to call'

some instances appear in a complex predicate, which is compatible with a verb + noun cluster, as in :

- (4.5) *sì lui spesso fa le telefonate con vigili*
 yes he often(?) makes telephone with firefighters
 ‘He repeatedly calls the fire brigade’

other instances are clearly predicative:

- (4.6) *lui telefona con vigili*
 he telephone with firefighters
 ‘He phones the firefighters’

- (4.7) *la signora blu telefona*
 the lady blue telephone
 ‘Mrs Blue telephones’

In the last three cases there is homophony with the first person singular of the indicative present of the verb *telefonare*. It is therefore impossible to decide whether there is overextension of the verb form. From the point of view of the learners, this would imply the presence of two distinct but homophone forms, which the algorithm cannot distinguish.

4.5.2.2 Category 6

Category 6 mainly contains connectors and adverbs like *ma anche quando infine finalmente intanto invece*; exceptions are *servare aiutata fortuna sbagliato vudimo*

- (4.8) *loro vogliono salvare il signor blu*
 they want:PRS-3PL save the mr blue
 ‘They want to save Mr Blue’

This is a target like construction; the infinitive construction with a second verb following the first is not recognized by the algorithm in the small sample. The second verb occupies the same position as a connector introducing a second sentence. The same happens in the following example:

- (4.9) *le polizie sono aiutata il signore verde*
 the police are helped:PTCP-PST-SG-F the mr green
 ‘The police helped Mr Blue’

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More interesting is the following construction: *fortuna*, though a noun, is part of an adverbial construction and is rightly classified as such:

- (4.10) *per fortuna il signore blu ha sentito la accidente*
for fortune the mr blue has heard the:SG-F accident
'Luckily Mr Blue became aware of the accident'

The same can be said of past participial *sbagliato*, which works like an adverb ('male', that is 'wrong').

- (4.11) *no ho fatto sbagliato*
no have:PRS-1SG made mistaken:PTCP-PST-SG-M
'no, i've made a mistake'

On a deeper level even the verb *vedimo* has an adverb like function, like Italian 'ecco', French 'voilà' (lit. 'see there'):

- (4.12) *il signor rosso vedimo il signore rosso uscita e*
the mr red see:1PL the mr red exit:PTCP-PST-SG-F and
da la finestra
from the window
'Mr Red, we see that Mr Red has come out of the window/Here is Mr Red coming out of the window'

4.5.2.3 Category 12

Category 12 mainly contains finite verbs like *passa spegne apri dispiace fossi scavo*

Among the exceptions we have non target *bussare* and target-like *facendo* which are both predicative heads.

- (4.13) *bussare la porta di il signore verde*
knok:INF the door of the mr red
'They knock at Mr Red's door'

and target like

- (4.14) *una tattera sta facendo la cacca*
a ? is making the poo
'A ? is making poo'

4.5.2.4 Category 16, 34, 39, 40

The items of these classes are all elements that can occur immediately after the copula ('è') and are therefore mainly predicative elements.

Non target like elements are present:

- (4.15) *quando loro dormiano il fuoco è incominciare*
 then they sleep the fire is start:INF
 'While they were sleeping the fire started'

- (4.16) *rossi è dorm-imento*
 rossi is sleep-DERIVATIONAL(V>N)
 'Red is asleep'

In this case the post-verbal element seems to be a deverbal noun with basis 'sleep'. Still it's clear that this element has a predicative function, meaning 'asleep'.

- (4.17) *l' uomo blu è pausa e poi bata la polta di l' uomo*
 the man blue is fear and then beat the door of the man
rossa
 red
 'Mr Blue is afraid and then knocks at the door of Mr Red'

Almost all occurrences of **pausa** (= 'paura', 'fear') are (non TL.like) post copula predicative elements.

This position can be of course be occupied also by adverbs, like:

- (4.18) *il signora blu è molte molto bluto*
 the:SG-M Mrs Blue is very:PL-F very:SG-M ugly:SG-M
 'Mrs Blue is very very ugly'

Other examples are existential⁸:

- (4.19) *c' è un popoli ha chiuso il luce*
 there is a preson(?):PL-M has closed the:SG-M light
 'there is someone(?) who has switched off the light'

⁸There is ample evidence (Bernini 2003b) that, in the pre-basic and basic varieties of Italian, the predicate *c'è* is interpreted by the learners as an unanalyzed form, instead of an instance of locative clitic *ci* + 3rd person singular of the verb *essere*; one could therefore object that a correct tokenization should count it as one element instead of two. Following Spreafico (2003, 100-101) we have chosen to maintain the same tokenization for IL the TL, in order to allow for a better comparability.

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(4.20) *non c' è telefonare squillare*
not there is telephone:INF ring:INF
'There's not a telephone ringing'

(4.21) *anche il signore rosso c è un stupore sulla sua faccia*
also the mr red there is a stupor on the his face
'Mr Red, too; there's astonishment on his face'

4.5.2.5 Category 18

Category 18 is a very heterogeneous category containing elements that are followed by an NP.

Here are three examples of setting elements:

(4.22) *adesso il verde si sveglia*
now the green REFL awakens
'Now the red one awakens'

(4.23) *spegnere il fuoco è spegneto*
extinguish:INF the fire is extinguished
'Extinguish, the fire has been extinguished'

(4.24) *fuoco la signora blu vedere il fuoco*
fire the mrs blue see:INF the fire
'fire, Mrs Blue sees fire'

Other items are not sentence initial, and more clearly predicative:

(4.25) *la casa loro aprire il fuoco*
the house them open fire
'In their house a fire breaks out'

(4.26) *no signor blu ha telefonato i viligi fuoco per difensare*
no mr blue has telephoned the officers of fire for
il fuoco
defend:INF the fire
'no, Mr Blue has phoned the firefighters to extinguish the fire'

4.6 The second experiment

4.6.1 The algorithm - Clark's Context Distribution Clustering

In order to compare the results from Biemann's algorithm with a slightly different method, we shall use Clark (2000); this article proposes an algorithm that, while still based on a positional intuition of category, formalizes the definition of context by using a probabilistic method.

Whereas earlier methods all share the same basic intuition, i.e. that similar words occur in similar contexts, I formalise this in a slightly different way: each word defines a probability distribution over all contexts, namely the probability of the context given the word. If the context is restricted to the word on either side, I can define the context distribution to be a distribution over all ordered pairs of words: the word before and the word after. The context distribution of a word can be estimated from the observed contexts in a corpus. We can then measure the similarity of words by the similarity of their context distributions, using the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence as a distance function.

This algorithm gives good results on the 12 million words of the British National Corpus, when compared to the CLAWS-4 tag set (Leech, Garside & Bryant 1994).

Apart from the methodology of context similarity, the other main difference with Biemann is in the clustering algorithm which is parametric: the number of classes must be defined by the user.

4.6.2 Results

We have run the algorithm on the same NL and IL samples as in the previous experiment. But in this case the number of categories had to be supplied: the purpose of the present study is not to compare the algorithms but the output of each for the IL vs the NL sample. So we chose to use a much smaller parameter size, of 8 classes, the last of which contains the residual, unclusterable elements whose number in this case is higher, due to the smaller number of classes. The clustered items, divided into the remaining 7 classes, are 174 over a vocabulary of 982 types for the NL group and 141 over a vocabulary of 909 types for the IL group.

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Here, too, we consider the distinction between the two main classes of noun and verb, both in a formal and functional sense. The Native samples seem to be fairly homogeneous, even if the bigger categories allow for less specificity. In 4.2 we can see a fairly clear distinction between nominal clusters and verbal clusters with the small exception in the bigger class 2, a verbal class with two nouns. Other classes tend to be less homogeneous; adverbs particularly tend to mix with function words, whereas prepositions and articles (and their combination) tend to cluster very homogeneously with each other, just as they do with Biemann’s algorithm. Another similarity is the clear emergence of a class of proper names, which, in the “Finite Story”, coincide with names of color.

Table 4.2: Analysis of clusters in NL (Clark’s algorithm)

Output		Analysis	Verbs	Nouns
types	cl	PoS		
30	1	function words	7	0
54	2	verbs	41	2
22	3	nouns	0	17
20	4	function words	6	1
13	5	prep/det	0	0
4	6	proper names	0	0
31	7	prep/det	8	0
174				

The IL sample (4.3) is obviously less homogeneous; five classes show no overlapping of formally noun-like and verb-like items. Class 2 is clearly verbal, and class 3 is clearly nominal. Just as in the Native sample, prepositions and determiners cluster clearly together, while classes 1 and 5 show overlap of verb-like and noun-like elements. Class 5, in particular is the most heterogeneous, presenting mostly functions words, adverbs and adjectives, but also five verbs and three nouns.

Once again, we are going to look at the formally non-matching elements to see whether the behavior of the positional clusters can be functionally motivated.

Table 4.3: Analysis of clusters in L2 (Clark’s algorithm)

Output		Analysis	Verbs	Nouns
Types	cl	PoS		
36	1	nouns	8	18
22	2	finite verbs	11	0
9	3	nouns	0	8
23	4	prep/det	6	0
31	5	function words	5	3
12	6	proper names	2	0
8	7	prep+det	0	0
141				

4.6.2.1 Category 1

This category contains formally heterogeneous elements, possessive adjectives (which, when not fronted with an article, can be considered a determiner, like in English), past participles, and nouns-like elements (like *rumore*, *camera*, *finestra*), some of which may present some ambiguity like *telefonata*:

(4.27) *il signore blu ha telefonata a polizia*
 the mr blue has telephoned:PTCP-PST-SG-F to police
 ‘Mr Blue has phoned the police’

(4.28) *e a fa la telefonata sì*
 and to does the phone-call yes
 ‘and he/she makes the phone-call’

At the same time the class contains adverbs with a very strong referential function: they denote a position in space or a deictic gesture, and can be seen as arguments of the verb.

(4.29) *ma alla ultima tempo la signora rossi fa così*
 but at the last:F time the mrs red does so
 ‘but the last time Mrs Red does so’

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(4.30) *poi lei va fuori di bagno*
then she goes out of bath
'then she comes out of the bathroom'

(4.31) *ma la persona rossa non va giù*
but the person red not goes down
'but the red person does not go down'

Adjectives do not cluster as a single class, but come often together with nouns and past participles. The reason may be that, even though the prototypical function of adjectives is to modify nouns, their use as a modifier is not favored by the task ("Finite Story" retelling). In our sample (both for natives and learners) they are mainly used as post copula predicative elements, like *grande* in:

(4.32) *ma adesso il fuoco è più grande e il signore blu ha*
but now the fire is more big and the mr blue has
più paura
more fear
'but now the fire has grown bigger and Mr Blue is more and more afraid'

In general all these elements tend to contrast functionally with finite verbs; in this class all verbs are non finite heads of implicit subordinates introduced by prepositions, something that can be considered (positionally, if not functionally) a noun-like behavior.

On the whole, it can be concluded that this category is functionally characterized through the grouping of non predicative elements (absence of finite verbs, or non finite verbs used as non TL-like predicative heads of VP, with the exception of one ambiguous instance of *telefonata*), with a tendency to referential use.

4.6.2.2 Category 2

Category 2 clusters together mostly finite verbs, but some exceptions are adverbs (*ancora, non, no, forse*; probably trapped positionally by their collocation near the predicative focus of the sentence) and numerals with a clear referential meaning in the context (*uno, due*), as in the following example.

(4.33) *e poi telefona uno uno otto ancora*
and then telephones one one eight again
'and then he telephones to one-one-eight again'

Other referential elements are pronouns (*lui, si*); still in this case, although we cannot explain out the attraction of referential elements (non noun-like, it must be underlined) the class is prototypically oriented towards grouping predicative elements: the only non finite verb has a clear predicative function, as in:

- (4.34) *il signor blu scendere la scale*
 the mr blue descend:INF the stairs
 ‘Mr Blue comes down the stairs’

4.6.2.3 Category 3

This group shows a high homogeneity, with the only non nominal element being a clitic, with referential function.

4.6.2.4 Category 4

Category 4 mostly groups pre/det elements, with the exception of verbs. It may be interesting to notice that prepositions, like verbs, have a valency to be filled by a referential element. This can explain the attraction of verbs in this category.

4.6.2.5 Category 5

This category groups mostly adverbs and function words, with one of the nouns occurring in the text in an adverbial construction:

- (4.35) *questo volta lui ha riposto questa chiamata*
 this:M time he has answered this call
 ‘This time he answers the call’

Some head-VP verbs are present too, as well as adjectives with predicative value (*forte, felice, contenti*)

- (4.36) *il signore rosso ancora non vuole scende*
 the mr red still not wants descends:IND-PRS-1SG
 ‘Mr Red still doesn’t want to come down’

- (4.37) *i pompieri parlare con signora rossa*
 the firefighters talk:INF with mrs red
 ‘The firefighters talk to Mrs Red’

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- (4.38) *ma adesso il fuoco è più forte quindi il blu preoccupa*
but now the fire is more strong so the blue worries
'But now the fire is getting stronger and the blue one is worried'

On the whole this cluster can be characterized by the lack of referential function.

4.6.2.6 Category 6

This class groups very sharply the proper nouns, since the color terms are used as such to identify the characters of the story, and often preceded by *signor*, *signora*; it's the only class that clearly coincides almost perfectly with a class in Biemann's experiment.

Interestingly enough this class emerges only from the IL sample.

Exceptions here are: *non lo so*, *non lo sa* constructions

4.6.2.7 Category 7

This last class is also quite homogeneous, clustering prep/det elements; *perché* is probably attracted by its usually pre NP position, as in:

- (4.39) *rossi è molto paura perché la tua camera è molto alto*
red is very fear because the your room is very high
'The red person is very afraid because his room is very high up'

4.7 Discussion

On the whole we can say that Biemann's methodology seems to cluster the items in a clearer way, as the comparison with the native sample shows. Probably this is due to the higher number of classes, which allows for a finer tuning. Still, from both experiments it is clear that, while the NL sample is quite homogeneous when formal criteria are taken into account, in the IL sample the overall picture becomes clearer when more functional criteria are taken into account.

Since the clusters are built solely on the basis of positional information, this seems to support the Basic Variety hypothesis that in the earlier stages of acquisition word order is highly influenced by the function of words and less by morphosyntactic reasons. In more advanced levels this becomes probably less true, approaching more and more to the TL structure, where the word order is more formally conditioned, with the result that positional information becomes a better predictor of the syntactic category.

Two caveats must be expressed when working on such a small and biased sample. In the first place the NL sample, though quite similar in content and length, is dissimilar from the IL sample in the fact that interaction with the interviewer is almost non-existent in the natives, and the stripping of the interviewer's lines has an almost null impact on the textual structure. The IL sample has more inter-turn interaction, and therefore shorter sentences, and this might impair the comparability of the samples. The second caveat is that the IL sample has been produced native speakers of Mandarin Chinese only. The choice has been made to avoid influences from other Standard Average European languages, with a class of syntactic categories too similar to the target. Still, some comparison should be made with a bigger and mixed IL sample, and a more interactive TL sample.

Another, greater theoretical problem with this experiment is that the formal analysis of the clusters has been conducted using the researcher's intuition only. When I say that a certain token has the form of an adjective I rely on many clues: the morphology, the position, the lexical root (or the similarity to a certain lexical root for some non-TL-like items); still the overall meaning of the sentence is influencing this tagging, and may lead to a comparative fallacy, as we shall see in the next chapters. Still, we have claimed that a clear separation of the formal and the functional levels is important when analyzing interlanguage.

From this experiment we can see how tokens in IL seem to cluster together in a way that only partially coincides with TL. But this is not yet a definite proof that IL categories differ from TL categories. It only shows that they have a very different distribution. In the next chapters we shall take other clues like morphology into a deeper consideration. To do this, we shall need to compare them directly to the target categories, according to their formal definition.

5

Target vs source categories

In the last chapter, we made an attempt at inducing word clusters based on similarity in distribution from a sample of interlanguage. A comparison was made between clusters induced from similar samples of native language, and this seems points at the conclusion that, when analyzing interlanguage clusters based on the sole distributional category, their degree of homogeneity seems to improve and to tend towards the homogeneity of the native sample's clusters.

Of course these clusters cannot be considered in any case as lexical categories given the exiguity of the samples and the subsequent extremely limited nature of the generalizations; still this test can be seen as supporting the intuition that positional features seem to align to the functional and semantical prototype of the target language earlier than the morpho-syntactical and lexical features .

In this chapter we shall concentrate on the consequences that this has from the applicative point of view. We have already stated that given the heterogeneity of interlanguages, any type of PoS tagging of IL corpora must necessarily resort to the target PoS inventory, and hence to the target lexical categories. We shall here show how a form oriented tagging is the only one that can both maintain the form/function contrast in IL, and at the same time give some possibility of operability and automatization. The main problem standing in the way of a viable IL PoS tagging is how to use TL tagging while keeping track of the significant amount of mismatching among the PoS's defining features that IL is expected to display.

A distribution-predominant method for the detection and the annotation of target oriented categories will be proposed. After an introduction to PoS tagging and IL category annotation, the notion of virtual category shall be introduced and a relatively

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simple yet efficient method of applying virtual categories to IL corpora shall be outlined. Subsequently the tagging performance will be evaluated and some qualitative analysis will be performed on an IL sample using an XML based context extractor.

5.1 Corpus tagging

When processing a text humans use a vast amount of information that is not directly present in the text itself. For instance when reading a book, a person knows that a single line printed in a bigger font at the top of a page is likely to be the title of a new chapter. Tagging a text means adding part of this information to the text in a way that is understandable and retrievable by a machine.

The information can be added both manually or automatically, but while the procedure of extracting the information from an annotated text can be done by a trivial algorithm, the procedure of adding new information to a text is something that requires some sort of human-like intelligence: if an algorithm is to add contextual information that is not present in the text, or make inferences from the text, it must somehow simulate human comprehension.

As seen in Chapter 3, PoS tagging is just one of the possible kinds of information that can be added to a text. The popularity of PoS tagging derives partly from the fact that it is a relatively easier task (with respect for instance to semantic annotation) and because it is necessary before deriving any other kind of information (like syntactic parsing).

What is needed for PoS tagging is a tokenized text, a PoS tagset, and some kind of preliminary information about how to assign a tag to each token. In the following paragraphs, we shall first introduce a tagset and subsequently an algorithm for PoS tagging Italian texts.

5.1.1 Defining a set of PoS for Italian

Literally, part of speech tagging means attributing each token of a text to a part of speech. Parts of speech are usually considered equivalent to lexical categories in theoretical linguistics, but computational linguists tend to use a much broader tagset, that represents not only the relevant category, but also some morphological traits. At the same time, since PoS tagging is in part related to the reconstruction of the lexical

root, the lemmatization is usually carried out along with it, even if lemmata are not always necessary to recognize the PoS of a certain token.

Usually each language has its own tagset, even though the tagsets of cognate languages contain many common tags. In order to apply PoS tagging, the description of lexical categories for Italian must be transformed into an operative set of PoS, that includes guidelines to apply the PoS in context, and that can be used for both manual and automatic tagging.

The EAGLES¹ specifications for Italian (Monachini 1996) define 12 main categories: nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, determiners, pronouns, articles, adpositions, conjunctions, numerals, interjections, and residuals. Subcategories are defined, that can be considered as equivalent to the features and values of figure 2.1

For what concerns ambiguity, the guidelines distinguish between members of a category that can carry morphological and syntactic features of another category, such as instances of infinite verbs that can be inserted in an NP

(5.1) *l' agire*
 the act:VER-INF
 "The acting"

and transcategorization phenomena, like:

(5.2) *il bello della vita*
 the beautiful:NOUN of life
 "The beautiful of life"

that contrasts with:

(5.3) *Un uomo bello*
 A man beautiful:ADJ
 "A beautiful man"

¹ The Expert Advisory Group on Language Engineering Standards (EAGLES) is an initiative of the European Commission, within the DG XIII Linguistic Research and Engineering programme, which aims to accelerate the provision of standards for:

- Very large-scale language resources (such as text corpora, computational lexicons and speech corpora);
- Means of manipulating such knowledge, via computational linguistic formalisms, mark up languages and various software tools;
- Means of assessing and evaluating resources, tools and products.

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In the first cases the guidelines recommend assigning an instance of infinite to the class of verbs, even if it shares some features with the class of nouns. In the second case the same token must be disambiguated according to whether the occurrence is an instance of adjective or noun.

The Evalita2007² guidelines for PoS tagging are not dissimilar from the ones proposed by Monachini. Here too we have a first level of categories, verbs, noun, proper nouns, articles, conjunctions, prepositions, adjectives, adverbs, interjections, numbers, pronouns, symbols, punctuation marks.

The main problems here can be seen in the absence of a class of determiners independent from that of articles, and in a greater attention to the class of residual, non lexical elements, here divided into symbols and punctuation marks.³

For the present purpose - that is to say from the perspective of the target oriented annotation of Interlanguage - what is required is a standard tagset that, while being suitable for both TL Italian and IL Italian samples, maintains a good distinction among all the classes that are considered crucial in the study of non native varieties. In this sense the EAGLES guidelines as modified by Evalita can be considered a good standard.

In particular it is to be underlined that, although articles can be considered as members of the broader class of determiners, it can be useful to keep them apart and annotate them with two specific tags (one for determinative and one for indeterminate articles) in order to be able to retrieve them easily, without having to add lemma information to the query. At the same time the attention given to more marginal classes like interjections and symbols can be very useful from the applicative point of view, in dealing with spoken, discourse annotated data.

5.1.2 Rule based vs probabilistic tagging

Let us now turn our attention to tagging algorithms. It is clear that a PoS tagging algorithm needs some information in order to apply tags to a raw text.

²Evalita 2007, now followed by Evalita 2009, is an initiative dedicated to the evaluation of Natural Processing tools for Italian. The general objective of EVALITA is to promote the development of language technologies for the Italian language, providing a shared framework where different systems and approaches can be evaluated in a consistent manner.

³Evalita 2007 also proposed a second task, with a Distributionally/Syntactically Oriented tagset, based on the one derived in Bernardi, Bolognesi, Seidenari & Tamburini (2006) with a distributional algorithm similar to the ones that we have described in chapter 4.

The first kind of information concerns the notion of word. In Chapter 2 we discussed how the notion of lexical category can apply at several levels (root, lemma, type, token). In this case PoS tagging applies at the token level, and the tagging program needs to be able to separate every single token from the others in the text. The problem of tokenization is a non trivial one, but it shall be taken for granted here, since it is partially solved by human transcribers and can be implemented without too much ambiguity for our present purposes. The standard format for a tokenized text, which constitutes the input for the PoS tagger is one token per line.

The other kinds of information needed by the tagger are of far greater importance for us. In the first place taggers must rely on some kind of lexicon: there lexical roots are stored together with a list of all the PoS connected to that root. In the second place a morphological analysis module should be present, providing a list of all possible morphological forms and their implications in terms of disambiguation and transcategorization. Finally the tagger must encode a set of syntactic or distributional (categorical or stochastic) rules in order to decide the final PoS assignment. Lexical, morphological, and positional information corresponds respectively to the level of lemma, type and token, and the syntactic or distributional level is considered decisive for the final disambiguation.

The methods that have been applied for contextual disambiguation can be roughly divided into two categories: rule based and stochastic. Rule based algorithms should be seen as sets of hand-written conditional statements. If token 1 is ambiguously assigned to tag “definite article” or “clitic”, the algorithm searches for a rule that has ‘tag = definite article or clitic’ as an initial condition and will start performing the checks that are stated in the rule; in this case the check may be on the following token: if the following token 2 has tag = finite verb, then token 1 is assigned to clitic, else if token 2 has tag = noun or adjective, token 1 is assigned to definite article.

Rules can be very complex and include checks on lemmas and morphology (agreement) over several positions; several conditions can be nested and checks will continue being performed until a possible combination of assignments can be derived. Clearly if a possible combination or sequence of tags has not been foreseen in the implementation, the tagger will not be able to disambiguate the context. With a rule based system it is very difficult to treat unknown cases; moreover tokens that do not correspond to any

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known lemma will not get a set of possible tags, thus making it impossible to disambiguate by context only. This is a crucial problem when dealing with learner varieties, which is expected to present a greater amount of non predictable tag sequences.

Stochastic models work in a different way. For each ambiguous token they assign a probability to each tag, based on the context. The algorithm needs to be trained on a hand tagged corpus; in the simplest model the possible tags for a token are derived by looking at the training corpus, by looking at all occurrences for the type. By always assigning the most frequent tag for each type, an accuracy of 90 % can be already easily reached for a native text, especially if the genre of the input is similar to that of the training. In order to improve this baseline, the training corpus is used to calculate the probability of certain patterns, which are then used to tag new data. This can be formalized as follows ($w = \text{word}$, $t = \text{tag}$):

(5.4)

$$t_1, \dots, t_n = \underset{t_1, \dots, t_n}{\operatorname{argmax}} P(t_1, \dots, t_n | w_1, \dots, w_n)$$

given a certain sequence of words (for instance a sentence), we want to find the sequence of tags with the highest probability.

The first taggers (Church 1988) used the Hidden Markov model which is still the most popular one (the TnT tagger, trained on the Penn treebank ⁴ uses this model). These models are based on two important assumptions: the probability of tag t_0 being the right tag for token w_0 depends only on (a) the token that w_0 happens to be and (b) on the sequence of tags that have been assigned to the preceding tokens; given a tagged corpus, the following equation can be used to maximize the parameter set;

(5.5)

$$t_1, \dots, t_n = \underset{t_1, \dots, t_n}{\operatorname{argmax}} \prod_{i=1}^n P(w_i | t_i) P(t_i | t_{i-1})$$

in the equation the term $P(w_i | t_i)$ represent assumption (a) and the term $P(t_i | t_{i-1})$ represent assumption (b). The most probable sequence of tags for a certain sequence

⁴Brants (2000)

of tokens is the one that depends on the probability of each single tag given the corresponding token and the probability of each tag given the preceding tag.⁵ Usually at least two preceding tags are used instead of just one (Second Order Markov models):

$$(5.6) \quad t_1, \dots, t_n = \operatorname{argmax}_{t_1, \dots, t_n} \prod_{i=1}^n P(w_i|t_i)P(t_i|t_{i-2}, t_{i-1})$$

By using the training corpus, the probability of the first term of this equation can be calculated as:

$$(5.7) \quad P(w_i|t_i) = \frac{f_q(t_i, w_i)}{f_q(t_i)}$$

the probability of a tag given a token can be approximated using the relative frequency of the tag being assigned to that token in the training corpus. If a token X is assigned to tag A 1/4 of the time, and to tag B 3/4 of the time, the probability of tag A given X is 0.25.

The second term is calculated as:

$$(5.8) \quad P(t_i|t_{i-2}, t_{i-1}) = \frac{f_q(t_{i-2}, t_{i-1}, t_i)}{f_q(t_{i-2}, t_{i-1})}$$

the probability of the sequence of tags (A, B,C) is equal to the relative frequency of the sequence (A, B, C) in the training corpus.

If the model is a Second Order Markov Model, training the tagger from a corpus means creating a file with the relative frequencies of the observed tag/token combinations (lexicon) and a file with the relative frequencies of all observed trigrams (parameters). When tagging an unknown text, the algorithm will use those frequencies and assign tags in a way that maximizes the equation in 5.6.

This model can be improved in many ways. By increasing the size of the training corpus, the number of unknown types is reduced, thus making it less likely that the tagger meets with an unknown type, or an unknown tag sequence. The performance

⁵The probability of the first tag is derived from the probability of the tag/token combination being at the beginning of a sentence

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can be further improved by extending the lexicon: taggers are usually provided with an independent lexicon in order to extend the one derivable from the training set; the lexicon lists the possible tags for rare tokens. Lemmatization is another useful way of extending the lexicon: if a certain inflected form has tag inventory A,B in the training set, it is possible to derive the lemma for that form and to reconstruct the entire paradigm for that lemma; since inflectional morphology does not change the categorization, the PoS inventory can be then extended from the available form to the others ⁶. Morphological analysis is another way of reducing ambiguity and analyzing unknown forms. Given the (extended) lexicon, a string of n characters at the beginning or at the end of each form can be taken into account; forms containing the same strings tend to coincide with morphological classes: the most common PoS in each class is assigned to the unknown form ⁷.

This kind of statistical modeling is consistent with the theoretical description of the problem of categories that was presented in Chapter 2. Here too the formal cues assigning a token to a specific category can be divided into different levels. In a native text the several levels point for a large part to the same category, but in order to improve accuracy to above the baseline and correctly tag the less frequent or more ambiguous tokens, more and more levels have to be taken into consideration.

Let us try now to extend this model to the analysis of interlanguage texts.

5.2 Desiderata of interlanguage annotation

Before trying to describe a way to efficiently recognize lexical categories, we first have to analyze what it is that we are trying to achieve by enriching a corpus with a morpho-syntactic annotation such as PoS tagging ⁸.

⁶Homograph forms, forms that instantiate two different lemmas, inherit their PoS inventory from both, and account for one of the possible kinds of ambiguous token.

⁷Imagine for instance the string *-avano* in Italian, which is clearly identifying the 3rd person plural imperfect mark; an unknown form terminating in *-avano* will be matched to the known forms, like *mangiavano*, *volavano*, almost all of which are potential verbs; so the unknown form has a great likelihood of being a verb and can be assigned to this class.

⁸These ideas were developed within the framework of a project on SLA-tagging which was carried out at the Laboratory of Language Resources (LARL) of the Linguistics Department of the University of Pavia, under the supervision of Anna Giacalone, Cecilia Andorno and Stefano Rastelli (Rastelli & Frontini 2008); for further information see the internet site of the project: <http://sla-tagging.unipv.it>.

5.2 Desiderata of interlanguage annotation

Given the assumption that SLA research consists in making hypotheses about learner data, when preparing a corpus for general research purposes one should try to facilitate, rather than substitute human re-analysis. A good annotation system for lexical categories should therefore provide a way to investigate the typical form-function split in IL, and should do this in the most consistent way possible – at the same time avoiding any preconceived ideas about the nature of learner data.

Most importantly, the quality of SLA tagging should be evaluated according to five parameters:

Specificity - as seen in previous chapters, a specific form-function pairing is prototypical of a specific language, and it cannot be taken for granted in IL, which then calls for a separation of function and form in the treatment of IL categories. In IL a verb in the first person singular can be used to refer to third person plural objects, a masculine adjective can modify a feminine noun. Also, forms that are utterly impossible in TL can occur in IL with specific functions; tagging should be IL specific enough to be able to signal, in some way, the form and function split typical of IL;

Efficiency - on the side of context extraction this should be reflected in the researchers (end users of the corpus) being facilitated in retrieving unexpected regularities in the corpus; the issue of non circularity is very important: researchers should be helped to find new interesting contexts, and not just those which have been already marked up in the corpus release;

Comparability - at the same time tags should be applicable to different types of IL and TL as well, so that researchers can compare the presence or absence of certain features across different samples - in order to verify hypotheses concerning the principles governing learner varieties;

Usability - since all interlanguage varieties target the TL, so the tagset too should bear a link to the grammatical categories of the TL. Ideally, the tags should allow the researcher to use his or her own competence in the TL to query for contexts;

Scalability - a final, important requirement that annotation can be performed on

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large and heterogeneous amounts of data in a way that is both consistent and annotator independent.

One way of treating learner corpora is by tagging errors. Error tagging has its strength in specificity, since a specific tagset of errors is created to describe the idiosyncrasy of ILs with respect to their TL; for what concerns categories, error tagging works in tandem with functional PoS tagging: each token is attributed a PoS tag according to functional clues which are subject to the interpretation of the human annotator, whereas error tagging carries the information about the formal mismatch (“this token has the function of a noun, hence is PoS tagged as a noun, but lacks the formal traits of a noun, e.g. plural inflection, and this will be signaled by the error tag”).

For a more complex analysis of error tagging in morpho-syntactic annotation the reader is referred to specific sources like Granger (2003), Díaz-Negrillo & Fernández-Domínguez (2006), Lüdeling, Walter, Kroymann & Adolphs (2005). In particular a criticism of error tagging can be found in Rastelli (2007). Rastelli’s criticism points out the problems in error tagging with respect to the issues of efficiency, comparability and usability: error tagging superimposes such a highly theory-biased and often opaque markup on the IL corpus, that it scarcely offers any help to the researcher in investigating new phenomena.

Another important fact that we want to underline here is that error tagging is a practice that requires a great amount of human skill, and is thus problematic from the point of view of scalability: even provided that a large number of annotators is available, a lot of training and cross checking is necessary in order to reach consistency and inter-annotator agreement ⁹.

Our alternative idea is to explore instead the possibility of using some machine tagging tool in order to allow for a quick and consistent yet unbiased and theoretically-light enrichment of IL corpora. Instead of a function to form approach, a form to function approach is proposed: the annotation of the IL corpus should record the form of each token, and leave it to the researcher to verify the alignment of the form to the TL function. The idea is simple, if a token has the form of a verb (according to the formal definition of verb in the TL), then it should be tagged as a verb; it may well

⁹Inter-annotator disagreement is a serious issue in all kinds of manual tagging, even in simple PoS tagging of TL corpora (Bayerl & Paul 2007); when applying IL specific error tags, the disagreement can only increase.

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be that not all tokens tagged as verbs have the function of predicates, but this kind of analysis should be left to the end-user of the corpus: the researcher.

Formal annotation has the advantage of being scalable, since it is easy to implement a consistent tagging of formal traits. At the same time, tagging tokens in IL by their formal resemblance to TL categories means that the tagset mirrors the one used for the target language, thus improving the comparability and the usability and the annotation.

5.3 Tagging with virtual categories and confidence levels

The key potential difficulty that this proposal faces is specificity: how can a formal, target oriented automatic tagging be able to capture the idiosyncratic features of IL; how can it help to enrich an IL text with information that - without being too intrusive - can still help the researcher to spot interesting contexts and peculiar features?

Let's go back to TL tagging: algorithms performing formal stochastic PoS tagging rely, as we have seen, on several cues, mainly morphology, lemma, position. When the formal traits do not align, the tagger has to make a choice between the different tagging options of each formal dimension according to the weights that have been derived from the training set. When different outcomes are possible, the algorithm compares their relative probability and issues a tentative tag and a numeric value, which represents the confidence the tagger has in the tag being the right one. This implies that there is a right answer but that the tagging algorithm has trouble in figuring it out because it cannot rely on semantic/pragmatic cues.

Now what about IL: if a TL trained tagger is run on an IL corpus many more mismatches and ambiguous contexts will emerge. But here there is no right solution, because of the form/function mismatch. The idea is to change our perspective, accept that formal categories are all that we can hope to tag, and that if a mismatch occurs between formal traits, then this may be a hint of an unclear categorization, not just of a difficulty of the algorithm in tagging an otherwise clear category.

In our proposed categories we let the algorithm recognize the most formally plausible tag for each token, using a NL tagset and NL training (resulting in NL weights); but, since we want to make it clear that there is a difference between the automatically recognized tag and the TL lexical category of the same name, we use the term **virtual category**.

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We define VIRTUAL CATEGORY as a word category (noun, verb, ...) that has been recognized on the basis of FORMAL TRAITS only, without any assumption of its FUNCTION. In other terms, a virtual category is a category which must undergo successive researchers' evaluation as far as its function is concerned, before it can be accepted as a real category. Among the virtual categories, those which are more interesting are obviously those showing some higher level of mismatch, like those whose lemma could not be recognized, and which had to be assigned on the basis of reconstructed morphology or distribution alone.

For instance, in order to be listed as a virtual adjective, an item does not need to match all formal, functional and distributional criteria (as it happens for L1 items). It suffices that it can meet just one or two of these requirements with a low degree of probability (a low confidence rate). Once the researcher has set the appropriate confidence rate for each criteria, the TreeTagger is likely to output a list of unexpected virtual adjectives. When looking up this list, the researcher will find: (a) items which are not adjectives from a formal point of view but that are used with an adjective-like distribution and function; (b) items which are considered adjectives only in virtue of their position; (c) items which are considered adjectives only in virtue of their lexical root or of their suffix. We claim that this is a reliable starting ground for SLA research, since the most useful data to SLA research is free from our expectations (on form/function mappings) and free from obligatory context (the position where we expect the items to be).

In particular we claim here that error tagging can be partly overridden by using a mix of VIRTUAL CATEGORIES, CONFIDENCE LEVELS and POSITIONAL INFORMATION.

Let us here emphasize that virtual categories, although bearing the name and features of target categories, are virtual, hence non interpreted. In this sense comparative fallacy in the sense of Bley-Vroman (1983) is avoided, since using the same names of TL categories does not imply that the same rules are at work in the analyzed sample.

5.3.1 Running L1 tagger on a L2 data

Since tagging by virtual categories basically only implies a change in the way we look at the tagging process and its outcome, it can be performed by any TL trained stochastic PoS tagging algorithm. PoS tagging having been considered with or without good

5.3 Tagging with virtual categories and confidence levels

reason a “solved NLP problem” for statistically driven computational linguistics ¹⁰, the performances of most taggers on native samples do not influence us in our choice of the ideal tagger for our goals. Instead our preference is based on:

- **availability**: many good tagging algorithms have limited or no access; worse even, they are freely distributed with English parameters and training, but it’s hard to retrain them for Italian since most of the resources (corpora, lexica, and morphological analyzers) are only partially available;
- **number of features** that are separately considered in order to achieve a PoS tagging with confidence when more than one option is possible

TreeTagger (Schmid 1994, Schmid 1995) is a freely available stochastic tagger developed at the IMS of the University of Stuttgart, Germany. It was first applied to English, but was immediately afterwards modified and extended to cope with morphology rich languages including German, and the Romance languages. It has a good support service¹¹ and is being constantly improved (the last improvement for Italian was the version presented for Evalita 2009).

The main difference between TreeTagger and other stochastic taggers lays in its statistical underpinnings: instead of using a Markov Model, TreeTagger uses decision trees. A decision tree (or tree diagram) is a decision support tool that uses a tree-like graph or model of decisions and their possible consequences, including chance event outcomes, resource costs, and utility. Decision trees are commonly used as a descriptive means for calculating conditional probabilities.

It is important for us here to take stock of which conditional probabilities TreeTagger takes into account. TreeTagger has the goal of performing well on morphology rich languages. For this reason, alongside the normal lexicon of lemmas and inflected forms, the morphological level of analysis has been particularly well developed by implementing an analyzer of prefixes and suffixes. As far as the distributional parameters are concerned, a version for Italian is available, trained on the Repubblica corpus.

The way in which the formal cues interact is also significant: when the token has a type in the lexicon that gives just one possible tag, this is applied with confidence 1.0.

¹⁰With accuracy over 97 %, for newspaper texts - see the results of the PoS tagging task of Evalita 2009 for Italian results

¹¹<http://ims.stuttgart/treegagger>

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In all other cases guessing is necessary. Iterated subtraction of initial (as described in note 7) and terminal letters is used to find a clue to the lemma, and at the same time to correlate the subtracted elements with morphological classes. Those hints are then combined with the positional weights given by the training.

Let's examine these three artificial examples, the first is a correct italian sentence, the second has a problem in the verbal morphology (*-iemo* instead of *-iamo*) and the last combines the morphological with the positional problem (the object preceding the verb is a marked structure only possible as a dislocation in spoken texts to mark the status of the destination (Newcastle) as new information).

(5.9) *Oggi andiamo a Newcastle*
today we:go to Newcastle
“Today we go to Newcastle / Let's go to Newcastle today”

Here's what the TreeTagger output looks like ¹²:

token	tag	lemma	confidence
oggi	ADV	oggi	0.997884
andiamo	VER:cpre	andare	0.384356
a	PRE	a	0.999163
Newcastle	NPR	Newcastle	1.000000
.	SENT	.	1.000000

In this correct sentence the only case of low ambiguity applies to the verb, since it is can be interpreted as an *imperative* or as an *indicative*; the tagger outputs a guess, and interprets this sentence as an exhortative (“let's go to Newcastle”). In fact when creating this artificial example (on a train to Newcastle!) we intended it as an unambiguous statement.

Moral: even when analyzing TL like utterances, looking at confidence levels can make us aware of ambiguities that we may overlook because of semantics or extralinguistic information.

(5.10) *Oggi andiemo a Newcastle.*
today we:go(?) to Newcastle
“Today we go to Newcastle”

¹²TreeTagger comes with two tagsets: the complete list with definitions, together with the reasons for choosing Stein's over Baroni's can be found in Appendix E; as to the distinction between between PoS and lexical category: see reference in Chapter 2.

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Here's what the TreeTagger output looks like:

token	tag	lemma	confidence
oggi	ADV	oggi	0.994090
andiamo	VER:futu	<unknown>	0.788243
a	PRE	a	0.998948
Newcastle	NPR	Newcastle	1.000000
.	SENT	.	1.000000

The new element here is the misspelled form of the verb *andiamo* becoming *andiamo*; as a consequence, the lexicon is incapable of recognizing the lemma. Still the ending is separated, the closest morphological class is recognized by the algorithm and the tag attributed according to the most frequent PoS for that class. Note that in this case the confidence is higher, since the imperative option is ruled out. What is immediately interesting is this: we wanted to construct a fake example of a “wrong” present indicative, but we ended up with a future indicative. Once again we see how much more consistent the algorithm is when compared to human taggers: the *-emo* ending has certainly bears a clear similarity to the future TL marking. The tagger correctly records this, and the presence of an unknown lemma is a clear sign of some problem: this context as it is contains a clear and retrievable signal to the researcher to investigate further. Note also the interaction position/morphology: the confidence value for the neighbor tokens changes with the influence of the *andiamo* tagging.

Moral: the clever human tagger would have tagged this as a present indicative verb, intending the *-iemo* as an allomorph of *-iamo* for this variety. But this would be going beyond the limits of annotation. The ‘dull’ automatic algorithm records that here we have a virtual future present, and the researcher is invited to check all these virtual future forms to see whether the IL paradigm form is really used as a variant to the present form, or whether it isn't perhaps the case that there is a different and consistent paradigm (with the look and feel of a future) that may be used in connection with specific functions that are different from those of the TL present and maybe also of the TL future¹³.

¹³Remember that we are talking about virtual, i.e. formal resemblance, and the labels we use are just there to give an idea of the form that they cover; one could call this category ‘c22’, but it's easier and user friendlier to say that it's a virtual future: a verb with an ending that occurs usually in the inflection of Italian future.

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- (5.11) *Oggi a Newcastle andiamo .*
today to Newcastle we:go(?)
“Today we go to Newcastle”

Here’s how the TreeTagger output looks like:

token	tag	lemma	confidence
oggi	ADV	oggi	0.976942
a	PRE	a	0.999065
Newcastle	NPR	Newcastle	1.000000
andiamo	VER:futu	<unknown>	0.635622
.	SENT	.	1.000000

In the last case the expected sequential order of the sentence is scrambled. The construction with VERB final is not impossible in Italian but is less frequent, so this lowers the confidence level, in comparison with the previous case. Still the morphological analysis doesn’t change, and makes it possible to recognize this as a verb even in absence of the lemma. In other words lacking another alternative, the algorithm has to accept this token as a verb, but seems to underline its ‘disappointment’ at the uncommon position of this verb by lowering the confidence level from 0.78 to 0.63, due to the strong weight conferred to positional cues.

Moral: statistical PoS taggers are sensitive to infrequent contexts; in native texts infrequent contexts often are just odd or marginal sentence orderings, but in IL infrequent or odd orders are often something that the researcher may want to check, since they may underline a different grammar in the observed variety.

5.3.2 TreeTagger Output

Now we are ready to apply TreeTagger to our IL corpora. The sequence of steps to do that is as follows:

1. we shall use both written (ISA) and spoken corpora available at the University of Pavia: the Chini Corpus, the Pavia Corpus, the Marco Polo Corpus, ISA (See the appendix C for a description of the corpora, and appendix A for an example of spoken corpus cleaning from CHAT annotation);
2. the cleaned text is passed to a script that performs tokenization according to the rules of TL Italian and passes the result to the Italian TreeTagger, which, in its turn, outputs:

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- formal VIRTUAL CATEGORIES
- lemmas (including lemma <unknown>)
- confidence level

3. The output information is transformed with a second script into XML (see Appendix D for more details on the tagging procedure) and contexts can be retrieved by using either Xqueries or a XML aware concordancer like XAIRA (Burnard 2004).

5.3.3 Finding interesting contexts

In this section some examples of context extraction will be given and commented on in order to show how productive the proposed approach is. For each example the query (in verbal format) and the results will be listed, and a commentary will follow. It should be borne in mind that this chapter is primarily dedicated to the exposition of a new tagging methodology, and that the following examples should only be taken as possible ways of how the end user (the researcher) might take advantage of our annotation system. For this reason the following context extractions are necessarily poor from the theoretical point of view and may perhaps seem rather trivial to the SLA expert. Our hope is that they will nonetheless intrigue the researcher, and that given the simplicity of implementation, they will also encourage him or her to try SLA tagging on a wider range of examples.

5.3.3.1 Example 1: Working with unknown lemma

We retrieve tokens with lemma <unknown> that have been tagged as verbs (at this stage the level of confidence is ignored). The query outputs contexts such as:

(5.12) *il ragazzo pienere su la roccia per gridare*
the boy <unknown>:VER on the rock to scream
“The boy climbed(?) on the rocks to scream”

(from Corpus Chini)

The tagger recognizes something that could resemble the infinite suffix “-ere” even if it is attached to an unknown stem

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(5.13) *ogni giorno conosca dieci persone*
every day he.meets ten people
“Every day he meets ten people”

(from Corpus Pavia)

Both root and morphological agreement are target like, but the lemma is not recognised.

5.3.3.2 Example 2: Working with low confidence

We query for verbs with lemma NOT<unknown> which have been tagged with confidence level less than 1.0; the results we get are:

- Categorial ambiguity in isolation (*sveglia*:NOUN, ‘alarm-clock’) vs *sveglia*:VER-3SG, ‘wake up’)

(5.14) *quando si sveglia il bambino*
when REFL wakes up the child
“When the child wakes up ”

(from Corpus Chini)

- Well formed item in ill formed context: the presence of the verb *continuare* normally requires *a*+infinitive

(5.15) *Continua chiamandola*
He.keeps calling.her:VER-GERUN
“He keeps on calling her ”

(from Corpus Chini)

- Ill-formed items: like *costruggendo*, which apparently stem from the root of the TL verb *costruendo* (‘build’)

(5.16) *è sotto una nave che si sta costruendo*
is under a ship that IMPS is being built
“he is under a ship that is being built ”

5.3.3.3 Example 3: combining constraints

We query for *virtual adjectives* under some distributional constraints (post copula *è*, post modifier) and according to a low rate of confidence. Here is one of the results:

(5.17) *la donna è molto tardi*
 the:SG-F woman is very late
 ‘the woman is very late’

(5.18) *il ragazzo è noiso*
 the:SG-M boy:SG-M is boring:SG-M
 ‘the boy is boring’

(5.19) *la donna è molta bassa*
 the:SG-F woman is very short:SG-F
 ‘the woman is very short’

(5.20) *lui non è simpatico e la donna molta trista*
 he not is nice and the:SG-F woman very sad:SG-F
 ‘he’s not very nice and the woman is very sad’

The item *simpatico* ‘funny’ is recognized as being an adjective because it matches perfectly the corresponding target-like form both in the lexical root and in the suffix. The item *trista*, ‘sad’, is preceded by the item *molta* with which it seems to agree in gender (they share the typical Italian feminine ending *-a*). In contrast, *simpatico*, *trista* is signaled as being an adjective in virtue of its lexical root but in spite of its incorrect suffix (*trist-a* instead of *triste-e*) and because it is preceded by *molta*. Interestingly, *molta* is recognized as being an adverb in virtue of the frequency of its co-occurrence pattern even if the proper form would be *molto* (ADV, ‘very’) (Frontini & Rastelli 2009).

5.3.3.4 Form/function Mapping

We query for ART (article) + NOUN contexts (where NOUN has low level of confidence). In those cases the distribution has forced the second element to be classified as a noun because of the context, but the morphology and the lemma of tokens *chiama*, *catolica*, and *andata* tell a different story (see the glosses).

(5.21) *Dopo il chiama di telefono*
 Later the:SG-M calls:PRS-3SG of telephone
 ‘After the phonecall’

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(5.22) *ho volia di studiare il catolica sì*
have:PRS-1SG want:SG-F of to study:Inf the:SG-M catholic:SG-F yes
'I want to study/learn the Catholic (one)'

(5.23) *sì l aadata è molto difficile*
yes the:? gone:NOUN/PTCP-PST-SG-F is very difficult:SG
'yes, the journey (to our destination) was very difficult'

5.3.4 PoS tagger performances on L2 texts

The cases discussed in the previous section allowed us to elucidate an investigative procedure that we think might be interesting. But one possible objection may run as follows: 'interesting contexts' may be found even by randomly extracting sentences from an IL corpus. IL corpora are notoriously full of interesting contexts – indeed that's why we like them!

In order to prove that our methodology does in fact make sense, we need to answer two questions:

- is the average tagging confidence and the number of unknown lemmas higher in an IL corpus as compared to a native one?

- if so, are the unknown tags and the low confidence levels a reliable indicator of an 'interesting context', that is to say of an interesting non TL-like mismatch of form and function?

Before answering those questions we shall make a very simple assumption: it's obvious that a stochastic tagger will find a certain number of troublesome contexts (and even may ever register some failures) in a native sample. The average number of unknown lemmas, the average confidence per tag and the average accuracy rate will be our baseline. All that is beyond this baseline must be significant, otherwise it would just mean that the TreeTagger is so confused by the IL sample that it cannot make any sense of what it sees.

We compare the native and non native sample of the Marco Polo corpus, due to the high level of homogeneity in the task.

Table 5.1 shows the differences in the tagging output between the NL and the IL samples, the number of files and the overall number of tokens in the samples are

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listed; for each sample the average number of unambiguous tags is given (number of all tags tagged with 1.0 confidence in the sample, divided by the number of tokens in the sample) as well as the average number of unknown lemmas; finally the average confidence number is given: the confidence numbers of each tag issued are summed up and divided by the number of tokens in the sample. ($\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n c(t_i)}{n}$).

	files	tokens	non ambiguous	unknown	average confidence
TL	28	10461	0.57	0.042	0.9424
NL	19	10466	0.59	0.004	0.9450

Table 5.1: Compared tagging output

	files	tokens	average confidence
TL	28	6711	0.9249
NL	19	6513	0.9396

Table 5.2: Compared tagging output - only full categories (verbs, nouns, adjectives, adverbs)

	files	tokens	average confidence
TL	28	3331	0.8493
NL	19	2952	0.8667

Table 5.3: Compared tagging output - only full categories (verbs, nouns, adjectives, adverbs) and excluding unambiguous items (confidence =1),

From table 5.1 we can see that the overall confidence levels are not very different: this convergence can probably be explained by the more complex use of language of the NL informants on one side, and on the relatively advanced level (basic to post basic) of the Marco Polo IL sample informants. Still, when checking the number of non ambiguous items and, above all, of unrecognized lemmas, the difference between target language and native language is revealed more clearly. In fact, as we have seen in the above examples, the most interesting cases emerge when we search for contexts that combine unknown lemma with low confidence level.

The differences in the confidence rate become clearer when looking at table 5.2, where function words have been excluded from the count and, more specifically, when

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taking into account only the ambiguous items, those with confidence less than 1. What table 5.3 tells us in plain words is that the average ambiguous item in the TL samples is “more ambiguous” than the average ambiguous item in the NL sample.

Let’s now see what happens when querying for tokens with unknown lemma, at varying degrees of confidence (5.4):

confidence	< 0.5	0.5 < x < 0.7	0.7 < x < 1
insances found	18	98	149
applied tags	mostly verbs or nouns	nouns, verbs, adjectives	adjectives, nouns and verbs
tagging output	most contexts spurious, interesting treatment of onomatopoeic	high amount of noun/adjective ambiguity, some of which is interesting	mostly interesting cases, especially of morphological reconstruction
example	<i>drin</i> VER:impe	<i>dormenta</i> NOM (TL addormenta ‘falls asleep’)	<i>vuoio/vuoiono</i> (TL voglio/volgiono ‘want’); <i>ser-vare</i> (TL salvare ‘save’)

Table 5.4: Confidence level intervals and the information that we can extract from them.

Obviously only content words can be ambiguous, that is, even if some mispronounced function words (namely articles and prepositions) could be mistaken for content words. These are the kind of contexts that are less interesting for us. Other less interesting contexts occur when the tagger relies on some weak positional clue only; in those cases the output relies heavily on guesswork and the confidence level is very low. By querying for confidence levels around 0.7-0.9 instead, many interesting cases can be found, since the slightly higher confidence level - in cases when the lemma cue is missing - is a sign that some morphological analysis was possible and has been combined with the positional one. In this last group some interesting cases of paradigm reconstruction can be found, as for example the *vuoio/vuoiono* alternation for the first person singular and the third person plural of the present indicative of *volere*, clear evidence that the Marco

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Polo informants mastered the verbal morphology but overextend the stem *vuo-* from the other persons of the paradigm.

Our conclusion is therefore that the annotation system outperforms random querying, but one still has to cope with some degree of spurious data. The most interesting cases can be found when lemma information is not retrieved; in those cases, when choosing a very low level of confidence, noisier data should be expected, but many interesting idiosyncrasies of IL can be found; when raising the confidence to medium level, the data is less noisy, and some interesting cases of form/function mismatch are found; when confidence is highest, given that lexical information is absent, some clear morphological cue must have been recognised: data is usually less noisy and even form function ambiguities are less frequent, but interesting phenomena of alternative but regular paradigms, and formal reconstructions of the TL morphological rules by the learners can be found.

6

Quantitative analysis - Target categories

In the previous chapters a system for PoS tagging has been proposed and it has been used to enhance the extraction of relevant contexts from interlanguage corpora. Although the annotation of virtual categories with low confidence levels can be considered as a way of automatically detecting interesting evidence within the corpus, context extraction still remains a hypothesis driven method of investigation.

In this last chapter a different kind of analysis shall be presented as an example of how PoS distribution can be used to conduct a bottom up quantitative comparison of different varieties of IL, both with each other and with the TL.

6.1 Quantitative Corpus analysis applied to IL corpora

Quantitative analysis of text samples is typical of disciplines like computational stylistics, forensic linguistics and text analysis. The common idea behind these disciplines is that quantitative techniques can be used in profiling, i.e., in the identification of the most salient features in a particular person or register (Crystal 1991).

One of the tasks that is normally connected with profiling is authorship detection; in this case some distinctive quantitative patterns in the text are used as a fingerprint in order to identify the author of a text. But genre recognition and text classification can also be seen as similar problems. All these issues can be modeled as clustering problems: is there a group of texts in the sample that share greater similarity with each other? and how does Text A fit in?

Profiling can be carried out by measuring various linguistic features, referring to vocabulary, lexical patterns, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, information content or item

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distribution throughout a text; still there is a conceptual difference between authorship and classification, which can be seen as two perpendicular tasks: the perfect algorithm for authorship would in fact group all texts by the same author no matter if poetry or prose, while text classification must separate texts by the same author according to the genre.

Moreover, in authorship detection the aim is to capture a unique combination of features that can be seen as distinctive of a single individual no matter whether he/she is aware of using them, and requires therefore an analysis of as much linguistic information as possible: the best algorithm in this case will be the one that combines as many measures as possible (Stamatatos, Fakotakis & Kokkinakis 2000). On the contrary the detection of textual category must rely on a specific subgroup of features, that are capable of capturing linguistic register, lexical richness, syntactic complexity. In this case lexical and syntactic indicators seem to be good predictors of textual category. In Laudanna & Voghera (2002) for instance the difference between the relative frequency of verbs and nouns in spoken versus written Italian is described. More generally, the frequencies of PoS *n*-grams (sequences of *n* parts of speech) can be considered as a good indicator of stylistic differences.

In Granger & Rayson (1998) and Aarts & Granger (1998) the idea of applying text categorization techniques to the analysis of interlanguage was first introduced. Given the hypothesis that each sample of interlanguage is characterized by a unique matrix of frequencies of various forms, the same techniques used in profiling could be applied to non native corpora in order to extract groups with consistently similar behavior. In the authors' own words: "if tag sequences can help us discover writers' fingerprints (here they were talking about stylometry), one can assume that they can help uncover EFL learners' fingerprints." Aarts & Granger (1998, 132).

Subsequent to these tests, which were carried out on the International Corpus of Learner English, similar analyses have been attempted on other samples, such as the Japanese EFL Learner Corpus (Tono 2000).

In Nerbonne & Wiersma (2006) the PoS tri-gram distribution is used as a measure of distances between text samples, and applied in a test analysis of a 305,000 word corpus containing the English of Finnish emigrants to Australia. The method seems to be capable of capturing the differences between two different groups (adult vs. child emigrants) and also in highlighting syntactic deviations between the two groups.

All the cited works used samples of interlanguages of English. In this chapter we are going to attempt a similar test using a sample of Italian IL and NL texts, and their frequencies of PoS n -grams as a comparing measure.

6.2 Theoretical presuppositions

In the previous chapter the outcome of a possible target tagging has been described; target categories have been defined as virtual categories when applied to IL, since they may not describe real categories for the IL system they are applied to, but only represent the nearest TL category to each IL token, possibly with some level of approximation.

In this chapter the degree of approximation will not be taken into account. When choosing a post-basic sample the following assumptions can be made that:

- a** word tokens in the texts can be unambiguously assigned to a specific PoS, since a system of syntactic distinctions has replaced the pragmatic mode typical of pre-basic levels;
- b** the system of lexical categories should be grossly equivalent to the target system, even though not all formal criteria seem to converge;
- c** an acceptable tagging can be achieved using the TreeTagger algorithm, which emphasizes the weight of positional criteria over morphological ones (typically problematic even at advanced stages of acquisition);
- d** the differences in the PoS distribution between post-basic IL samples and TL samples are not such that make a comparison impossible; the range of the differences between IL and TL is certainly greater than the one between different varieties of TL, but it can be studied using the same techniques that text analysis applies to detect stylistic variation in TL.

Given these presuppositions, the hypothesis that we want to verify in our test is whether there is some correlation between the level of syntactic development and the PoS distribution between IL samples of TL and IL. We know that PoS distributions have been successfully used in the detection of stylistic varieties. The reason why this is possible relies on the concept of optionality. The grammar of a language normally contains different devices to convey similar meanings. Sometimes native speakers tend to overuse

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specific devices over others; this can be due to diamesic, diaphasic, diastratic, diatopic conditions, or can be simply determined by the preference of the single speaker (style). When the differences concern the syntactic level, they tend to reflect in the distribution of lexical categories, and can be used to extract a measure between sample pairs.

6.3 Specification and Methodology of the Experiment

6.3.1 The corpus

For this experiment three text collections have been selected from the corpora described in C:

- Corpus Chini - German native speakers (henceforth GER) - 63 conversations = 63 files
- Corpus Chini - Spanish native speakers (henceforth SPA) 18 conversations = 18 files
- Corpus LIP- Italian native speakers as control corpus (henceforth ITA) - 66 conversations = 18 files

As far as **homogeneity** is concerned :

- Corpus LIP has not been collected in the same way as Corpus Chini; the themes are different, the number of informants is larger and the elicitation methods could be different;
- Corpus LIP is nonetheless a spoken corpus, and the interview subcorpus has been selected;
- the cleaning of the corpus from textual annotation has been carried out in the same way (described in A).

6.3.2 The tagset and the n -grams

As seen in the last chapter, the selected texts have been annotated using **TreeTagger** (Schmid 1994, Schmid 1995), with the Italian tagset by Achim Stein(E).

Subsequently, the sequences of one, two, and three PoS (hence Uni-grams, Bi-grams, Tri-grams) have been taken into account. In table 6.1 the overall number of n -grams per group is given. Notice that the figures differ by just one unit, due to the fact that overlapping sequences are used. In other words a text containing the sequences A B C

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D E, will count 5 uni-grams (A, B, C, D, E), 4 bi-grams (A B, B C, C D, D E) and 3 tri-grams (A B C, B C D, C D E).

Table 6.1: Number of n -grams

	Uni-grams(=tokens)	Bi-grams	Tri-grams
ita	221747	221746	221745
spa	18524	18523	18522
ger	56775	56774	56773

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6.3.3 Some qualitative observations

In table 6.2 the uni-grams have been listed in decreasing frequency order. For the IL groups GER and SPA, as well as for the TL control group ITA, nouns and verbs are the most frequent PoS. The noun/verb ratio does not vary much within the groups, but the IL groups show some over-representation. As a general fact more frequent categories tend to be overused in IL, and less frequent ones to be underused, as can be seen by observing the low ranked categories. Adverbs too are under-represented in IL, although quite highranked (probably an effect of the oral medium). The most striking divergence between IL and TL is the overuse of articles; this could be a general IL feature, which has also been noticed for English IL (Granger & Rayson 1998). As for the non categorized items (NOCAT), they are obviously more frequent in the IL samples, although not strikingly more frequent.

In table 6.3 the first 20 most frequent bi-grams in ITA and their frequencies in the 3 groups are listed (for the first 20 in SPA and GER see Appendix A). First of all it should be observed that the bi-gram combinations that are present in at least one of the 3 samples are 1106 out of 2401 possible bi-grams. This means that more than one half of the possible bi-grams are never effectively produced in the samples. As for the differences between TL and IL, here again some common combinations (ART NOUN, AUX:fin VER:ppast) are strongly overused by the two IL groups. On the other side ITA shows a stronger preference for sentences beginning with verbs or adverbs (table 6.4).

Similar considerations can be made for the table 6.5; here again the first 20 most frequent tri-grams in ITA and their frequencies in the 3 groups are listed (for the first 20 in SPA and GER see Appendix A). Note that the effectively represented trigrams are 11175 out of 117649 possible tri-grams. Here again the most frequent combination in ITA is over-represented in the IL groups.

Finally, general data on the underuse of CLI alone and in combination with other PoS can be derived for the GER sample, probably due to a transfer effect, since the NL does not have clitic pronouns in the same form as the Romance languages (ITA, SPA).

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
NOUN	29082	2844	9237	0.13115	0.15353	0.16269

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VER:fin	25910	2484	6410	0.11684	0.13410	0.11290
ADV	24122	1046	4474	0.10878	0.05647	0.07880
SENT	19982	704	3588	0.09011	0.03800	0.06320
PRE	13564	1536	3643	0.06117	0.08292	0.06417
ART	12358	1681	5368	0.05573	0.09075	0.09455
ADJ	10672	1255	2951	0.04813	0.06775	0.05198
CLI	8096	647	1306	0.03651	0.03493	0.02300
CON	7400	897	3932	0.03337	0.04842	0.06926
PUN	5922	149	470	0.02671	0.00804	0.00828
VER:ppast	5868	585	1570	0.02646	0.03158	0.02765
PRO:pers	5544	468	1374	0.02500	0.02526	0.02420
AUX:fin	5096	455	1393	0.02298	0.02456	0.02454
ARTPRE	4860	404	1745	0.02192	0.02181	0.03074
CHE	4812	565	1002	0.02170	0.03050	0.01765
WH	4762	354	916	0.02147	0.01911	0.01613
VER:infi	4752	390	1055	0.02143	0.02105	0.01858
NOCAT	4012	555	1564	0.01809	0.02996	0.02755
NEG	3880	265	961	0.01750	0.01431	0.01693
NPR	3332	134	363	0.01503	0.00723	0.00639
PRO:demo	2644	110	214	0.01192	0.00594	0.00377
VER2:fin	2630	88	434	0.01186	0.00475	0.00764
PRO:indef	2152	161	384	0.00970	0.00869	0.00676
DET:num	1716	66	254	0.00774	0.00356	0.00447
DET:demo	1566	83	701	0.00706	0.00448	0.01235
DET:indef	1560	196	442	0.00704	0.01058	0.00779
ADV:mente	1062	30	146	0.00479	0.00162	0.00257
PRO:num	1012	22	90	0.00456	0.00119	0.00159
VER:infi:cli	1012	113	151	0.00456	0.00610	0.00266
DET:poss	736	124	352	0.00332	0.00669	0.00620
VER:geru	458	75	112	0.00207	0.00405	0.00197
DET:wh	204	11	29	0.00092	0.00059	0.00051
VER:fin:cli	196	5	12	0.00088	0.00027	0.00021
AUX:ppast	172	1	20	0.00078	0.00005	0.00035
VER2:ppast	124	2	4	0.00056	0.00011	0.00007
AUX:infi	116	0	23	0.00052	0.00000	0.00041
PRO:poss	110	10	43	0.00050	0.00054	0.00076
VER2:infi	76	3	14	0.00034	0.00016	0.00025
VER2:infi:cli	64	0	5	0.00029	0.00000	0.00009
VER:ppre	42	3	11	0.00019	0.00016	0.00019
VER:geru:cli	36	4	4	0.00016	0.00022	0.00007
AUX:infi:cli	18	0	1	0.00008	0.00000	0.00002

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VER2:geru	6	0	0	0.00003	0.00000	0.00000
VER2:fin:cli	6	0	0	0.00003	0.00000	0.00000
AUX:geru	4	0	0	0.00002	0.00000	0.00000
VER2:ppre	0	0	1	0.00000	0.00000	0.00002
NUM	0	0	7	0.00000	0.00000	0.00012

Table 6.2: Uni-grams

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
ART NOUN	8644	1184	3882	0.03898	0.06392	0.06838
CLI VER:fin	5646	484	896	0.02546	0.02613	0.01578
SENT ADV	5392	104	711	0.02432	0.00561	0.01252
NOUN SENT	5116	257	1521	0.02307	0.01387	0.02679
AUX:fin VER:ppast	4424	431	1232	0.01995	0.02327	0.02170
PRE NOUN	4106	329	874	0.01852	0.01776	0.01539
VER:fin ADV	3966	223	1004	0.01789	0.01204	0.01768
ADV SENT	3892	107	581	0.01755	0.00578	0.01023
NOUN PRE	3828	371	1036	0.01726	0.02003	0.01825
ADV ADV	3704	142	508	0.01670	0.00767	0.00895
VER:fin ART	3664	426	1297	0.01652	0.02300	0.02284
ARTPRE NOUN	3166	325	1211	0.01428	0.01755	0.02133
SENT VER:fin	2846	88	367	0.01283	0.00475	0.00646
NOUN ADJ	2752	269	633	0.01241	0.01452	0.01115
NOUN ADV	2682	142	472	0.01209	0.00767	0.00831
NOUN VER:fin	2510	339	1077	0.01132	0.01830	0.01897
VER:fin SENT	2478	66	344	0.01117	0.00356	0.00606
ADV VER:fin	2474	108	488	0.01116	0.00583	0.00860
ADJ PUN	2216	8	6	0.00999	0.00043	0.00011
VER:fin PRE	2138	336	702	0.00964	0.01814	0.01236

Table 6.3: 20 most frequent bi-grams in ITA and their frequencies in SPA and GER

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
SENT ADJ	494	99	198	0.00223	0.00534	0.00349
SENT ADV	5392	104	711	0.02432	0.00561	0.01252

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SENT ADV:mente	88		6	0.00040	0.00000	0.00011
SENT ART	762	38	157	0.00344	0.00205	0.00277
SENT ARTPRE	352	12	55	0.00159	0.00065	0.00097
SENT AUX:fn	264	9	42	0.00119	0.00049	0.00074
SENT CHE	276	11	42	0.00124	0.00059	0.00074
SENT CLI	578	15	55	0.00261	0.00081	0.00097
SENT CON	1600	161	1024	0.00722	0.00869	0.01804
SENT DET:demo	58		19	0.00026	0.00000	0.00033
SENT DET:indef	56	2	9	0.00025	0.00011	0.00016
SENT DET:num	96	1	4	0.00043	0.00005	0.00007
SENT DET:poss	4		1	0.00002	0.00000	0.00002
SENT DET:wh	64	4	10	0.00029	0.00022	0.00018
SENT NEG	408	5	57	0.00184	0.00027	0.00100
SENT NOCAT	1500	58	271	0.00676	0.00313	0.00477
SENT NOUN	1303	21	155	0.00588	0.00113	0.00273
SENT NPR	230	3	9	0.00104	0.00016	0.00016
SENT PRE	898	36	128	0.00405	0.00194	0.00225
SENT PRO:demo	294	2	11	0.00133	0.00011	0.00019
SENT PRO:indef	68	2	14	0.00031	0.00011	0.00025
SENT PRO:num	166	2	4	0.00075	0.00011	0.00007
SENT PRO:pers	598	12	78	0.00270	0.00065	0.00137
SENT PUN	2	1		0.00001	0.00005	0.00000
SENT SENT	392	2	25	0.00177	0.00011	0.00044
SENT VER:fn	2846	88	367	0.01283	0.00475	0.00646
SENT VER:fn:cli	38			0.00017	0.00000	0.00000
SENT VER:geru	14		7	0.00006	0.00000	0.00012
SENT VER:geru:cli	0		1	0.00000	0.00000	0.00002
SENT VER:infi	86		11	0.00039	0.00000	0.00019
SENT VER:infi:cli	22		1	0.00010	0.00000	0.00002
SENT VER:ppast	70	2	19	0.00032	0.00011	0.00033
SENT VER2:fn	208	2	12	0.00094	0.00011	0.00021
SENT VER2:infi	2			0.00001	0.00000	0.00000

Table 6.4: Sentence-beginning PoS

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
VER:fn ART NOUN	2578	305	923	0.0116260	0.0164669	0.0162577
NOUN PRE NOUN	1620	113	323	0.0073057	0.0061009	0.0056893

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ART NOUN PRE	1464	191	453	0.0066022	0.0103121	0.0079791
NOUN SENT ADV	1416	23	246	0.0063857	0.0012418	0.0043330
SENT ADV ADV	1248	21	132	0.0056281	0.0011338	0.0023250
ART NOUN SENT	1236	85	515	0.0055740	0.0045891	0.0090712
ADJ PUN VER:fin	1202	2	1	0.0054206	0.0001080	0.0000176
SENT ADV SENT	1130	10	128	0.0050959	0.0005399	0.0022546
ADV SENT ADV	1076	23	142	0.0048524	0.0012418	0.0025012
NOUN ARTPRE NOUN	1058	79	350	0.0047712	0.0042652	0.0061649
ADV ART NOUN	1016	50	360	0.0045818	0.0026995	0.0063410
PRE ART NOUN	1010	250	545	0.0045548	0.0134975	0.0095996
ART NOUN ADJ	986	87	279	0.0044465	0.0046971	0.0049143
PUN AUX:fin VER:ppast	962		10	0.0043383	0.0000000	0.0001761
CLI VER:fin ADV	908	48	132	0.0040948	0.0025915	0.0023250
ART NOUN VER:fin	806	147	495	0.0036348	0.0079365	0.0087189
PRE NOUN SENT	806	40	181	0.0036348	0.0021596	0.0031881
CLI AUX:fin VER:ppast	798	65	141	0.0035987	0.0035093	0.0024836
NEG CLI VER:fin	780	29	96	0.0035176	0.0015657	0.0016909
ART NOUN ADV	766	44	203	0.0034544	0.0023756	0.0035756

Table 6.5: 20 most frequent tri-grams in ITA and their frequencies in SPA and GER

6.4 The method

We outline here a method (Vogel 2007, Frontini, Lynch & Vogel 2008, Mencke 2006) for comparing n groups of items, each group having some *a priori* label, and for seeing whether each item turns out to be significantly more similar to the items belonging to its *a priori* group than to the others.

In this case we want to measure the homogeneity of items (here files) belonging to a-priori labels *ITA*, *SPA*, *GER*, and maybe find *a posteriori* clusters of similar items (similarities between files belonging to different groups).

The method can operate over every kind of n -gram vector distance (letter n -grams, token n -grams, lemma n -grams; here it will operate over PoS n -grams, henceforth n -grams). It consists of 3 steps:

1. Pairwise-file similarity indexing (χ^2 statistic)
2. Rank-ordering of questioned files with respect to categories (Mann-Whitney)

3. Assessment of *a priori* and *a posteriori* category homogeneity (Bernoulli Schema)

Let's explain the steps in some detail:

1. Each file is compared with every other file in its group and from the other groups. The distance between each pair of files is calculated by comparing the frequencies of PoS n -grams (when an n -gram is not present in a file its frequency is set to 0). The n -gram frequency list for each file being a vector with each attested n -gram as an index and the corresponding frequency as its value, the distance between two files can be calculated using χ^2 statistics, which is a measure of distance between vectors. The output of this operation is a symmetric distance matrix, where the distance between each pair of files can be read.
2. Now we want to know, for each *a priori* group (ITA, SPA, GER), and each file within that group, if the file is really *a posteriori* more similar to the files of its own group than to the other ones. What we do is for each file, X , to order all other files by their distance to X . On top of the list are the files that score the highest similarity (as defined in the previous point). Now, let's imagine this as the order of arrival of runners at a finishing point of a marathon; the participants of this marathon are our files, and their nationality is their *a priori* label. We want to know if this order is random or skewed, that is to say if the runners of the marathon labeled ITA are overall better than GER, or SPA. To do this it's not enough to look at who came first. Even if the winner is ITA, it may be that overall SPA runners performed better. The Mann-Whitney rank ordering test is normally used to solve this kind of problem, and it can calculate for each file the best performing label; it also outputs a significance level, since in some cases the decision may be very difficult and in others very clear instead. This means that, given a file, we can now know if there is an *a priori* group which is significantly similar. Given the presupposition that PoS n -grams can be used to measure syntactic distance this method can tell us, for example, that a file labeled GER shows a significantly more similar syntactic behavior to SPA files than to other GER files.

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3. We now have, for each file, its *a priori* label and its *a posteriori* “new home”. This means that we can now count for each *a priori* label how many files present this label *a posteriori* too, and how many found instead a different home according to the distance measure. This can be used to assess the homogeneity of each *a priori* group; a group is significantly homogeneous if the significant majority of its files find again its group *a posteriori*.
4. In order to avoid problems arising from the difference in the number of members of each *a priori* group, we use an additional level of significance testing for assessing group homogeneity. Instead of taking all files in each category into account, we can imagine of putting our files into three baskets, each one labeled with the *a priori* label. The files in the baskets themselves are little balls, with the *a posteriori* label written on them. Then we run say 1000 extractions: at each run we take 8 balls from each basket, we record their labels and take care to place them back into the same basket we extracted them from; after 1000 runs we can see if there is some significant correlation between the label on the basket and the label on the balls: Bernoulli schema let us decide whether sufficiently many files are attributed to a category to deem the category homogeneous. As sometimes the best fit category for one or more files of an *a priori* group is instead some other category, it is useful to also consider those alternative assignments.

6.5 Results

The distances between the files have been measured by analyzing the differences between the distributions of uni, bi- and tri-grams of PoS in the files.

To see the complete table of results for each file for this and the following sections see Appendix A

Group	Correct Hits	Total Files
ita	64	66
spa	4	16
ger	55	63

Table 6.6: Group Homogeneity: Tag Unigrams

Actual Group	Alternative	Significant Hits
ita	n/a	2/2
spa	ger	11/14
spa	ita	1/14
ger	ita	5/8

Table 6.7: Best Alternative Assignments: Tag Unigrams

Group	Correct Hits	Total Files
ita	66	66
spa	10	18
ger	53	63

Table 6.8: Group Homogeneity: Tag Bigrams

Actual Group	Alternative	Significant Hits
ita	n/a	n/a
spa	ger	6/8
ger	ita	5/10

Table 6.9: Best Alternative Assignments: Tag Bigrams

Group	Correct Hits	Total Files
ita	65	66
spa	13	18
ger	41	63

Table 6.10: Group Homogeneity: Tag Trigrams

6.5.1 Repeated Experiments

Adopting a bigram analysis, and using samples of 8 files from each of 3 categories in 1000 experiments, the average homogeneity of the categories was ITA, 7.787; SPA,

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Actual Group	Alternative	Significant Hits
ita	n/a	n/a
spa	ger	4/5
spa	n/a	1/5
ger	n/a	17/22
ger	ita	5/22

Table 6.11: Best Alternative Assignments: Tag Trigrams

5.801; GER, 5.965. Significance for homogeneity with this number of categories and files within categories is 6 out of 8 ($p < 0.05$).

The best alternatives turn out as in table 6.12. For each group, a total of 8000 tests are involved (8 files per group, and 1000 experiments).

Actual Group	Alternative	Significant Hits
ita	spa	46
ita	ger	98
spa	ita	223
spa	ger	625
ger	ita	706
ger	spa	137

Table 6.12: Best Alternatives: Tag Bigrams 8 Files/Group, 1000 Experiments

Thus, ITA is a homogeneous group, and the other two tend towards homogeneity, but aren't significantly so. The *a priori* group SPA most often finds GER as its best alternative to SPA when SPA is not the best fit, while the group GER most often finds ITA as the best alternative.

6.6 Scaling, visualisation of clusters

Another way of treating the problem of homogeneity is to visually represent the distances that are the output of the first step of this method in a bidimensional space and

Figure 6.1: Unigrams - Multidimensional scaling - plot

Figure 6.2: Bigrams - Multidimensional scaling - plot

Figure 6.3: Trigrams - Multidimensional scaling - plot

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representing the different labels with colors so that we can see how they plot in the space.

In order to give a visual representation of the homogeneity results, we apply *multidimensional scaling*, a technique that given a distance matrix between a number of elements can output the relative position of each element in an n -dimensional space (for a simple explanation of this technique with two examples see Appendix G). Figures 6.1 6.2 and 6.3 are the result of the multidimensional scaling of the distance matrix. In this case we chose to scale to a 2 dimensional space, using the *mdscale* function available in the statistical software R. The output coordinates have then been plotted; each dot corresponds to a file, and colors and forms have been used to differentiate between the three *a priori* groups, ITA, TED, SPA.

The output of MDS does not contradict the quantitative homogeneity assessment, and it gives a good visual representation of it.

6.7 Discussion

In the first place the differences between uni-, bi, and tri-grams should be taken into account. Considering both group homogeneity and best alternatives, the picture does not seem to change significantly, whether we consider sequences of one, two or three PoS. If confirmed on larger samples, this could have useful methodological consequences: tag bi-grams might be informative enough to represent the distributional features of a sample without any need of checking broader context for the purpose of quantitative analysis over large samples.

From the analysis of the results some conclusions can be drawn. In the first place ITA seems to be a much more homogeneous sample than the others. And this is the case even in the tests where the sample size is not normalized and when a wider variety could then be expected from ITA, which is the larger group in terms of files (and informants). According to tests in 6.12 only ITA shows a level of homogeneity that is significant; this means that only the files from the target language sample seem to significantly cluster with each other, to build an *a posteriori* group.

SPA and GER tend towards homogeneity, but are not homogeneous enough to build *a posteriori* clusters of files. This means that files in SPA are not more similar to each other than they are to GER or ITA, and the same is true for GER. This seems to

exclude the possibility that transfer from L1 is strong enough to make our 2 samples cluster together. At the same time though, IL samples show a great internal variability, and do not seem to cluster together as a whole. Although SPA items seem to be more similar to GER (thus showing a higher similarity with the other IL group) the files from GER tend to be nearer to the ITA cluster.

The result of the multidimensional scaling and plotting of the distance matrixes seem to reflect this analysis quite well, and allows us to give a visual representation of the relative distribution of the files in an imaginary bi-dimensional space. ITA shows a higher degree of homogeneity in all three plots (the ITA dots tend to cluster together). SPA dots are the least homogeneous: although smaller in number, they tend to occupy a portion of space that is almost as large as the ITA one. The GER dots behavior is somewhat in the middle, but with a tendency to non homogeneity.

The IL files (SPA+TED) tend to occupy the same portion of space, and be separated from the ITA. On the whole, it is more likely that TED files occur near to the ITA cluster, rather than SPA files, thus accounting for the results of the repeated experiment; the *a priori* group SPA most often finds GER as its best alternative to SPA when SPA is not the best, while the group GER most often finds ITA as the best alternative.

Thus we can order the three groups in a sequence, starting from ITA, then to GER and ending with SPA. Further analysis is necessary to draw a conclusion, although the possibility should be verified that GER informants are at a higher stage of acquisition than the SPA ones¹. If this is true, then it means that, in our samples, the level of competence of the learners produces a PoS distribution which is more similar to that of the TL. Also, the level of competence correlates better with the PoS distribution similarity than possible transfer effects from NL, since SPA files have the least similarity with the ITA cluster.

¹Professor Marina Chini, personal communication

Final considerations on the definition and use of lexical categories

This work has dealt with the definition of lexical categories in Interlanguage. Yet, as sometimes happens in second language acquisition research, the problem of defining lexical categories in interlanguage has a more than obvious relationship with the problem of defining lexical categories in natural language in general. Cross-linguistically, as well as in the learner varieties, we encounter with questions such as: “does this language/variety have category x?”, “is category y distinguishable from category z in this language/variety?” and more radically “does it make sense to speak of lexical categories in this language/variety?”

The solution that we have given implies a great deal of effort in clarifying what we mean when talking about lexical categories and what use we want to make of this concept. This problem has obviously two aspects, one aspect which is rather theoretical and the other which is more methodological, but they are both actually quite interconnected from a corpus linguistics perspective: every annotated element in the corpus has the function of bringing to the surface phenomena that are hidden in the deep structure of language; at the same time annotation is a tool to analyze other phenomena of a different level. When we annotate a token with a certain PoS tag, we are highlighting an implicit convergency of morphological, lexical, distributional, semantic and pragmatic features, and at the same time we are making it possible to discover other regularities at the level of syntax.

Theoretical linguists are mainly focused on finding a universal definition for lexical categories, one that can be used both intra- and cross-linguistically, and are there-

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fore less concerned with the practical and methodological issues that derive from their definition.

On the other hand, very few works on PoS tagging go into depth on the problem of defining lexical categories from the theoretical point of view regardless of whether they are NL-oriented or IL-oriented. Most of the time the evaluation of the algorithm is reduced to the a-problematic comparison of the accuracy of the tagger against a human annotated test corpus, meaning that the accuracy of the test corpus is considered to be the 100%. Yet human PoS tagging is not a trivial problem (hence the verbosity of PoS tagging guidelines for human annotation); human annotators can disagree because they use different criteria or because they use the same criteria in a less consistent way, and therefore automatic PoS tagging is a good thing not just because it is cheap and quick, but because it allows a better control of the criteria that we want to rely on in PoS annotation, as well as a better consistency in application.

As with human annotators automatic PoS taggers stumble on ambiguous contexts; some of the mistakes that result seem trivial to humans. But they are useful because they remind us that ambiguity is there and that perhaps it's just that our eyes or ears are ill fitted to recognize it, since it is part of our language competence not to see it, but to choose between one interpretation or the other within in fractions of a second. If the goal of PoS taggers is not that of performing like the human taggers, but that of outperforming them, we may even say that the problem of PoS tagging is not yet completely solved, and still worth some further investigation.

The broader consequences of this last observation could not be taken into account in this research since by following them we would have had no time left to say something about the behavior of categories in IL. What is worth underlining here is that shifting the perspective from a fully fledged language to interlanguage varieties is a way of studying the problem of categories in its extremest condition; the more ambiguity is amplified, the more the problem of clarity and consistency becomes crucial. But ambiguity is always present and what we have claimed as necessary for IL category annotation - that is separation of levels (formal/functional first) and a clear distinction between cues (morphological, lexical, distributional) - may be just as well applied to the target language, where most of (yet, significantly, not all of) the time form and function converge, and one cue makes the others redundant.

From a more practical and methodological point of view the problem of keeping a clear control on the criteria is equally important; not in the sense of finding which criteria are decisive in a general definition of lexical categories, but in that of finding which criteria one needs to take into account when investigating a certain problem. This becomes evident every time a choice of annotation of the corpus makes a specific research aim difficult: how can one retrieve all verb to noun conversions (for instance by querying for a DET + VERB context) if all Italian infinitives or English gerunds in the corpus have been classified as nouns already? And again how can one investigate the continuum between on-line generated conversions and lexicalizations (i.e. the same form referring to two different lemmas) when this distinction has already been encoded in the annotation (“il:DET mangiare:NOUN” vs “il:DET bere:VERB”)?

In the praxis of corpus linguistics the solution to these theoretical issues is given by two practical issues: the issue of standardization, i.e., of one corpora’s being comparable with other existing corpora, and the issue of usability, i.e., to be functional to the uses of the corpus that the researcher is aiming at. What we have tried here is to imagine how a working definition of lexical categories in interlanguage (chapter 2, 3), based on the evidence of a primacy of the distributional cue (chapter 4) may be transformed in a standard for PoS annotation in IL corpora (chapter 5), and how it could be productively used in research (chapter 6).

What may be interesting for future investigation would be to explore the possibility of a more complex standard of annotation, that keeps a separate record of every formal cue, so that the researcher can eventually choose at which level the disambiguation should take place. From the practical point of view this could take the form of a stochastic tagger where the weights of each feature (distribution, morphology, lexicon) can be separately measured, annotated and retrieved, thus making it possible to generate online the tag best satisfying the requirements for the research one wants to undertake. Such a standard, though designed for interlanguage, could be easily applied to the target language as well, and may prove itself useful even outside the scope of acquisitional research.

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Appendix A

Corpus treatment

A.1 Chat annotation

*ITO: &mh &mh # okay # puoi continuare.
*DAV: <prima di> [/] -, <prima di andare> [/] # prima di andare a letto
-, &eh il signore verdi -, &eh fa! &mh # una # passeggiata?
*ITO: &mh &mh.
*DAV: poi <il signore verde> [//] &eh il signore -, &eh rossi -, &eh # va a letto.
*ITO: &mh &mh -, okay.
*DAV: <quando loro &mh -, addormenta> [//]: quando loro addormentAno -,
*ITO: &mh &mh.
*DAV: &mh # <il> [//] <la casa la ca> [/] la casa loro &eh # aprire il fuoco?
*ITO: okay -, &mh &mh.

A.2 Cleaning procedure

prima di andare a letto il signore verdi fa una passeggiata
poi il signore rossi va a letto
quando loro addormentano
la casa loro aprire il fuoco

A.3 Cleaning algorithm - pseudocode

The cleaning algorithm defines a function called “clean” that removes the annotation symbols (including, most importantly false starts). Then the checks each line, and removes the lines of the interviewer as well as those containing biographic infos, while

A. CORPUS TREATMENT

submitting the lines of the informant to the “clean” function. The output is the cleaned text.

```
define function:: clean {  
  
$line =~ s/\&\w+:?//g; => removes interjections (&mh)  
  
$line =~ s/<.+?>//g; => removes <self repair>  
  
$line =~ s/\[.+?\]//g; => removes [pauses] and [transcriber's comments]  
  
$line =~ s/,+//g; => removes ,  
  
$line =~ s/#+//g; => removes #  
  
$line =~ s/:+//g; => removes :  
  
$line =~ s/-+//g; => removes -  
  
$line =~ s/\(+//g; => removes (  
  
$line =~ s/\)+//g; => removes )  
  
$line =~ s/\/+//g; => removes -  
  
$line =~ s/' ?/ /g; => removes '  
  
$line =~ s/x+?/ /g; => removes xxx  
  
$line =~ s/^ //; => removes spaces at line beginning  
  
$line =~ tr/A-Z/a-z; => capital to small letters  
  
$line =~ s/ +/ /g; => removes spaces  
  
}
```

A.3 Cleaning algorithm - pseudocode

```
if (($input =~ m/ITA: /)||($input =~ m/IT0/)){

remove(); => removes interviewer's lines
}

else if ($line =~ m/@/){

remove(); => removes biographic infos

}

else{ => what remains are the informant's lines

    clean(); => applies cleaning function

out(); => writes to output

}
```


Appendix B

Results of clustering analysis of source categories

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
1	617	il	1	536	il
2	556	signor	2	371	la
3	416	e	3	324	è
4	356	si	4	249	fuoco
5	215	blu	5	245	blu
6	193	a	6	216	signore
7	192	è	7	204	signora
8	186	rossi	8	186	e
9	184	i	9	175	ma
10	175	di	10	173	a
11	173	pompieri	11	157	non
12	173	verdi	12	145	verde
13	163	che	13	144	ha
14	162	la	14	143	poi
15	140	anche	15	139	di
16	138	del	16	133	signor
17	99	in	17	126	anche
18	89	l	18	125	casa
19	86	non	19	103	lui
20	84	telefono	20	88	rossi
21	82	alla	21	81	no
22	81	incendio	22	75	sua

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
23	79	casa	23	73	loro
24	77	finestra	24	73	si
25	67	ha	25	69	rosso
26	67	le	26	66	va
27	65	un	27	65	camera
28	62	va	28	61	i
29	60	sta	29	58	lei
30	58	fuoco	30	58	sono
31	58	per	31	57	telefono
32	56	dal	32	55	le
33	54	dalla	33	54	lo
34	54	dei	34	54	rossa
35	53	al	35	52	quando
36	51	lui	36	51	del
37	51	sul	37	51	l
38	50	appartamento	38	50	da
39	48	pompieri	39	50	uomo
40	47	sono	40	49	letto
41	46	fiamme	41	49	vigile
42	44	ma	42	48	c
43	44	porta	43	47	per
44	43	sua	44	47	questo
45	39	buttarsi	45	45	!
46	39	luce	46	44	bagno
47	38	dormire	47	41	+
48	38	tetto	48	40	più
49	37	letto	49	39	persona
50	36	vede	50	39	verdi
51	35	allora	51	37	finestra
52	35	bagno	52	37	pompieri
53	34	suo	53	36	che
54	33	nel	54	36	in
55	31	una	55	36	persone
56	30	con	56	35	adesso
57	30	decide	57	35	molto
58	30	vigili	58	35	un
59	29	spegne	59	32	sveglia
60	28	quindi	60	32	tre
61	28	verso	61	31	dice
62	26	finalmente	62	31	pompieri

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
63	26	mentre	63	30	salta
64	25	nella	64	30	so
65	25	poi	65	28	con
66	25	saltare	66	28	signole
67	24	tre	67	28	sì
68	23	lo	68	28	telefona
69	23	tutti	69	26	fa
70	22	andato	70	26	infine
71	22	butta	71	26	paura
72	22	svegliato	72	25	dalla
73	22	viene	73	25	grande
74	21	camera	74	24	saltare
75	21	continua	75	24	vigili
76	21	esce	76	23	chiama
77	21	questa	77	23	perché
78	21	sotto	78	23	sa
79	20	gli	79	23	tutti
80	20	numero	80	23	una
81	20	più	81	22	ancora
82	20	scale	82	22	come
83	20	telo	83	22	telefonato
84	19	dell	84	21	acqua
85	19	dopo	85	20	dorme
86	19	nuovo	86	19	al
87	19	sveglia	87	19	cosa
88	18	bussare	88	19	dormire
89	18	pero	89	19	dormito
90	18	preoccupato	90	19	hanno
91	18	questo	91	19	quindi
92	18	signori	92	19	stanza
93	18	verde	93	18	alla
94	17	invece	94	18	chiuso
95	17	perché	95	18	nel
96	17	però	96	18	polizia
97	17	salvato	97	18	sul
98	17	sembra	98	17	contenti
99	17	spegnere	99	17	luce
100	17	vuole	100	17	sta
101	16	chiamare	101	17	telefonare
102	16	dormendo	102	16	così

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
103	16	guarda	103	16	dal
104	16	punto	104	16	fuori
105	16	vediamo	105	16	macchina
106	15	ai	106	16	porta
107	15	alza	107	16	uno
108	15	andando	108	15	alza
109	15	cornetta	109	15	dopo
110	15	giù	110	15	verbi
111	15	volta	111	15	vuole
112	14	andare	112	14	deve
113	14	cosa	113	14	losso
114	14	dorme	114	14	può
115	14	ormai	115	14	questa
116	14	telone	116	13	della
117	13	accorto	117	13	due
118	13	ancora	118	13	esce
119	13	aver	119	13	forte
120	13	c	120	13	lampada
121	13	da	121	13	sente
122	13	probabilmente	122	13	sentito
123	13	rifiuta	123	12	nella
124	13	scena	124	12	subito
125	13	stanno	125	11	andato
126	13	stava	126	11	coperta
127	12	caserma	127	11	finito
128	12	cercano	128	11	mentre
129	12	della	129	11	nuovo
130	12	due	130	11	poliziotto
131	12	fa	131	11	svegliato
132	12	fine	132	11	volta
133	12	mette	133	10	bussare
134	12	quello	134	10	scende
135	12	sempre	135	10	sulla
136	12	sentono	136	10	tua
137	12	spento	137	10	uscito
138	12	torna	138	9	ambulanza
139	11	arrivano	139	9	fare
140	11	davanti	140	9	fatto
141	11	fare	141	9	prende
142	11	fuori	142	9	saltato

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
143	11	loro	143	9	suo
144	11	molto	144	9	suona
145	11	rispondere	145	9	tutte
146	11	rumori	146	9	verdo
147	11	scende	147	8	ah
148	11	sia	148	8	aiutano
149	10	accorge	149	8	aiutare
150	10	ad	150	8	eh
151	10	adesso	151	8	parlano
152	10	bussa	152	8	paula
153	10	cui	153	8	pensato
154	10	dall	154	8	torna
155	10	hanno	155	8	uscire
156	10	niente	156	8	vegili
157	10	pensa	157	7	accordo
158	10	quando	158	7	aiuto
159	10	salvo	159	7	andata
160	10	subito	160	7	d
161	10	vanno	161	7	dorma
162	9	arrivate	162	7	felice
163	9	compone	163	7	folco
164	9	frattempo	164	7	forse
165	9	intanto	165	7	giù
166	9	momento	166	7	grazie
167	9	ora	167	7	guarda
168	9	personaggi	168	7	pensa
169	9	prima	169	7	perciò
170	9	riescono	170	7	qualcosa
171	9	risponde	171	7	rumore
172	9	sente	172	7	scale
173	9	stanza	173	7	signori
174	9	stesso	174	7	solo
175	8	alzato	175	7	telefonata
176	8	arrivati	176	7	uscita
177	8	buttare	177	7	via
178	8	col	178	7	visto
179	8	così	179	6	amico
180	8	dai	180	6	arrivato
181	8	forse	181	6	bussato
182	8	inquadratura	182	6	ci

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
183	8	neanche	183	6	dicono
184	8	no	184	6	dove
185	8	paura	185	6	drin
186	8	rumore	186	6	gente
187	8	sdraia	187	6	nervoso
188	8	se	188	6	pausa
189	8	sentito	189	6	perchè
190	8	stato	190	6	piano
191	8	unico	191	6	polizio
192	7	all	192	6	russo
193	7	chiama	193	6	scendere
194	7	chiude	194	6	spegnere
195	7	ci	195	6	spento
196	7	contenti	196	6	stato
197	7	convincere	197	6	su
198	7	corica	198	6	uomini
199	7	delle	199	5	alto
200	7	elastico	200	5	alzato
201	7	fatto	201	5	andare
202	7	infine	202	5	arrivata
203	7	nell	203	5	bru
204	7	nonostante	204	5	chiamare
205	7	omino	205	5	chiudere
206	7	po	206	5	finalmente
207	7	primo	207	5	fuochi
208	7	risposto	208	5	ho
209	7	siccome	209	5	io
210	7	siede	210	5	nela
211	7	sopra	211	5	niente
212	7	squilla	212	5	oh
213	7	stessa	213	5	passa
214	7	succedendo	214	5	posta
215	7	svegliare	215	5	queste
216	7	tappeto	216	5	scala
217	7	telefonare	217	5	sera
218	7	telefonata	218	5	spengono
219	7	tranquillamente	219	5	stanno
220	7	visto	220	5	suoi
221	6	chiamata	221	5	vede
222	6	coperta	222	5	vegile

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
223	6	coricato	223	5	velde
224	6	dalle	224	5	vengono
225	6	diciamo	225	5	voglio
226	6	ed	226	4	ascoltato
227	6	era	227	4	chiamale
228	6	essere	228	4	chiamano
229	6	infatti	229	4	chiamata
230	6	invitano	230	4	chiamato
231	6	lanciarsi	231	4	chiude
232	6	li	232	4	contento
233	6	notte	233	4	dei
234	6	posizionano	234	4	detto
235	6	proprio	235	4	dormendo
236	6	quale	236	4	dormi
237	6	quel	237	4	dormiva
238	6	qui	238	4	felici
239	6	raggiunto	239	4	improvviso
240	6	ringraziano	240	4	lavora
241	6	salgono	241	4	lossa
242	6	salta	242	4	momento
243	6	sera	243	4	musica
244	6	su	244	4	notte
245	6	successo	245	4	parlare
246	6	sulla	246	4	penso
247	6	testa	247	4	possono
248	6	vedono	248	4	prima
249	5	aiuto	249	4	primo
250	5	altri	250	4	provato
251	5	appunto	251	4	quale
252	5	apre	252	4	quel
253	5	avvicina	253	4	quello
254	5	bisognava	254	4	questi
255	5	buttato	255	4	sceso
256	5	cade	256	4	sicuro
257	5	chiamato	257	4	sotto
258	5	conto	258	4	spende
259	5	divampando	259	4	suonato
260	5	dormono	260	4	troppo
261	5	entra	261	4	trovato
262	5	erano	262	4	uende

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
263	5	fanno	263	4	vegi
264	5	finestre	264	3]
265	5	immagine	265	3	accesso
266	5	nulla	266	3	ai
267	5	palazzo	267	3	all
268	5	pericolo	268	3	altro
269	5	presto	269	3	ascolta
270	5	prova	270	3	ca
271	5	questi	271	3	caduto
272	5	rosso	272	3	camere
273	5	salvarsi	273	3	capito
274	5	salvati	274	3	chiamando
275	5	scoppia	275	3	compagni
276	5	siano	276	3	completamento
277	5	spengono	277	3	continua
278	5	spostano	278	3	dala
279	5	suona	279	3	dentro
280	5	vedendo	280	3	dietro
281	4	abbracciano	281	3	dormino
282	4	addormenta	282	3	dormono
283	4	affacciano	283	3	escono
284	4	allargando	284	3	evviva
285	4	arriva	285	3	fanno
286	4	arrivando	286	3	fuo
287	4	arrivato	287	3	guidano
288	4	camion	288	3	infino
289	4	cammina	289	3	ir
290	4	colpi	290	3	italiano
291	4	convince	291	3	lossi
292	4	copre	292	3	me
293	4	dentro	293	3	mh
294	4	dice	294	3	mi
295	4	dirige	295	3	nei
296	4	dove	296	3	o
297	4	espandendo	297	3	ok
298	4	espressione	298	3	ora
299	4	essersi	299	3	otto
300	4	facendo	300	3	palmente
301	4	far	301	3	però
302	4	giu	302	3	po

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
303	4	già	303	3	polizi
304	4	gru	304	3	possibile
305	4	h	305	3	prendono
306	4	han	306	3	pò
307	4	indietro	307	3	quattro
308	4	inquilini	308	3	riceve
309	4	ne	309	3	ricevere
310	4	nessuno	310	3	ritelefona
311	4	nostri	311	3	rosse
312	4	o	312	3	sai
313	4	omini	313	3	saluta
314	4	parte	314	3	scendo
315	4	pie di	315	3	scople
316	4	prende	316	3	sembra
317	4	qualcosa	317	3	sentì
318	4	recano	318	3	spegnande
319	4	salutano	319	3	spegne
320	4	salvare	320	3	successo
321	4	scendere	321	3	tappeto
322	4	secondo	322	3	telefo
323	4	sedia	323	3	telefonando
324	4	siamo	324	3	tornato
325	4	situazione	325	3	trova
326	4	spaventato	326	3	tuo
327	4	spente	327	3	tutto
328	4	stati	328	3	usa
329	4	succede	329	3	usce
330	4	suonare	330	3	vado
331	4	vedere	331	3	vedere
332	3	accorgersi	332	3	ver
333	3	accorti	333	3	vilige
334	3	acqua	334	3	volte
335	3	affaccia	335	3	voluto
336	3	aiutano	336	3	vuoi
337	3	alle	337	2	able
338	3	allontana	338	2	acende
339	3	altro	339	2	aciulo
340	3	amici	340	2	aiuta
341	3	appartamenti	341	2	aiutato
342	3	appena	342	2	alivati

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
343	3	averli	343	2	alle
344	3	bianche	344	2	altre
345	3	brandina	345	2	alzo
346	3	bruciando	346	2	apri
347	3	bussato	347	2	arrivano
348	3	case	348	2	ascoltare
349	3	cenni	349	2	azulo
350	3	cestello	350	2	banio
351	3	chiedere	351	2	bata
352	3	chiedono	352	2	bene
353	3	colla	353	2	bianco
354	3	convinto	354	2	bombiere
355	3	coricarsi	355	2	bravo
356	3	credo	356	2	cade
357	3	crepitii	357	2	cadere
358	3	direzione	358	2	cambiano
359	3	entrato	359	2	case
360	3	escono	360	2	caza
361	3	evidentemente	361	2	cellulare
362	3	fece	362	2	chia
363	3	fiamma	363	2	chiedere
364	3	finita	364	2	chiedono
365	3	getta	365	2	chiudo
366	3	gira	366	2	cima
367	3	guardano	367	2	cinque
368	3	incitano	368	2	co
369	3	inquadrato	369	2	cole
370	3	insistentemente	370	2	contanti
371	3	insomma	371	2	contente
372	3	lancia	372	2	continuare
373	3	male	373	2	cos
374	3	mani	374	2	dalle
375	3	mano	375	2	de
376	3	mente	376	2	diagi
377	3	mettono	377	2	dire
378	3	musica	378	2	diventato
379	3	n	379	2	dolce
380	3	nuovamente	380	2	donna
381	3	pare	381	2	dormile
382	3	particolarmente	382	2	dunque

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
383	3	partono	383	2	edificio
384	3	penso	384	2	era
385	3	piano	385	2	fai
386	3	poter	386	2	fatta
387	3	prendendo	387	2	ferito
388	3	preso	388	2	figure
389	3	presumibilmente	389	2	formo
390	3	provano	390	2	fumo
391	3	quanti	391	2	funzione
392	3	quest	392	2	giusto
393	3	riesce	393	2	già
394	3	risale	394	2	guardano
395	3	ritorna	395	2	idea
396	3	rosse	396	2	inizio
397	3	s	397	2	insegna
398	3	salvi	398	2	insieme
399	3	scenetta	399	2	lasciano
400	3	sceso	400	2	lasciato
401	3	scoppi	401	2	lu
402	3	scoppiato	402	2	uomo
403	3	sdraiato	403	2	mento
404	3	segno	404	2	metodo
405	3	so	405	2	mette
406	3	solo	406	2	mettere
407	3	squillando	407	2	metto
408	3	stazione	408	2	mezz
409	3	suoi	409	2	mille
410	3	svegli	410	2	ne
411	3	svegliarlo	411	2	occupare
412	3	svilupato	412	2	palazzo
413	3	sì	413	2	pensano
414	3	tempo	414	2	pieno
415	3	terra	415	2	piere
416	3	tira	416	2	plima
417	3	tornano	417	2	polizie
418	3	tutte	418	2	polta
419	3	tutto	419	2	pombieri
420	3	vengono	420	2	posso
421	3	water	421	2	posto
422	2	abita	422	2	preso

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
423	2	abitano	423	2	profondamente
424	2	abitanti	424	2	purtroppo
425	2	abitazioni	425	2	qualcuno
426	2	accende	426	2	riesce
427	2	acceso	427	2	riescono
428	2	affacciato	428	2	risposto
429	2	alta	429	2	rispoto
430	2	alto	430	2	rispunda
431	2	altra	431	2	ritorno
432	2	alzarsi	432	2	sali
433	2	aperto	433	2	saltano
434	2	arrivo	434	2	salvare
435	2	atterra	435	2	salvo
436	2	aumentato	436	2	scelto
437	2	avanzare	437	2	scoperto
438	2	avere	438	2	scopre
439	2	aveva	439	2	scusa
440	2	avvicinato	440	2	scusi
441	2	barella	441	2	secondo
442	2	bene	442	2	senta
443	2	bianco	443	2	sentire
444	2	bisogni	444	2	sento
445	2	brucia	445	2	servare
446	2	bruciato	446	2	signure
447	2	butti	447	2	signuri
448	2	camionetta	448	2	spendere
449	2	carabinieri	449	2	spenie
450	2	carro	450	2	spiega
451	2	cenno	451	2	stazione
452	2	cerca	452	2	succede
453	2	cercar	453	2	sula
454	2	chiamano	454	2	suolo
455	2	chiudere	455	2	svegliano
456	2	coinquilini	456	2	svegliare
457	2	come	457	2	svegliata
458	2	comincia	458	2	talta
459	2	cominciano	459	2	tanti
460	2	compose	460	2	telefonale
461	2	comunque	461	2	teme
462	2	condominio	462	2	tetto

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
463	2	coperte	463	2	ua
464	2	coperto	464	2	usano
465	2	coraggio	465	2	uscile
466	2	corre	466	2	vegele
467	2	corsa	467	2	veloce
468	2	d	468	2	venuto
469	2	dato	469	2	vince
470	2	decise	470	2	vita
471	2	deciso	471	2	vogliono
472	2	degli	472	2	vuoio
473	2	deve	473	2	zero
474	2	dicono	474	2	é
475	2	dirigono	475	1	\$eh
476	2	disperato	476	1	abbraccio
477	2	disponibile	477	1	abita
478	2	distende	478	1	abitato
479	2	divampa	479	1	abli
480	2	domato	480	1	accede
481	2	dunque	481	1	accen
482	2	durante	482	1	accende
483	2	ecco	483	1	accesa
484	2	eh	484	1	accidente
485	2	esterno	485	1	accito
486	2	farsi	486	1	accorgere
487	2	festeggiano	487	1	acorta
488	2	finito	488	1	acquistare
489	2	fino	489	1	acquistato
490	2	fortunatamente	490	1	ad
491	2	fosse	491	1	addormentano
492	2	giallo	492	1	agitate
493	2	gioiscono	493	1	agiulo
494	2	girato	494	1	ahah
495	2	giungere	495	1	ahiuto
496	2	guardia	496	1	aiutarmi
497	2	idea	497	1	aiutata
498	2	improvviso	498	1	ala
499	2	iniziano	499	1	alfino
500	2	insistenza	500	1	alimano
501	2	interno	501	1	alimpoviso
502	2	lavoro	502	1	aliva

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
503	2	luci	503	1	alivadato
504	2	lì	504	1	alivano
505	2	m	505	1	alliva
506	2	macchina	506	1	alta
507	2	maggior	507	1	altra
508	2	materasso	508	1	altri
509	2	mh	509	1	alzono
510	2	modo	510	1	ambulan
511	2	nemmeno	511	1	amici
512	2	nota	512	1	anghe
513	2	nè	513	1	apadamento
514	2	osservano	514	1	apamento
515	2	pancia	515	1	aple
516	2	parlare	516	1	appartamento
517	2	passeggia	517	1	appena
518	2	pensato	518	1	aprire
519	2	perche	519	1	arivece
520	2	piu	520	1	arriva
521	2	piuttosto	521	1	arrivatono
522	2	poiché	522	1	arriviamo
523	2	pompa	523	1	arza
524	2	portano	524	1	aspetano
525	2	portati	525	1	aspetta
526	2	porte	526	1	astare
527	2	posa	527	1	azuli
528	2	positivo	528	1	azzulo
529	2	prendono	529	1	azzuri
530	2	prepara	530	1	azzurro
531	2	preparano	531	1	bieco
532	2	propagato	532	1	bluto
533	2	provenire	533	1	borta
534	2	puzza	534	1	brava
535	2	qualche	535	1	buen
536	2	quanto	536	1	buona
537	2	quasi	537	1	buttare
538	2	quattro	538	1	cacca
539	2	quella	539	1	cam
540	2	rende	540	1	cambia
541	2	reso	541	1	cambiale
542	2	riappende	542	1	cambiare

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
543	2	riattacca	543	1	camele
544	2	richiamare	544	1	camio
545	2	rifiutarsi	545	1	camion
546	2	righe	546	1	capisce
547	2	rimaneva	547	1	capita
548	2	ringrazia	548	1	cas
549	2	sale	549	1	ce
550	2	saltar	550	1	cerca
551	2	seduto	551	1	cercare
552	2	sembrano	552	1	cercato
553	2	sembrava	553	1	chembia
554	2	sentiamo	554	1	chi
555	2	sentire	555	1	chiamacendo
556	2	senza	556	1	chiamanda
557	2	servizi	557	1	chiamate
558	2	sicuro	558	1	chiano
559	2	signora	559	1	chiede
560	2	smesso	560	1	chiedo
561	2	smette	561	1	chiema
562	2	solleva	562	1	chiesto
563	2	sollevati	563	1	chiudi
564	2	spaventata	564	1	chiusa
565	2	spiegato	565	1	colda
566	2	spuntano	566	1	com
567	2	squillare	567	1	combiera
568	2	stavolta	568	1	comincia
569	2	stia	569	1	cominciare
570	2	strada	570	1	cominciato
571	2	sui	571	1	comodino
572	2	svegliarsi	572	1	compagno
573	2	sveglia	573	1	comunque
574	2	sviluppando	574	1	condinua
575	2	telefonato	575	1	conentissimo
576	2	tengono	576	1	conosco
577	2	tentano	577	1	consigliano
578	2	toilette	578	1	continualmente
579	2	tornato	579	1	corto
580	2	triste	580	1	cu
581	2	troppo	581	1	cul
582	2	turno	582	1	

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
583	2	tutta	583	1	cuoce
584	2	ultimo	584	1	dai
585	2	uomini	585	1	dar
586	2	uscire	586	1	davanti
587	2	uscito	587	1	deciso
588	2	velocemente	588	1	dela
589	2	vi	589	1	deniforo
590	2	vita	590	1	der
591	2	volversi	591	1	devo
592	2	voleva	592	1	difendo
593	2	vuol	593	1	difensare
594	1	+	594	1	digitato
595	1	abbastanza	595	1	dispiace
596	1	abitavano	596	1	dole
597	1	abitazione	597	1	dolino
598	1	accadendo	598	1	dolmile
599	1	accaduto	599	1	dolmito
600	1	accertarsi	600	1	domo
601	1	accinge	601	1	dompieri
602	1	accompagnato	602	1	dormenta
603	1	accordo	603	1	dormente
604	1	accorse	604	1	dormiano
605	1	accotto	605	1	dormimento
606	1	affacciandosi	606	1	dorna
607	1	affacciati	607	1	drosso
608	1	affacciò	608	1	ed
609	1	affinché	609	1	el
610	1	agire	610	1	esco
611	1	agitano	611	1	espetano
612	1	agitarsi	612	1	faccia
613	1	aiutarlo	613	1	facendo
614	1	aiutato	614	1	fale
615	1	alcune	615	1	fano
616	1	allarga	616	1	fazzoletto
617	1	allargano	617	1	ferma
618	1	allegra	618	1	fermo
619	1	almeno	619	1	festa
620	1	alzano	620	1	fetto
621	1	alzò	621	1	film
622	1	anch	622	1	finestre

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
623	1	andata	623	1	finisci
624	1	andate	624	1	fisso
625	1	angolo	625	1	folchi
626	1	ansia	626	1	folno
627	1	aprendo	627	1	fortuna
628	1	aria	628	1	fossi
629	1	arrivare	629	1	fotografia
630	1	arrivata	630	1	freddo
631	1	assolutamente	631	1	fucuro
632	1	attenzione	632	1	funghi
633	1	atterrito	633	1	funziona
634	1	attimo	634	1	funzioni
635	1	attirare	635	1	fuoli
636	1	attutita	636	1	fuomo
637	1	aumentando	637	1	grasie
638	1	auto	638	1	grave
639	1	avanti	639	1	graziano
640	1	avesse	640	1	gruppo
641	1	avvertire	641	1	guardato
642	1	avvicinano	642	1	guardiamo
643	1	avvisare	643	1	guida
644	1	azione	644	1	guidare
645	1	baciano	645	1	han
646	1	balia	646	1	incominciare
647	1	basta	647	1	indormendo
648	1	battito	648	1	infinito
649	1	ben	649	1	informazione
650	1	bloccata	650	1	iniziano
651	1	bordo	651	1	innanzitutto
652	1	braccia	652	1	intanto
653	1	bruciano	653	1	invece
654	1	bruciare	654	1	laligancia
655	1	buio	655	1	lampade
656	1	bussando	656	1	lasciare
657	1	buttò	657	1	lasciata
658	1	caduta	658	1	lava
659	1	caduto	659	1	lavorato
660	1	camere	660	1	lebe
661	1	camminare	661	1	leggero
662	1	camminato	662	1	li

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
663	1	capire	663	1	lingrazi
664	1	capo	664	1	lire
665	1	caso	665	1	livece
666	1	cercare	666	1	lolo
667	1	cercato	667	1	loso
668	1	certo	668	1	lossso
669	1	chiamarli	669	1	luso
670	1	chiamerà	670	1	lì
671	1	chiedendo	671	1	male
672	1	cioè	672	1	messo
673	1	circondavano	673	1	mezza
674	1	coi	674	1	mezzo
675	1	coll	675	1	minuti
676	1	colore	676	1	mo
677	1	compenso	677	1	modo
678	1	composto	678	1	molta
679	1	comunicare	679	1	molte
680	1	concluso	680	1	morimo
681	1	condomini	681	1	motivo
682	1	congratulano	682	1	neanche
683	1	contento	683	1	nelle
684	1	continuano	684	1	nera
685	1	continuato	685	1	neruoso
686	1	controllare	686	1	nervosa
687	1	convincerlo	687	1	nervose
688	1	convincono	688	1	nessuno
689	1	corridoio	689	1	neverso
690	1	corso	690	1	noi
691	1	cose	691	1	nove
692	1	credono	692	1	numero
693	1	cuo	693	1	nuonato
694	1	cuore	694	1	nuotare
695	1	danni	695	1	occhiale
696	1	dello	696	1	occupato
697	1	destro	697	1	ocupato
698	1	devono	698	1	ola
699	1	dimenano	699	1	opato
700	1	dimensioni	700	1	opinione
701	1	dirigendosi	701	1	palato
702	1	disteso	702	1	paldano

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
703	1	divampano	703	1	palmenti
704	1	divampare	704	1	paltano
705	1	divampato	705	1	pariamo
706	1	divampavano	706	1	parla
707	1	diventa	707	1	parlato
708	1	dormivano	708	1	parle
709	1	dovranno	709	1	passeggiata
710	1	dovrà	710	1	paure
711	1	edificio	711	1	peccato
712	1	effettivamente	712	1	pel
713	1	elastica	713	1	pensando
714	1	ennesima	714	1	pensavano
715	1	episodio	715	1	pentiere
716	1	esito	716	1	pericoloso
717	1	esortano	717	1	personi
718	1	espandono	718	1	pian
719	1	essa	719	1	plende
720	1	essendo	720	1	plendele
721	1	esso	721	1	plendeno
722	1	evitato	722	1	plimo
723	1	faccia	723	1	poliziata
724	1	faceva	724	1	poliziotti
725	1	farlo	725	1	pom
726	1	fatta	726	1	pombiere
727	1	felici	727	1	pomopieri
728	1	ferma	728	1	pompiemieri
729	1	festaggiamenti	729	1	pomupie
730	1	fianco	730	1	pomupierie
731	1	fila	731	1	pontori
732	1	fin	732	1	popoli
733	1	finire	733	1	portano
734	1	focolai	734	1	portare
735	1	fondo	735	1	porto
736	1	forte	736	1	pozil
737	1	fortuna	737	1	prenda
738	1	forza	738	1	prendere
739	1	freddoloso	739	1	prendo
740	1	fretta	740	1	preoccupa
741	1	fuochi	741	1	preoccupano
742	1	furgone	742	1	prepara

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
743	1	gabinetto	743	1	preparato
744	1	gesti	744	1	preponente
745	1	gesticolano	745	1	pronto
746	1	gettato	746	1	punte
747	1	gia	747	1	qua
748	1	giornata	748	1	qualche
749	1	giro	749	1	quande
750	1	giunto	750	1	quella
751	1	grandi	751	1	qui
752	1	guardando	752	1	rete
753	1	hm	753	1	ricevuto
754	1	ho	754	1	richiama
755	1	idem	755	1	richiamato
756	1	idrante	756	1	ricorda
757	1	imminente	757	1	rin
758	1	impaurito	758	1	ringrazato
759	1	impresa	759	1	riposto
760	1	incendiando	760	1	risponda
761	1	inchinandosi	761	1	risponde
762	1	inchino	762	1	rispondere
763	1	incoraggiandoli	763	1	rispondo
764	1	indicano	764	1	risposta
765	1	indicare	765	1	ritelefonare
766	1	inizia	766	1	ritelefonato
767	1	inizialmente	767	1	ritorna
768	1	inizio	768	1	riuscito
769	1	inquadrata	769	1	rivice
770	1	inquieta	770	1	ros
771	1	insieme	771	1	rusi
772	1	insistono	772	1	s
773	1	intatta	773	1	salata
774	1	intenzione	774	1	sale
775	1	inutilmente	775	1	salire
776	1	invaso	776	1	salito
777	1	invitando	777	1	saltale
778	1	lenzuolo	778	1	saltar
779	1	lontano	779	1	salto
780	1	lunga	780	1	salve
781	1	manca	781	1	sbagliato
782	1	meglio	782	1	sca

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
783	1	meno	783	1	scalpa
784	1	mi	784	1	scarpa
785	1	migliore	785	1	scarpe
786	1	minima	786	1	scavo
787	1	minimamente	787	1	scegliere
788	1	molta	788	1	scendi
789	1	mostra	789	1	scerso
790	1	muovono	790	1	scerto
791	1	muro	791	1	scripli
792	1	musicchetta	792	1	scripule
793	1	nello	793	1	scripure
794	1	nervoso	794	1	se
795	1	notare	795	1	seconda
796	1	numerosa	796	1	sedia
797	1	occhiata	797	1	sedie
798	1	ode	798	1	sendo
799	1	okay	799	1	sentitono
800	1	operazione	800	1	servato
801	1	oppone	801	1	serve
802	1	opportuno	802	1	sia
803	1	osservare	803	1	siamo
804	1	osservato	804	1	siccome
805	1	ostinarsi	805	1	significa
806	1	ovvero	806	1	signo
807	1	panico	807	1	signola
808	1	parla	808	1	signoli
809	1	parlando	809	1	signorle
810	1	parlino	810	1	signra
811	1	partendo	811	1	sigume
812	1	parti	812	1	silenzio
813	1	partito	813	1	simile
814	1	partivano	814	1	sinistra
815	1	passeggiato	815	1	snibene
816	1	pen	816	1	sognore
817	1	pensando	817	1	sonate
818	1	pensarci	818	1	spece
819	1	pensare	819	1	spegneto
820	1	pensò	820	1	spesa
821	1	percussioni	821	1	spesso
822	1	picchia	822	1	spiegato

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
823	1	poco	823	1	squillare
824	1	pomperi	824	1	stanco
825	1	possa	825	1	stesso
826	1	possiamo	826	1	sto
827	1	possono	827	1	storia
828	1	poterlo	828	1	strano
829	1	povero	829	1	studio
830	1	precipitatosi	830	1	stupidi
831	1	prenderlo	831	1	stupito
832	1	preoccupando	832	1	stupore
833	1	preoccupata	833	1	succe
834	1	preparato	834	1	sucende
835	1	presumibilmente	835	1	sue
836	1	presentano	836	1	sull
837	1	presume	837	1	suonare
838	1	presumere	838	1	suono
839	1	procinto	839	1	svegliate
840	1	profondamente	840	1	svela
841	1	propongono	841	1	sviene
842	1	prossimità	842	1	ta
843	1	protettore	843	1	tanta
844	1	provando	844	1	tanto
845	1	provenienti	845	1	tattera
846	1	pubblico	846	1	telefonata
847	1	pure	847	1	temo
848	1	qualcuno	848	1	tempo
849	1	quelle	849	1	tenda
850	1	quidi	850	1	terra
851	1	rappresentazione	851	1	tessuto
852	1	reca	852	1	tira
853	1	rese	853	1	tirare
854	1	resistenza	854	1	toccato
855	1	rialza	855	1	tolme
856	1	riavere	856	1	tornare
857	1	riceve	857	1	tornata
858	1	ricevuto	858	1	tra
859	1	richiama	859	1	tranquillo
860	1	richiamato	860	1	triste
861	1	richiesta	861	1	tronalto
862	1	ricomposto	862	1	tuffo

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
863	1	riconoscenti	863	1	tuliste
864	1	riconoscere	864	1	tutta
865	1	ridendo	865	1	uerde
866	1	rientra	866	1	uguale
867	1	rifa	867	1	ultima
868	1	rilassante	868	1	ultimo
869	1	rimane	869	1	uo
870	1	rimanere	870	1	uolta
871	1	rimasti	871	1	usato
872	1	rimbocca	872	1	uscita
873	1	rimessa	873	1	usciamo
874	1	rimettersi	874	1	uso
875	1	ringraziati	875	1	uza
876	1	ringraziato	876	1	vada
877	1	ripassa	877	1	vadino
878	1	ripensato	878	1	vai
879	1	ripetuta	879	1	vaie
880	1	ripetuti	880	1	vandie
881	1	riprova	881	1	vaso
882	1	risalito	882	1	vedano
883	1	rispondeva	883	1	vederle
884	1	rispondono	884	1	vedio
885	1	rispose	885	1	velbi
886	1	riuscita	886	1	veligi
887	1	riusciti	887	1	velti
888	1	ro	888	1	veniedo
889	1	saltato	889	1	verbo
890	1	salutando	890	1	versi
891	1	salutati	891	1	verso
892	1	salva	892	1	vesto
893	1	salvandosi	893	1	viagi
894	1	salvarlo	894	1	viendo
895	1	salì	895	1	viene
896	1	sarà	896	1	viligi
897	1	sbaglio	897	1	viso
898	1	sbracciano	898	1	vivere
899	1	sbraitano	899	1	vivo
900	1	scala	900	1	voce
901	1	scendono	901	1	voi
902	1	schiena	902	1	vorrei

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
903	1	schierano	903	1	vudimo
904	1	sconsolato	904	1	vuò
905	1	scoppiate	905	1	vuoglio
906	1	scoppiò	906	1	vuòia
907	1	scuote	907	1	vuòiono
908	1	scuotere	908	1	vuote
909	1	sentiva	909	1	zati
910	1	sentivano		9014	
911	1	serata			
912	1	signorr			
913	1	sistema			
914	1	soddisfatti			
915	1	soggiorno			
916	1	sola			
917	1	sollecitazioni			
918	1	sopraggiunge			
919	1	soprassalto			
920	1	sorride			
921	1	sostengono			
922	1	sottofondo			
923	1	spaventa			
924	1	spaventosa			
925	1	spegnendo			
926	1	spegnerlo			
927	1	spense			
928	1	spenta			
929	1	spiegare			
930	1	sporto			
931	1	sposta			
932	1	spostati			
933	1	spostato			
934	1	spunta			
935	1	squillo			
936	1	stanco			
937	1	stessi			
938	1	storia			
939	1	strano			
940	1	stringere			
941	1	stringono			
942	1	strisce			

B.1 Vocabulary of the texts

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
943	1	successivamente			
944	1	sull			
945	1	suonato			
946	1	suoni			
947	1	suono			
948	1	svegliati			
949	1	svegliava			
950	1	talmente			
951	1	tazza			
952	1	teatrale			
953	1	telecamera			
954	1	telefona			
955	1	tendono			
956	1	tentato			
957	1	tenuto			
958	1	teso			
959	1	tipo			
960	1	tirano			
961	1	toccava			
962	1	tornare			
963	1	tornò			
964	1	totalmente			
965	1	troppa			
966	1	trova			
967	1	ultima			
968	1	ultimi			
969	1	uniforme			
970	1	uomo			
971	1	uscì			
972	1	vale			
973	1	vedano			
974	1	vedo			
975	1	via			
976	1	vicini			
977	1	vicino			
978	1	vigile			
979	1	vigilessa			
980	1	visti			
981	1	vittoria			
982	1	vogliono			

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Native sample			IL sample		
rank	freq	token	rank	freq	token
983	1	voltandosi			
	9903				

B.2 Biemann's experiment

Abbreviations	
adj	adjective
adv	adverbe
clit	clitic
con	connective
det	determiner
fv	finite verb
int	interjection
nfv	non finite verb
nn	noun
num	numeral
on	onomatopoeia
pn	proper noun
pp	past participial
pre	preposition
pre+det	preposition+determiner
pron	pronoun
v	Verb (fv/nfv)
car	category
cl	class/cluster
H.	homogeneity
tok	number of tokens in the class

B.2.1 NL Italian - Clusters

Output of Biemann's algorithm on NL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H > 0.75	cat
1	4	il del dal povero	0	0	1	3	1	det
2	5	signor telefono pompiere numero colore	0	0	5	0	1	nn
3	2	e che	0	0	0	2	1	con
4	6	blu rossi verdi verde giallo ro	0	0	0	6	1	pn

B.2 Biemann's experiment

Output of Biemann's algorithm on NL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H > 0.75	cat
5	31	è vede butta sveglia alza rifi- uta sentono accorge sdraia corica siede vedono avvicina affacciano convince recano affaccia allontana getta gira lancia butti rende af- facciò alzò ferma muovono rese sarà sistema sposta	31	0	0	0	1	fv
6	4	i dei ai dai	0	0	0	4	1	det
7	5	pompieri tre nostri suoi pomperi	0	0	2	3	0	
8	23	anche ma allora mentre cui neanche siccome svegliare invitano vedere incitano abitano dunque nè sollevati accorse avvertire avvisare compenso inutilmente mostra pen succesivamente	3	5	0	15	0	
9	2	l dell	0	0	0	2	1	det
10	5	incendio unico omino aria inchino	0	0	4	1	1	nn
11	6	va continua prova corre continuato riprova	5	1	0	0	1	fv
12	2	fuoco cuo	0	0	1	1	0	
13	8	fiamme scale mani abitazioni cop- erte luci braccia cose	0	0	8	0	1	nn
14	4	buttarsi saltare lanciarsi scendere	0	4	0	0	1	nfv
15	10	luce cornetta chiamata testa macchina vita minima riuscita scala storia	0	0	10	0	1	nn
16	9	dormire coricarsi rifiutarsi bru- ciare divampare ostinarsi rimanere scuotere stringere	0	9	0	0	1	nfv
17	6	spegne finita accende bloccata scuote spenta	3	3	0	0	0	
18	6	quindi poi così crepitii presumibil- mente rosse	0	0	1	5	0	
19	3	verso squilla suona	2	0	0	1	0	
20	5	andato tornato triste andata ar- rivata	0	4	0	1	1	nfv
21	15	svegliato accorto alzato coricato buttato sdraiato sviluppato avvic- inato coperto girato propagato reso concluso sporto spostato	0	15	0	0	1	nfv

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Output of Biemann's algorithm on NL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H > 0.75	cat
22	10	nuovo niente no nulla bruciato corsa squillare comunicare strano vittoria	0	3	2	5	0	
23	2	pero però	0	0	0	2	1	con
24	13	invece pensa ringraziano posa riap- pende sale solleva inchinandosi pic- chia ripassa salì sbraitano telefona	11	1	0	1	1	fv
25	2	vuole vuol	2	0	0	0	1	fv
26	7	chiamare chiamato richiamare cuore invitando richiama ri- conoscenti	1	4	0	2	0	
27	2	aver molta	0	1	0	1	0	
28	3	stava riceve rispose	3	0	0	0	1	fv
29	2	caserma stazione	0	0	2	0	1	nn
30	2	cercano tentano	2	0	0	0	1	fv
31	17	mette abbracciano addormenta co- pre dirige tira dirigono distende ac- cinge agitano buttò credono reca rialza salva schierano spaventa	17	0	0	0	1	fv
32	2	spento acceso	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
33	3	torna rientra tornò	3	0	0	0	1	fv
34	2	scende risale	2	0	0	0	1	fv
35	3	salvo piedi fila	0	1	2	0	0	
36	10	vanno aiutano provano tornano al- largano esortano possono rispon- dono tirano vogliono	10	0	0	0	1	fv
37	2	compone rifa	2	0	0	0	1	fv
38	3	riescono cominciano iniziano	3	0	0	0	1	fv
39	4	arrivati ringraziato svegliati visti	0	4	0	0	1	nfv
40	9	buttare allargando espandendo sviluppano ben dimenano incen- diando preoccupando sull	1	6	0	2	0	v
41	2	chiama chiamerà	2	0	0	0	1	fv
42	2	chiude chiudere	1	1	0	0	0	
43	2	convincere salvare	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
44	2	po tipo	0	0	2	0	1	nn
45	2	visto dato	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
46	2	posizionano spostano	2	0	0	0	1	fv
47	2	sera divampato	0	0	1	1	0	
48	2	aiuto insieme	0	0	1	1	0	

B.2 Biemann's experiment

Output of Biemann's algorithm on NL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H > 0.75	cat
49	2	altri ultimi	0	0	0	2	1	adj
50	2	erano siano	2	0	0	0	1	fv
51	2	salvati evitato	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
52	5	scoppia scoppiato divampa inizia scoppiò	4	1	0	0	1	fv
53	2	camion carro	0	0	2	0	1	nn
54	2	dove episodio	0	0	1	1	0	
55	2	amici bisogni	0	0	2	0	1	nn
56	2	preso suonato	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
57	2	quanti felici	0	0	0	2	0	
58	2	sceso risalito	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
59	2	scoppi soprassalto	0	0	2	0	1	nn
60	2	segno cenno	0	0	2	0	1	nn
61	2	svegliarlo cercare	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
62	3	terra coraggio bordo	0	0	3	0	1	nn
63	2	abitanti coinquilini	0	0	2	0	1	nn
64	4	alzarsi agire aiutarlo esso	0	3	0	1	1	nfv
65	2	arrivo auto	0	0	2	0	1	nn
66	2	bianco affinché	0	0	0	2	0	
67	2	cerca richiamato	1	1	0	0	0	v
68	4	decise parlare intenzione pensare	1	2	1	0	0	
69	2	disperato sconsolato	0	0	0	2	1	adj
70	2	guardia turno	0	0	2	0	1	nn
71	2	improvviso inizio	0	0	1	1	0	
72	2	lavoro panico	0	0	2	0	1	nn
73	5	mh abbastanza buio camminare via	0	1	1	3	0	
74	2	modo fretta	0	0	2	0	1	nn
75	4	osservano idem oppone spense	3	0	0	1	1	fv
76	2	pancia rimettersi	0	1	1	0	0	
77	4	pensato attimo camminato tentato	0	3	1	0	1	nfv
78	2	prendono insistono	2	0	0	0	1	fv
79	2	righe strisce	0	0	2	0	1	nn
80	2	saltar minimamente	0	1	0	1	0	
81	4	sicuro gabinetto pubblico signorr	0	0	2	2	0	
82	2	stavolta spostati	1	0	0	1	0	
83	3	allegra forte numerose	0	0	0	3	1	adj
84	4	andate fin manca vale	2	1	0	1	0	
85	3	assolutamente farlo ho	1	1	0	1	0	
86	2	attenzione furgone	0	0	2	0	1	nn

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Output of Biemann's algorithm on NL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H > 0.75	cat
87	3	attirare convincerlo spegnerlo	0	3	0	0	1	nfv
88	5	attutita corso ringraziati ripetuta salutati	0	5	0	0	1	nfc
89	2	avvicinano presentano	2	0	0	0	1	fv
90	3	capo squillo suono	0	0	3	0	1	nn
91	2	composto passeggiato	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
92	2	divampano nervoso	1	0	0	1	0	
93	2	dovrà possa	2	0	0	0	1	fv
94	3	imminente impresa operazione	0	0	2	1	0	
95	2	indicano propongono	2	0	0	0	1	fv
96	2	inizialmente vigile	0	0	1	1	0	
97	2	lunga sollecitazioni	0	0	1	1	0	
98	2	notare riconoscere	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
99	2	pensarci ultima	0	1	0	1	0	
100	2	rispondeva sentiva	2	0	0	0	1	fv
101	2	sbracciano tendono	2	0	0	0	1	fv
							69	

B.2.2 IL Italian - clusters

Output of Biemann's algorithm on IL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H. > 0.75	cat
1	3	la ala storia	0	0	1	2	0	
2	13	fuoco telefono polizio fuo bombiere telefonale folno fucuro plendele pozil qua suono vaso	0	2	10	1	1	nn
3	10	blu verde rossi rosso rossa verdi verbi verde rosse luso	0	0	0	10	1	pn
4	5	signore signor signole signola sognore	0	0	0	5	1	pn
5	8	signora persona polizia luce macchina porta polta signo	0	0	8	0	1	nn
6	12	ma anche quando infine finalmente servare aiutata fortuna intanto invece sbagliato vudimo	1	3	1	7	0	con
7	2	non no	0	0	0	2	1	adv
8	5	ha trova acorta se vorrei	3	1	0	1	0	
9	3	di del der	0	0	0	3	1	det
10	2	lui lei	0	0	0	2	1	pro
11	3	va andare vado	2	1	0	0	0	

B.2 Biemann's experiment

Output of Biemann's algorithm on IL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H. > 0.75	cat
12	11	da bussare passa spegne apri dispi- ace facendo fossi neanche scavo tutta	5	2	1	3	0	
13	5	letto buen cas chi mezzo	0	0	1	4	0	
14	3	vigile poliziotto vegele	0	0	3	0	1	nn
15	3	c cos folchi	0	0	1	2	0	
16	14	più chiuso spento stato troppo suc- cesso diventato già pieno difendo grave incominciare spegneto tanto	1	8	0	5	0	
17	2	persone signorle	0	0	2	0	1	nn
18	18	adesso spegnere vede scope vedere mento salvare accende apamento aprire conosco difensare dormi- ano fetto infinito prendo siccome sigume	6	6	1	5	0	
19	5	molto svegliato svegliata spesso tanta	0	2	0	3	0	
20	2	un una	0	0	0	2	1	det
21	6	sveglia alza alzo dormenta ferma preoccupano	6	0	0	0	1	fv
22	6	pompieri signori suoi polizi dom- pieri signoli	0	0	5	1	1	nn
23	3	so sa sai	3	0	0	0	1	fv
24	6	telefona torna continuare arivece dolino tornare	4	2	0	0	0	
25	3	paura dormito paula	0	1	2	0	0	
26	6	grande forte nervoso alto freddo neverso	0	0	0	6	1	adj
27	3	vigili vaie vandie	0	0	3	0	1	nn
28	5	telefonato pensato provato salto spiegato	0	5	0	0	1	pp
29	7	contenti felice felici alivati contanti silenzio stupidi	0	1	1	5	1	adj
30	3	può funzione vuio	3	0	0	0	1	fv
31	6	lampada ambulanza scale scala cacca scarpe	0	0	6	0	1	nn
32	5	sente ricevere finisci livece plende	3	1	0	1	0	
33	6	sentito visto preso rispoto spiega digitato	1	5	0	0	1	pp

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Output of Biemann's algorithm on IL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H. > 0.75	cat
34	22	andato uscito andata sceso caduto scendo bravo accesa alimano chiamacendo dolmile fermo fuomo lasciata molte ocupato opato parlato salito scerto tornata tronalto	0	18	0	4	1	nfv
35	2	tutte quande	0	0	0	2	1	prn
36	2	ah oh	0	0	0	2	1	esc
37	3	uscire scendere uscile	0	3	0	0	1	inf
38	2	arrivato arrivata	0	2	0	0	1	pp
39	13	pausa altro abita bluto cu occupato pericoloso popoli squillare stupore triste tuliste vivo	1	2	1	9	0	
40	4	alzato occupare dormente dormimento	0	3	1	0	1	nfv
41	5	bru uende aciulo azulo agiulo	0	0	0	5	1	pn
42	7	chiamare \$eh anghe cerca chiedo richiamato vesto	3	2	0	2	0	
43	2	voglio voglio	2	0	0	0	1	fv
44	2	chiamata spece	1	0,5	0,5	0	0	
45	4	dormi spende all bata	3	0	0	1	1	fv
46	3	suonato male suonare	0	2	0	1	0	
47	3	chiamando telefonando dole	0	2	0	1	0	
48	3	dormino grasie vedano	2	0	0	1	0	
49	3	guidano sali guida	3	0	0	0	1	fv
50	3	otto cinque nove	0	0	0	3	1	num
51	3	po pò tessuto	0	0	1	2	0	
52	2	spegnande spenie	1	1	0	0	0	
53	2	acende accede	2	0	0	0	1	fv
54	2	cadere scegliere	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
55	2	contente dolce	0	0	0	2	1	adj
56	2	diagi serve	1	0	0	1	0	
57	5	donna buona funzioni passeggiata tattera	1	0	3	1	0	
58	2	dunque domo	0	0	0	2	0	
59	2	figure vedio	1	0	1	0	0	
60	3	guardano addormentano dolmito	2	1	0	0	0	
61	2	riesce vuovia	2	0	0	0	1	fv
62	4	rispunda chiamate risponda risponde	3	1	0	0	1	fv
63	2	teme temo	2	0	0	0	1	fv

B.3 Clark experiment

Output of Biemann's algorithm on IL sample			Analysis					
cl	typ	items	fv	nfv	nn	rest	H. > 0.75	cat
64	4	accen arza sentitono snibene	2	1	0	1	0	
65	2	accito rispono	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
66	3	agitate alzono palato	1	2	0	0	0	
67	2	aiutarmi nessuno	0	1	0	1	0	
68	2	arriva cominciato	1	1	0	0	0	
69	2	aspetta scripli	2	0	0	0	1	fv
70	4	bieco com mezza vuote	0	0	0	4	1	adj
71	2	borta saltale	0	1	1	0	0	
72	3	brava paure scripule	1	0	1	1	0	
73	2	buttare scerso	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
74	3	cam chiudi prenda	2	0	1	0	0	
75	3	cambia chembia pian	2	0	0	1	0	
76	5	cambiaie cambiare loso paldano portare	1	3	0	1	0	
77	3	cercare el uguale	0	1	0	2	0	
78	2	cercato deciso	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
79	2	devo innanzitutto	1	0	0	1	0	
80	2	informazione telefonanata	0	0	2	0	1	nn
81	3	messo pensando plendeno	1	2	0	0	0	
82	3	minuti ringrazato uolta	0	1	2	0	0	
83	5	modo prepara rete siamo sue	2	0	2	1	0	
84	3	morimo veniedo voi	1	1	0	1	0	
85	2	poliziata pomupie	0	0	2	0	1	nn
86	2	prendere rispondere	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
87	2	preoccupa sviene	2	0	0	0	1	nn
88	2	ricevuto riposto	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
89	3	risposta ritorna sucende	2	0	1	0	1	nn
90	2	scarpa vivere	0	1	1	0	0	
91	2	succe usciamo	1	0	0	1	0	
92	2	svegliate zati	0	2	0	0	1	nfv
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B.3 Clark experiment

B.3.1 Italian NL - Clusters

Output		Analysis
Type	cl	PoS
sia	1	fv
dopo	1	prep/con

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Output		Analysis
si	1	clit
mentre	1	con
finalmente	1	adv
ma	1	con
le	1	det
adesso	1	adv
tutti	1	pron
sembra	1	fv
ci	1	clit
ora	1	adv
forse	1	adv
pero	1	con
probabilmente	1	adv
sempre	1	adv
lo	1	clit
proprio	1	adv
poi	1	con
scende	1	fv
essere	1	nfv
nonostante	1	prep/con
li	1	clit
ed	1	con
se	1	con
è	1	fv
e	1	con
bussa	1	fv
non	1	adv
era	1	fv
30		function words
alzato	2	pp
più	2	adv
siede	2	fv
siccome	2	con
chiude	2	fv
scale	2	nn
ringraziano	2	fv
salgono	2	fv
coricato	2	pp
successo	2	pp
svegliato	2	pp
vedono	2	fv

B.3 Clark experiment

Output		Analysis
continua	2	fv
intanto	2	adv
invitano	2	fv
arrivano	2	fv
dorme	2	fv
accorge	2	fv
pensa	2	fv
cercano	2	fv
mette	2	fv
fa	2	fv
sentono	2	fv
rifiuta	2	fv
guarda	2	fv
riescono	2	fv
corica	2	fv
sente	2	fv
vediamo	2	fv
stesso	2	pron
giù	2	adv/prep
compone	2	fv
vuole	2	fv
posizionano	2	fv
infine	2	adv
fiamme	2	nn
chiama	2	fv
allora	2	con
vede	2	fv
stato	2	pp
infatti	2	con
davanti	2	prep
neanche	2	adv/con
alza	2	fv
accorto	2	pp
torna	2	fv
anche	2	adv
sveglia	2	fv
sdraia	2	fv
va	2	fv
andato	2	pp
spegne	2	fv
visto	2	pp

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Output		Analysis
decide	2	fv
54		verbs
bagno	3	nn
frattempo	3	nn
tetto	3	nn
finestra	3	nn
tappeto	3	nn
telone	3	nn
rumore	3	nn
fuoco	3	nn
pompieri	3	nn
appartamento	3	nn
signor	3	nn
numero	3	nn
telo	3	nn
po	3	adv
suo	3	poss
incendio	3	nn
letto	3	nn
telefono	3	nn
unico	3	adj/pron
omino	3	nn
primo	3	adj/pron
quale	3	adj/pron
22		nn
invece	4	adv
tranquillamente	4	adv
c	4	clit
vanno	4	fv
delle	4	prep+det
squilla	4	fv
elastico	4	adj
salta	4	fv
qui	4	adv
lui	4	pron
risponde	4	fv
sopra	4	prep
sotto	4	prep
verso	4	prep

B.3 Clark experiment

Output		Analysis
diciamo	4	fv
fuori	4	prep
esce	4	fv
con	4	con
che	4	con
punto	4	nn
	20	
dall	5	prep+det
un	5	det
del	5	prep+det
nell	5	prep+det
col	5	prep+det
dal	5	prep+det
dell	5	prep+det
il	5	det
sul	5	prep+det
nel	5	prep+det
al	5	prep+det
dalla	5	det
l	5	det
	13	
blu	6	pn
verdi	6	pn
rossi	6	pn
verde	6	pn
	4	
all	7	prep+det
sulla	7	prep+det
a	7	prep
di	7	prep
ad	7	prep
la	7	det
della	7	prep+det
dei	7	prep+det
quando	7	con
ha	7	fv
in	7	prep
viene	7	fv
una	7	det
gli	7	det

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

Output		Analysis
nella	7	prep+det
aver	7	fv
sono	7	fv
per	7	prep
sta	7	fv
hanno	7	fv
molto	7	adv
stessa	7	adj/adv
i	7	det
dalle	7	prep+det
alla	7	prep+det
da	7	prep
dai	7	prep+det
stanno	7	fv
ai	7	prep+det
questa	7	det
stava	7	fv
	31	prep/det

B.3.2 Italian IL - Clusters

Output of Clark's algorithm on IL sample		Analysis
Type	cl	PoS
tua	1	adj
rumore	1	nn
così	1	adv
camera	1	nn
fuori	1	adv
sua	1	adj
vegile	1	nn
finestra	1	nn
andato	1	pp
persone	1	nn
vigile	1	det
folco	1	nn
uscito	1	pp
suo	1	adj
accordo	1	nn
più	1	adv
andata	1	pp
telefonata	1	pp

B.3 Clark experiment

giù	1	adv
arrivato	1	pp
porta	1	nn
piano	1	nn/adv
luce	1	nn
telefono	1	nn
letto	1	nn
lampada	1	nn
scale	1	nn
casa	1	nn
grande	1	adj
stato	1	pp
uomini	1	nn
dormire	1	nfv
telefonare	1	nfv
fuoco	1	nn
nuovo	1	adj
gente	1	nn
36		nn
va	2	fv
ancora	2	adv
sta	2	fv
hanno	2	fv
torna	2	fv
uno	2	num
deve	2	fv
lui	2	pron
non	2	adv
si	2	clit
no	2	adv
telefona	2	fv
scendere	2	nfv
esce	2	fv
ha	2	fv
dorma	2	fv
c	2	clit
come	2	adv
forse	2	adv
due	2	num
dicono	2	fv

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

dove	2	adv
22		fv
signole	3	nn
signor	3	nn
signora	3	nn
signore	3	nn
polizia	3	nn
poliziotto	3	nn
lo	3	clit
uomo	3	nn
persona	3	nn
9		nn
un	4	det
fatto	4	pp
alla	4	pre+det
è	4	fv
su	4	pre
sul	4	pre+det
suona	4	fv
da	4	pre
della	4	pre+det
per	4	pre
d	4	pre
sulla	4	pre+det
dal	4	pre+det
di	4	pre
al	4	pre+det
a	4	pre
qualcosa	4	pron
del	4	pre+det
dalla	4	pre+det
guarda	4	fv
fa	4	fv
prende	4	fv
in	4	pre
23		pre/det
volta	5	nn
scende	5	fv

B.3 Clark experiment

i	5	det
con	5	pre
sono	5	fv
lei	5	pron
forte	5	adj
mentre	5	con
solo	5	adv
poi	5	con
parlano	5	fv
infine	5	con
parlare	5	nfv
felici	5	adj
io	5	pron
nervoso	5	adj
anche	5	adv
amico	5	nn
tutti	5	adj
drin	5	ono
felice	5	adj
contenti	5	adj
ah	5	int
e	5	con
ma	5	con
ci	5	clit
adesso	5	adv
dorme	5	fv
dopo	5	con
cosa	5	nn
che	5	con
31		function words
verdi	6	pn
losso	6	pn
sa	6	fv
rosso	6	pn
rossi	6	pn
so	6	fv
rossa	6	pn
blu	6	pn
verdo	6	pn
russo	6	pn

B. RESULTS OF CLUSTERING ANALYSIS OF SOURCE CATEGORIES

verbi	6	pn
verde	6	pn
12		pn
nel	7	pre+det
l	7	det
perché	7	con
le	7	det
il	7	det
tre	7	num
la	7	det
nella	7	pre+det
8		pre+det

Appendix C

Used corpora

C.1 Pavia Corpus

The Pavia Corpus is the result of both longitudinal and cross-sectional research design conducted across 15 years by a group of Italian Universities (for more details see Andorno and Bernini, 2003). The corpus consists of the transcriptions of spoken interviews between members of the project and twenty L2 Italian learners of various L1 backgrounds (ranging from Chinese, Cantonese, Moroccan Arabic, Albanian, French, English and German). The overall recording time may range from one to ten hours per learner and the .txt transcribed files may contain from 7.000 to 80.000 tokens. The whole corpus contains about 600,000 tokens. The text genre can be defined as a mix of unstructured, semi-guided conversation, personal narratives, elicitation tasks such as story re-telling and also role-playing.

C.2 Chini Corpus

This corpus was collected between 1995 and 1998 at the University of Pavia by Marina Chini and her collaborators. It is a cross-sectional corpus of spoken Italian by 16 German speaking (63 files) and 10 Spanish speaking (24 files) students of L2 Italian. The files are in in .cha (CHAT) extension but they can be easily transferred to .txt or to .doc formats. The subjects retell the Frog Story, one or more scenes from the film Modern Times and personal narratives. A native interviewer is present and participates in the dialogue. Each subject is described by a separate bio-sketch .doc file. A file may contain from a minimum of 400 to a maximum of 4500 tokens.

C. USED CORPORA

C.3 ISA Corpus

ISA Italiano Scritto di Americani (Written Italian by Americans) data come from written paragraphs composed by about two-hundred undergraduate American students spending one or two semesters of their second or third university year at the I.E.S. program in Milan. Students were asked to describe 11 scenes from the film “Pane e tulipani” (Italy, 2000) according to the elicitation formula: “describe what you’ve just seen: what are the characters doing?”. Students were free to decide whether to tell the scene in the past or in the present tense. Teachers did not interact with students during the session and the students were unaware what the aim of the assignment was. There are 150 .txt files already transcribed and almost 600 files still to transcribe. ISA comes with software for manual tagging according to the early guidelines of SLAt. About 20% of files are from beginner students; another 25% from intermediate students and the remaining 55% from advanced L2 Italian students.

C.4 Marco Polo Corpus

Marco Polo corpus is still under construction and was made available for this research by kind permission of Prof. Cecilia Andorno, University of Pavia. It is a spoken corpus: the informants are native speakers of Mandarin Chinese (but a control corpus with Italian native speakers is also included), who had resided in Pavia for 6 months in order to participate in an intensive Italian language course. In the sample the informants are first presented with a video (“Finite Story” for both groups (Dimroth 2006)) which they are then asked to retell to the interviewer (see table C.1).

Being a spoken corpus the recorded interviews have been transcribed using an adaptation of the CHAT standard, created for the CHILDES corpus (MacWhinney 2000)¹. The annotation of the corpus includes special marking for repetitions, false starts, self repairs and other types of speech disfluencies. This kind of annotation is very useful, since speech disfluencies, in particular one token repetitions (like the repetition of the articles) can create large problems to any automatic system of natural language processing and have to be stripped away, together with the other CHAT symbols. The

¹The specifications for the corpus have not been published. For an introduction to the annotation system we refer to the Pavia Corpus, see Andorno & Bernini (2003).

details of the algorithm that has been used to clean the corpus texts can be found in Appendix A ².

Table C.1: default

Name	Marco Polo
Informants	28 Chinese exchange students
Control groups	19 Italian Native speakers
Elicitation	Retelling of “Finite Story”
Supervision	Cecilia Andorno, University of Pavia
Period	2007-2008
Size of IL group	9014 tokens after cleaning
Size of NL group	9903 tokens after cleaning

²It is very important to underline that the annotation of the corpus is very consistent this allows a completely automatic cleaning of the corpus, and no direct intervention on the external annotator’s work.

C. USED CORPORA

Appendix D

Tagging Procedure

D.1 Tagging with TeeTagger

Given a corpus of IL texts, each saved in a separate file, the tagging of each file is performed with command

```
TreeTagger -token -lemma -threshold 0.99999 -prob input.txt > output.txt
```

The options **-token -lemma -threshold 0.99999 -prob** are added to the default command, in order to obtain the lemma and confidence level as well as the tag.

The output looks like this:

```
va VER:pres andare 0.988343
bene ADV bene 0.894131
. SENT . 1.000000
c'PRO:demo c' 1.000000
era VER:impf essere 0.945113
un DET:indef un 0.998300
ragazzo NOM ragazzo 1.000000
piccolo ADJ piccolo 0.990862
che PRO:rela che 0.934021
aveva VER:impf avere 1.000000
due ADJ due 1.000000
amici NOM amico 0.856499
...
```

D. TAGGING PROCEDURE

D.1.1 Transform to XML

A Perl script is used to transform the TreeTagger output into XML. Here is a small sample of the output:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="ISO-8859-1"?>
<file name="SPO_CHI_GR_FROG_ALE.txt">
<s>
<token tag="VER:pres" lemma="andare" prob="b">va</token>
<token tag="ADV" lemma="bene" prob="c">bene</token>
</s>
<s>
<token tag="PRO:demo" lemma="c'" prob="a">c'</token>
<token tag="VER:impf" lemma="essere" prob="b">era</token>
<token tag="DET:indef" lemma="un" prob="b">un</token>
<token tag="NOM" lemma="ragazzo" prob="a">ragazzo</token>
<token tag="ADJ" lemma="piccolo" prob="b">piccolo</token>
<token tag="PRO:rela" lemma="che" prob="b">che</token>
<token tag="VER:impf" lemma="avere" prob="a">aveva</token>
<token tag="ADJ" lemma="due" prob="a">due</token>
<token tag="NOM" lemma="amico" prob="c">amici</token>
<token tag="PON" lemma="," prob="a">,</token>
<token tag="DET:indef" lemma="un" prob="b">un</token>
<token tag="ADJ" lemma="piccolo" prob="b">piccolo</token>
<token tag="NOM" lemma="cane" prob="a">cane</token>
<token tag="CON" lemma="e" prob="a">e</token>
<token tag="DET:indef" lemma="un" prob="b">un</token>
<token tag="PON" lemma="," prob="a">,</token>
<token tag="DET:indef" lemma="una" prob="a">una</token>
<token tag="ADJ" lemma="piccolo" prob="b">piccola</token>
<token tag="NOM" lemma="rana" prob="c">rana</token>
<token tag="CON" lemma="e" prob="a">e</token>
</s>
...
</file>
```

The root element is <file>, and it contains the name of the input file as an attribute. The script splits each line in order to create an xml element named <token> with the attributes 'tag', 'lemma', 'prob' (for the confidence)

For each full stop a sentence element <s> is added.

For the 'prob' attribute, the confidence value is transformed from a real number to a letter value, according to this table:

a = treetagger confidence = 1
b= treetagger confidence = 1 < x <= 0.9
c= treetagger confidence = 0.9 < x <= 0.8
c= treetagger confidence = 0.8 < x <= 0.7
d= treetagger confidence = 0.7 < x <= 0.6
e= treetagger confidence = 0.6 < x <= 0.5
f= treetagger confidence = 0.5 < x <= 0.4
g= treetagger confidence = 0.4 < x <= 0.3
h= treetagger confidence = 0.3 < x <= 0.2
i= treetagger confidence = 0.2 < x <= 0.1
j= treetagger confidence = 0.1 < x <= 0.0

Once the corpus is contexts can be retrieved by using either Xqueries or a XML aware concordancer like XAIRA (Burnard 2004).

For further information, and the step by step procedure with the downloadable scripts see:

<http://sla-tagging.unipv.it/CP/index.php>

D. TAGGING PROCEDURE

Appendix E

TreeTagger Tagsets for Italian

E.1 Alternative Tagsets

TreeTagger, just like any other stochastic tagger, can be retrained with any chosen tagset - provided that a training corpus is available, which has been tagged with the chosen tagset. TreeTagger comes with two possible tagsets. Both are enriched tagsets, in the sense that they bear reference not only to the lexical category, but also to some of their defining features.

In this work, Stein's tagset is preferred, because it maintains the distinction between determined and undetermined article, but the two tagsets are on the whole quite equivalent and functions can be written to convert one into the other, combining lemma and PoS information.

E.2 Stein's Tagset

Pos	Definition
ABR	abbreviation
ADJ	adjective
ADV	adverb
CON	conjunction
DET:def	definite article
DET:indef	indefinite article
INT	interjection
NOM	noun
NPR	name
NUM	numeral

E. TREETAGGER TAGSETS FOR ITALIAN

PON	punctuation
PRE	preposition
PRE:det	preposition+article
PRO	pronoun
PRO:demo	demonstrative pronoun
PRO:indef	indefinite pronoun
PRO:inter	interrogative pronoun
PRO:pers	personal pronoun
PRO:poss	possessive pronoun
PRO:refl	reflexive pronoun
PRO:rela	relative pronoun
SENT	sentence marker
SYM	symbol
VER:cimp	verb conjunctive imperfect
VER:cond	verb conditional
VER:cpre	verb conjunctive present
VER:futu	verb future tense
VER:geru	verb gerund
VER:impe	verb imperative
VER:impf	verb imperfect
VER:infi	verb infinitive
VER:pper	verb participle perfect
VER:ppre	verb participle present
VER:pres	verb present
VER:refl:infi	verb reflexive infinitive
VER:remo	verb simple past

Table E.1: Stein - Tagset for Italian

E.3 Baroni's Tagset

Pos	Definition
ADJ	adjective
ADV	adverb (excluding -mente forms)
ADV:mente	adverb ending in -mente
ART	article
ARTPRE	preposition + article
AUX:fin	finite form of auxiliary

AUX:fin:cli	finite form of auxiliary with clitic
AUX:geru	gerundive form of auxiliary
AUX:geru:cli	gerundive form of auxiliary with clitic
AUX:infi	infinitival form of auxiliary
AUX:infi:cli	infinitival form of auxiliary with clitic
AUX:ppast	past participle of auxiliary
AUX:ppre	present participle of auxiliary
CHE	che
CLI	clitic
CON	conjunction
DET:demo	demonstrative determiner
DET:indef	indefinite determiner
DET:num	numeral determiner
DET:poss	possessive determiner
DET:wh	wh determiner
NEG	negation
NOCAT	non-linguistic element
NOUN	noun
NPR	proper noun
NUM	number
PRE	preposition
PRO:demo	demonstrative pronoun
PRO:indef	indefinite pronoun
PRO:num	numeral pronoun
PRO:pers	personal pronoun
PRO:poss	possessive pronoun
PUN	non-sentence-final punctuation mark
SENT	sentence-final punctuation mark
VER2:fin	finite form of modal/causal verb
VER2:fin:cli	finite form of modal/causal verb with clitic
VER2:geru	gerundive form of modal/causal verb
VER2:geru:cli	gerundive form of modal/causal verb with clitic
VER2:infi	infinitival form of modal/causal verb
VER2:infi:cli	infinitival form of modal/causal verb with clitic
VER2:ppast	past participle of modal/causal verb
VER2:ppre	present participle of modal/causal verb
VER:fin	finite form of verb
VER:fin:cli	finite form of verb with clitic
VER:geru	gerundive form of verb
VER:geru:cli	gerundive form of verb with clitic
VER:infi	infinitival form of verb

E. TREETAGGER TAGSETS FOR ITALIAN

VER:infi:cli	infinitival form of verb with clitic
VER:ppast	past participle of verb
VER:ppast:cli	past participle of verb with clitic
VER:ppre	present participle of verb
WH	wh word

Table E.2: Baroni - Tagset for Italian

Appendix F

N-gram Analysis Results - Full tables

F.1 Files Considered and Categories

ita.FA01.tag	ita.MA13.tag	ita.NA09.tag
ita.FA02.tag	ita.MA14.tag	ita.NA10.tag
ita.FA03.tag	ita.MA15.tag	ita.NA11.tag
ita.FA04.tag	ita.MA16.tag	ita.NA12.tag
ita.FA05.tag	ita.MA17.tag	ita.NA13.tag
ita.FA06.tag	ita.MA18.tag	ita.RA01.tag
ita.FA07.tag	ita.MA19.tag	ita.RA02.tag
ita.FA08.tag	ita.MA20.tag	ita.RA03.tag
ita.FA09.tag	ita.MA21.tag	ita.RA04.tag
ita.FA10.tag	ita.MA22.tag	ita.RA05.tag
ita.FA11.tag	ita.MA23.tag	ita.RA06.tag
ita.FA12.tag	ita.MA24.tag	ita.RA07.tag
ita.FA13.tag	ita.MA25.tag	ita.RA08.tag
ita.FA14.tag	ita.MA26.tag	ita.RA09.tag
ita.MA01.tag	ita.MA27.tag	spa.FRSPIANU.tag
ita.MA02.tag	ita.MA28.tag	spa.FRSPIASU.tag
ita.MA03.tag	ita.MA29.tag	spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag
ita.MA04.tag	ita.MA30.tag	spa.FrogILEO.tag
ita.MA05.tag	ita.NA01.tag	spa.MTSPIANU.tag
ita.MA06.tag	ita.NA02.tag	spa.MTSPIASU.tag
ita.MA07.tag	ita.NA03.tag	spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag
ita.MA08.tag	ita.NA04.tag	spa.MdtmIALA.tag
ita.MA09.tag	ita.NA05.tag	spa.MdtmIDAM.tag
ita.MA10.tag	ita.NA06.tag	spa.MdtmILEO.tag
ita.MA11.tag	ita.NA07.tag	spa.MdtmILON.tag
ita.MA12.tag	ita.NA08.tag	spa.MdtmIMRC.tag

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

spa.PESPIANU.tag	ger.FRTEIWOL.tag	ger.P1TEIFRI.tag
spa.PESPIASU.tag	ger.MDTMIANT.tag	ger.P1TEIGIS.tag
spa.PESPIRAQ.tag	ger.MTTEIALE.tag	ger.P1TEIHER.tag
spa.POSPIASU.tag	ger.MTTEIANG.tag	ger.P1TEIKAR.tag
spa.PersILEO.tag	ger.MTTEICHR.tag	ger.P1TEINEW.tag
spa.PersIMRC.tag	ger.MTTEICLA.tag	ger.P1TEISEL.tag
ger.FROGIANT.tag	ger.MTTEICOR.tag	ger.P1TEISIM.tag
ger.FROGINAT.tag	ger.MTTEIFRA.tag	ger.P1TEISUS.tag
ger.FRTEIALE.tag	ger.MTTEIGIS.tag	ger.P1TEIWOL.tag
ger.FRTEIANG.tag	ger.MTTEIKAR.tag	ger.P2TEIALE.tag
ger.FRTEICHR.tag	ger.MTTEIMAR.tag	ger.P2TEICOR.tag
ger.FRTEICLA.tag	ger.MTTEINAT.tag	ger.P2TEIFRA.tag
ger.FRTEICOR.tag	ger.MTTEISEL.tag	ger.P2TEIKAR.tag
ger.FRTEIFRA.tag	ger.MTTEISIM.tag	ger.PERS1NAT.tag
ger.FRTEIFRI.tag	ger.MTTEISUS.tag	ger.PERS1WIL.tag
ger.FRTEIGIS.tag	ger.MTTEIWIL.tag	ger.POTEIALE.tag
ger.FRTEIHER.tag	ger.MTTEIWOL.tag	ger.POTEICHR.tag
ger.FRTEIKAR.tag	ger.P1TEIALE.tag	ger.POTEICOR.tag
ger.FRTEINEW.tag	ger.P1TEIANG.tag	ger.POTEIFRA.tag
ger.FRTEISEL.tag	ger.P1TEICHR.tag	ger.POTEIGIS.tag
ger.FRTEISIM.tag	ger.P1TEICLA.tag	ger.POTEIHER.tag
ger.FRTEISUS.tag	ger.P1TEICOR.tag	ger.POTEIKAR.tag
ger.FRTEIWIL.tag	ger.P1TEIFRA.tag	ger.POTEIWOL.tag

F.2 Quantitative analysis

F.2.1 Bi-grams - first 20

Table F.1: First 20 more frequent bi-grams in SPA

ART NOUN	8644	1184	3882	0.03898	0.06392	0.06838
CLI VER:fin	5646	484	896	0.02546	0.02613	0.01578
AUX:fin VER:ppast	4424	431	1232	0.01995	0.02327	0.02170
VER:fin ART	3664	426	1297	0.01652	0.02300	0.02284
NOUN PRE	3828	371	1036	0.01726	0.02003	0.01825
PRE ART	1478	344	795	0.00667	0.01857	0.01400
NOUN VER:fin	2510	339	1077	0.01132	0.01830	0.01897
VER:fin PRE	2138	336	702	0.00964	0.01814	0.01236
PRE NOUN	4106	329	874	0.01852	0.01776	0.01539
ARTPRE NOUN	3166	325	1211	0.01428	0.01755	0.02133
NOUN ADJ	2752	269	633	0.01241	0.01452	0.01115
NOUN SENT	5116	257	1521	0.02307	0.01387	0.02679
NOUN CON	1568	256	1371	0.00707	0.01382	0.02415
VER:fin ADV	3966	223	1004	0.01789	0.01204	0.01768
VER:fin ADJ	1758	215	387	0.00793	0.01161	0.00682
CHE VER:fin	1344	215	334	0.00606	0.01161	0.00588
PRE VER:infi	1428	215	455	0.00644	0.01161	0.00801
ADJ NOUN	1510	214	523	0.00681	0.01155	0.00921
NOUN CHE	1348	209	380	0.00608	0.01128	0.00669
VER:fin NOUN	1742	188	428	0.00786	0.01015	0.00754

F.2.2 Trigrams - first 20

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

Table F.2: First 20 more frequent bi-grams in GER

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
ART NOUN	8644	1184	3882	0.03898	0.06392	0.06838
NOUN SENT	5116	257	1521	0.02307	0.01387	0.02679
NOUN CON	1568	256	1371	0.00707	0.01382	0.02415
VER:fin ART	3664	426	1297	0.01652	0.02300	0.02284
AUX:fin VER:ppast	4424	431	1232	0.01995	0.02327	0.02170
ARTPRE NOUN	3166	325	1211	0.01428	0.01755	0.02133
NOUN VER:fin	2510	339	1077	0.01132	0.01830	0.01897
NOUN PRE	3828	371	1036	0.01726	0.02003	0.01825
SENT CON	1600	161	1024	0.00722	0.00869	0.01804
VER:fin ADV	3966	223	1004	0.01789	0.01204	0.01768
CLI VER:fin	5646	484	896	0.02546	0.02613	0.01578
PRE NOUN	4106	329	874	0.01852	0.01776	0.01539
PRE ART	1478	344	795	0.00667	0.01857	0.01400
SENT ADV	5392	104	711	0.02432	0.00561	0.01252
VER:fin PRE	2138	336	702	0.00964	0.01814	0.01236
NOUN ADJ	2752	269	633	0.01241	0.01452	0.01115
CON VER:fin	898	174	626	0.00405	0.00939	0.01103
CON ADV	1458	103	616	0.00658	0.00556	0.01085
DET:demo NOUN	1294	76	601	0.00584	0.00410	0.01059
ADV SENT	3892	107	581	0.01755	0.00578	0.01023

F.3 Results – Tag Unigrams

F.3.1 Tabular Results

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
ita.FA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A

F.3 Results – Tag Unigrams

ita.FA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA10.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA14.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA14.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA15.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA16.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA17.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA18.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA19.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA20.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA21.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA22.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA23.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA24.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA25.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA26.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA27.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA28.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA29.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

ita.MA30.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA10.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A

Table F.5: Results for ita

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
spa.FRSPIANU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIASU.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
spa.FRSPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag	spa	0.0005	0.001	B
spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FrogILEO.tag	spa	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.FrogILEO.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIANU.tag	spa	0.001	0.0025	C
spa.MTSPIANU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

F.3 Results – Tag Unigrams

spa.MTSPIASU.tag	spa	0.001	0.0025	C
spa.MTSPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIALA.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIALA.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
spa.MdtmIDAM.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
spa.MdtmIDAM.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
spa.MdtmILEO.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILEO.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILON.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
spa.MdtmILON.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
spa.MdtmIMRC.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.PESPIANU.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
spa.PESPIASU.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
spa.POSPIASU.tag	spa	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.PersIMRC.tag	ita	0.0025	0.005	D

Table F.6: Results for spa

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
ger.FROGIANT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FROGINAT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIANG.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIFRI.tag	ita	0.025	0.05	G
ger.FRTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIHER.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEINEW.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEISEL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEISIM.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

ger.FRTEISUS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIWIL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MDTMIANT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIANG.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICLA.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.MTTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIMAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEINAT.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.MTTEISEL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEISIM.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEISUS.tag	ger	0.005	0.01	E
ger.MTTEIWIL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEIANG.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.P1TEICHR.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.P1TEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEICOR.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEIFRA.tag	ita	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.P1TEIFRI.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.P1TEIGIS.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.P1TEIHER.tag	ger	0.005	0.01	E
ger.P1TEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEINEW.tag	ita	0.005	0.01	E
ger.P1TEISEL.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.P1TEISUS.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEIWOL.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.P2TEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P2TEIFRA.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.P2TEIKAR.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.PERS1NAT.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.PERS1WIL.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.POTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

F.3 Results – Tag Unigrams

ger.POTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.POTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIHER.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

Table F.7: Results for ger

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

Table F.3: First 20 more frequent bi-grams in SPA

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
VER:fin ART NOUN	2578	305	923	0.0116260	0.0164669	0.0162577
PRE ART NOUN	1010	250	545	0.0045548	0.0134975	0.0095996
ART NOUN PRE	1464	191	453	0.0066022	0.0103121	0.0079791
ART NOUN VER:fin	806	147	495	0.0036348	0.0079365	0.0087189
NOUN PRE NOUN	1620	113	323	0.0073057	0.0061009	0.0056893
ART NOUN CON	402	109	550	0.0018129	0.0058849	0.0096877
ART NOUN CHE	478	104	183	0.0021556	0.0056149	0.0032234
AUX:fin VER:ppast PRE	642	94	161	0.0028952	0.0050750	0.0028359
NOUN CHE VER:fin	410	89	155	0.0018490	0.0048051	0.0027302
ART NOUN ADJ	986	87	279	0.0044465	0.0046971	0.0049143
AUX:fin VER:ppast ART	648	85	287	0.0029223	0.0045891	0.0050552
ART NOUN SENT	1236	85	515	0.0055740	0.0045891	0.0090712
VER:infi ART NOUN	686	83	203	0.0030936	0.0044812	0.0035756
NOUN ART NOUN	502	82	260	0.0022639	0.0044272	0.0045796
NOUN PRE ART	408	82	216	0.0018400	0.0044272	0.0038046
VER:ppast ART NOUN	556	81	250	0.0025074	0.0043732	0.0044035
NOUN ARTPRE NOUN	1058	79	350	0.0047712	0.0042652	0.0061649
VER:fin PRE ART	206	77	142	0.0009290	0.0041572	0.0025012
CLI VER:fin ART	722	72	131	0.0032560	0.0038873	0.0023074
VER:fin PRE VER:infi	432	71	148	0.0019482	0.0038333	0.0026069

Table F.4: First 20 more frequent bi-grams in GER

	Absoulte values			Relative values		
	ITA	SPA	GER	ITA	SPA	GER
VER:fin ART NOUN	2578	305	923	0.0116260	0.0164669	0.0162577
ART NOUN CON	402	109	550	0.0018129	0.0058849	0.0096877
NOUN SENT CON	392	66	548	0.0017678	0.0035633	0.0096525
PRE ART NOUN	1010	250	545	0.0045548	0.0134975	0.0095996
ART NOUN SENT	1236	85	515	0.0055740	0.0045891	0.0090712
ART NOUN VER:fin	806	147	495	0.0036348	0.0079365	0.0087189
ART NOUN PRE	1464	191	453	0.0066022	0.0103121	0.0079791
ADV ART NOUN	1016	50	360	0.0045818	0.0026995	0.0063410
CON ART NOUN	288	60	352	0.0012988	0.0032394	0.0062001
NOUN ARTPRE NOUN	1058	79	350	0.0047712	0.0042652	0.0061649
NOUN PRE NOUN	1620	113	323	0.0073057	0.0061009	0.0056893
AUX:fin VER:ppast ART	648	85	287	0.0029223	0.0045891	0.0050552
ART NOUN ADJ	986	87	279	0.0044465	0.0046971	0.0049143
ARTPRE NOUN SENT	510	37	269	0.0022999	0.0019976	0.0047382
PRE DET:demo NOUN	508	28	268	0.0022909	0.0015117	0.0047206
NOUN ART NOUN	502	82	260	0.0022639	0.0044272	0.0045796
VER:ppast ART NOUN	556	81	250	0.0025074	0.0043732	0.0044035
ART ART NOUN	114	40	248	0.0005141	0.0021596	0.0043683
ARTPRE NOUN CON	170	41	246	0.0007666	0.0022136	0.0043330
NOUN SENT ADV	1416	23	246	0.0063857	0.0012418	0.0043330

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

Summary of MannWhitneyOutput		
Category	Significance Value	Total Comparisons
A	$0.00025 < p < 0.0005$	116
B	$0.0005 < p < 0.001$	5
C	$0.001 < p < 0.0025$	7
D	$0.0025 < p < 0.005$	8
E	$0.005 < p < 0.01$	3
F	$0.01 < p < 0.025$	4
G	$0.025 < p < 0.05$	7
Other	$0.05 < p < 1.0$	291
Total Comparisons		441

Table F.8: Summary of Results

F.4 Results – Tag Bigrams

F.4.1 Tabular Results

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
ita.FA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA10.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA14.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA07.tag	ita	0.0025	0.005	D
ita.MA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA10.tag	ita	0.025	0.05	G
ita.MA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA14.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA15.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA16.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA17.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA18.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA19.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA20.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

ita.MA21.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA22.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA23.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA24.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA25.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA26.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA27.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA28.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA29.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA30.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA10.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A

Table F.9: Results for ita

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category

F.4 Results – Tag Bigrams

spa.FRSPIANU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIASU.tag	spa	0.0005	0.001	B
spa.FRSPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FrogILEO.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FrogILEO.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIANU.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIANU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIASU.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag	spa	0.001	0.0025	C
spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIALA.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIALA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIDAM.tag	spa	0.0005	0.001	B
spa.MdtmIDAM.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
spa.MdtmILEO.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILEO.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILON.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILON.tag	ger	0.005	0.01	E
spa.MdtmIMRC.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.PESPIANU.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
spa.PESPIANU.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
spa.PESPIASU.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
spa.PESPIASU.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
spa.PESPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
spa.POSPIASU.tag	spa	0.001	0.0025	C

Table F.10: Results for spa

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
ger.FROGIANT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FROGINAT.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
ger.FROGINAT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

ger.FRTEIANG.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICOR.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
ger.FRTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIFRI.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.FRTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIHER.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEINEW.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEISEL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEISIM.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEISUS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIWIL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MDTMIANT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIANG.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIMAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEINAT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEISEL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEISIM.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEISUS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIWIL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEIALE.tag	ger	0.005	0.01	E
ger.P1TEIANG.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.P1TEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEICOR.tag	ita	0.01	0.025	F
ger.P1TEIFRA.tag	ita	0.01	0.025	F
ger.P1TEIGIS.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F

F.4 Results – Tag Bigrams

ger.P1TEIHER.tag	ger	0.005	0.01	E
ger.P1TEIKAR.tag	ita	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.P1TEINEW.tag	ita	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.P1TEISEL.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.P1TEISUS.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEIWOL.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.P2TEIALE.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.P2TEICOR.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
ger.P2TEIKAR.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.POTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIHER.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.POTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

Table F.11: Results for ger

Summary of MannWhitneyOutput		
Category	Significance Value	Total Comparisons
A	$0.00025 < p < 0.0005$	123
B	$0.0005 < p < 0.001$	2
C	$0.001 < p < 0.0025$	4
D	$0.0025 < p < 0.005$	5
E	$0.005 < p < 0.01$	3
F	$0.01 < p < 0.025$	5
G	$0.025 < p < 0.05$	12
Other	$0.05 < p < 1.0$	287
Total Comparisons		441

Table F.12: Summary of Results

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

F.5 Results – Tag Trigrams

F.5.1 Tabular Results

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
ita.FA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA10.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.FA14.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA11.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA14.tag	ita	0.0025	0.005	D
ita.MA15.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA16.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA17.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA18.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA19.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA20.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA21.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A

F.5 Results – Tag Trigrams

ita.MA22.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA23.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA24.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA25.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA26.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA27.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA28.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA29.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.MA30.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA01.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA09.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA10.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA11.tag	ita	0.001	0.0025	C
ita.NA12.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.NA13.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA01.tag	ita	0.001	0.0025	C
ita.RA02.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA03.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA04.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA05.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA06.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA07.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA08.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ita.RA09.tag	ita	0.0025	0.005	D

Table F.13: Results for ita Part 2

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
spa.FRSPIANU.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F

F. N-GRAM ANALYSIS RESULTS - FULL TABLES

spa.FRSPIANU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIASU.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FRSPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.FrogILEO.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.FrogILEO.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
spa.MTSPIANU.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIANU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIASU.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MTSPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIALA.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIALA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmIDAM.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILEO.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILEO.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.MdtmILON.tag	spa	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.MdtmILON.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
spa.MdtmIMRC.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
spa.MdtmIMRC.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
spa.PESPIANU.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
spa.PESPIASU.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
spa.PESPIASU.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
spa.PESPIRAQ.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
spa.POSPIASU.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
spa.PersILEO.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F

Table F.14: Results for spa

Results				
Filename	Assigned	P Value>	P Value<	Category
ger.FROGIANT.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
ger.FROGIANT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FROGINAT.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
ger.FROGINAT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A

F.5 Results – Tag Trigrams

ger.FRTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEICOR.tag	spa	0.005	0.01	E
ger.FRTEICOR.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.FRTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIFRI.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
ger.FRTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIHER.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.FRTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
ger.FRTEISEL.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.FRTEISIM.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.FRTEIWIL.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
ger.FRTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MDTMIANT.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
ger.MDTMIANT.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIALE.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
ger.MTTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIANG.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICHR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICLA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIFRA.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
ger.MTTEIFRA.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIGIS.tag	spa	0.025	0.05	G
ger.MTTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIMAR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEINAT.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.MTTEISEL.tag	ger	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.MTTEISIM.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEISUS.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIWIL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.MTTEIWOL.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEIALE.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.P1TEICHR.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.P1TEICLA.tag	ger	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.P1TEIFRA.tag	ita	0.001	0.0025	C
ger.P1TEIFRI.tag	ita	0.005	0.01	E

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ger.P1TEIHER.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
ger.P1TEIKAR.tag	ita	0.0005	0.001	B
ger.P1TEINEW.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P1TEISUS.tag	ita	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.P2TEICOR.tag	ger	0.025	0.05	G
ger.POTEIALE.tag	spa	0.01	0.025	F
ger.POTEIALE.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEICHR.tag	ger	0.01	0.025	F
ger.POTEICOR.tag	ger	0.00025	0.0005	A
ger.POTEIGIS.tag	ger	0.0025	0.005	D
ger.POTEIKAR.tag	ger	0.005	0.01	E

Table F.15: Results for ger

Summary of MannWhitneyOutput		
Category	Significance Value	Total Comparisons
A	$0.00025 < p < 0.0005$	105
B	$0.0005 < p < 0.001$	4
C	$0.001 < p < 0.0025$	5
D	$0.0025 < p < 0.005$	9
E	$0.005 < p < 0.01$	3
F	$0.01 < p < 0.025$	14
G	$0.025 < p < 0.05$	8
Other	$0.05 < p < 1.0$	293
Total Comparisons		441

Table F.16: Summary of Results

Appendix G

Multidimensional Scaling

G.1 The problem

In our clustering algorithm we face the problem of working with data whose true state is potentially highly dimensional. This happens because the distance that we measure between each pair of files is not the representation of a metric value, such as a distance in kilometers between two points, but rather a non metric and potentially non euclidean value.¹

Because of the nature of our data, which is a symmetrical matrix describing similarity distances between texts, a good way to report on the data would be through the use of 2-dimensional plots. However multidimensional data cannot be effectively plotted in a straightforward manner without serious data corruption.

The literature shows that there are solutions for this problem in the form of dimensionality reduction, with the goal to be able to plot the data in only 2 dimensions while keeping the loss of accuracy to the minimum.

The multidimensional scaling (MDS) algorithm takes a matrix of distances as input and transforms it in a set of coordinates that represent an n-dimensional space. Yet the required number of dimensions may not be sufficient to completely describe the matrix. In this case the algorithm outputs a measure, goodness of fit (GOF) that expresses the overall mismatch between the distances in the input matrix and those derivable from the output.

¹The outline of this appendix is the result of a week of intense work with Jerom Jennsen, of the Trinity College Dublin, to whom I take the opportunity to express my deepest gratitude

G. MULTIDIMENSIONAL SCALING

Two examples of MDS are given here; in the first case we have a cube of size $1 \times 1 \times 1$, from which we derive a distance matrix listing the distance between each of its point. When trying to scale the matrix in 2 dimensions we expect the loss of $1/3$ of the informations; the goodness of fit is 66 % and the cube is not recognizable when plotted in 2 dimensions. In the second case a 2 dimensional data set is used instead, the distances between European cities. In this case, when scaling the matrix in 2 dimensions, the plot we obtain is recognizable as a flipped map of Europe.

The built-in MDS algorithm in R was used for the present work; the *mdscale* function requires to set the number of dimensions, and also to enable/disable an additive value (ADD) for adjustment. Here we report the results with and without ADD value; for the data of chapter 6 ADD was set to true.

For each example the R code is given to import, scale and plot the data. The same code was used to plot the distances between files in chapter 6, but due to the wideness of the matrix, it is impossible to print the data here.

Note that in the plotted MDS output, the two dimensions do not represent any feature of the data; only the overall picture is important.

G.1.1 Cube

```
> matrix(data = loc, nrow = 8, ncol = 8, byrow = FALSE, dimnames = NULL)
      [,1] [,2] [,3] [,4] [,5] [,6] [,7] [,8]
[1,] 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214
[2,] 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051
[3,] 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214
[4,] 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000
[5,] 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000
[6,] 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214
[7,] 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000
[8,] 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000
```

G.1.1.1 MDS with Add=FALSE

```
> cube
      [,1] [,2] [,3] [,4] [,5] [,6] [,7] [,8]
```

G.1 The problem

```
[1,] 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214
[2,] 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051
[3,] 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214
[4,] 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000
[5,] 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000
[6,] 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214 1.732051 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000 1.414214
[7,] 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000 1.414214 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000 1.000000
[8,] 1.414214 1.732051 1.414214 1.000000 1.000000 1.414214 1.000000 0.000000
```

```
> cmdscale(cube, k=2, add = FALSE, eig = TRUE)
```

```
$points
```

```
      [,1]      [,2]
[1,] -0.8660254 0.000000e+00
[2,] -0.2886751 8.089397e-01
[3,] 0.2886751 3.084883e-01
[4,] -0.2886751 -5.004514e-01
[5,] -0.2886751 -3.084883e-01
[6,] 0.2886751 5.004514e-01
[7,] 0.8660254 2.355139e-16
[8,] 0.2886751 -8.089397e-01
```

```
$eig
```

```
[1] 2 2
```

```
$x
```

```
NULL
```

```
$ac
```

```
[1] 0
```

```
$GOF
```

```
[1] 0.6666667 0.6666667
```


Figure G.1: Cube, ADD=false - Scaled cube plot without additive value

G.1.1.2 Add=TRUE

```
> cmdscale(cube, k=2, add = TRUE, eig = TRUE)
```

```
$points
```

```
          [,1]      [,2]
[1,]  0.000000e+00  0.8660254
[2,] -5.827007e-01  0.2886751
[3,]  2.039728e-01 -0.2886751
[4,]  7.866734e-01  0.2886751
[5,] -2.039728e-01  0.2886751
[6,] -7.866734e-01 -0.2886751
[7,] -6.280370e-16 -0.8660254
[8,]  5.827007e-01 -0.2886751
```

```
$eig
```

```
[1] 2 2
```

```
$x
```

```
NULL
```

```
$ac
```

```
[1] 4.317118e-15
```

```
$GOF
```

```
[1] 0.6666667 0.6666667
```


Figure G.2: Cube, ADD=true - Scaled cube plot with additive value

G.1.2 Eurodist

Eurodist is a built in matrix in R, that gives the distances between 23 european capitals.

G.1.2.1 Add=FALSE

```
> cmdscale(eurodist, k=2, add = FALSE, eig = TRUE)
```

```
$points
```

	[,1]	[,2]
Athens	2290.274680	1798.80293
Barcelona	-825.382790	546.81148
Brussels	59.183341	-367.08135
Calais	-82.845973	-429.91466
Cherbourg	-352.499435	-290.90843
Cologne	293.689633	-405.31194
Copenhagen	681.931545	-1108.64478
Geneva	-9.423364	240.40600
Gibraltar	-2048.449113	642.45854
Hamburg	561.108970	-773.36929
Hook of Holland	164.921799	-549.36704
Lisbon	-1935.040811	49.12514
Lyons	-226.423236	187.08779
Madrid	-1423.353697	305.87513
Marseilles	-299.498710	388.80726
Milan	260.878046	416.67381
Munich	587.675679	81.18224
Paris	-156.836257	-211.13911
Rome	709.413282	1109.36665
Stockholm	839.445911	-1836.79055
Vienna	911.230500	205.93020

```
$eig
```

```
[1] 19538377 11856555
```

```
$x
```

```
NULL
```

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\$ac

[1] 0

\$GOF

[1] 0.7968344 0.8679134

Figure G.3: Eurodist, ADD=false - Scaled Eurodist plot without additive value

G.1.2.2 Add=TRUE

```
> cmdscale(eurodist, k=2, add = TRUE, eig = TRUE)
```

```
$points
```

```
          [,1]      [,2]
[1,] -2716.561820  3549.216493
[2,]  1453.753109  455.895291
[3,]  -217.426476 -1073.442137
[4,]   -1.682974 -1135.742982
[5,]   461.875781 -871.913389
[6,]  -594.256798 -1029.818247
[7,] -1271.216005 -1622.039302
[8,]   88.721376   4.068005
[9,]  3059.180990  836.535103
[10,] -1056.316198 -1350.037932
[11,]  -445.663432 -1304.392098
[12,]  2866.160085  211.043554
[13,]  436.147722 -140.147837
[14,]  2300.753691  234.863677
[15,]   586.877042  217.428075
[16,]  -336.906562  350.948939
[17,]  -928.407679 -112.132182
[18,]   193.653844 -847.157498
[19,]  -908.682100  1742.395923
[20,] -1499.140467 -1897.522865
[21,] -1319.918808  295.010834
```

```
$eig
```

```
[1] 42274974 31666186
```

```
$x
```

```
NULL
```

```
$ac
```

```
[1] 2132.678
```

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\$GOF

[1] 0.4886298 0.4886298

Figure G.4: Cube, ADD=true - Scaled Eurodist plot with additive value